

D6.4 - Final Exploitation Roadmap including Business Plan and IPR report

WP6 - Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation

T6.4 - Exploitation of Project Results

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ABBREVIATIONS AND ACRONYMS

ADR/Open ADR	Automated Demand Response
AI	Artificial Intelligence
ANSI	American National Standards Institute
API	Application Programming Interface
ASF	Apache Software Foundation
ATS (Test)	Automatic Transfer Switch Test
BESS	Battery Energy Storage System
BSD (License)	Berkeley Software Distribution License
CAN	Controller Area Network
CAPEX	Capital Expenditures
CE (Marking)	Conformité Européenne
CUPID	Controllable Unit Protocol Interface for Distributed Energy Resources
DES	Distributed Energy Storage
DER	Distributed Energy Resource
DSC	Data Space Connector
DSO	Distribution System Operator
DSOs	Distribution System Operators
EMS	Energy Management System
ESCO	Energy Service Company
ESG	Environmental, Social and Governance
EV	Electric Vehicle
GA	Grant Agreement
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GHG	Greenhouse Gas
GPL	GNU General Public License
GPL-LE	GNU General Public License - Linking Exception
HESS	Hybrid Energy Storage System
HEU	Horizon Europe
HMS	Home/Household Energy Management System
HTTP	HyperText Transfer Protocol
HW	Hardware
IAB	International Advisory Board
ICT	Information and Communications Technology
IEC	International Electrotechnical Commission
IDS	International Data Spaces
IEEE	Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers
IP	Intellectual Property
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
ISA	International Society of Automation
IT	Information Technology
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
JAR	Java ARchive
KER	Key Exploitable Result
LFE	Linux Foundation Energy

LGPL	GNU Lesser General Public License
LPC	Legacy Protocol Converter
MQTT	Message Queuing Telemetry Transport
MIT (Li- cense)	Massachusetts Institute of Technology License
NATS	High-Performance Cloud Native Messaging System
NEMA	National Electrical Manufacturers Association
OEM	Original Equipment Manufacturer
PEST	Political, Economic, Social, Technological
PV	Photovoltaic
REC	Renewable Energy Community
RES	Renewable Energy Sources
ROI	Return on Investment
SAE	Society of Automotive Engineers
SC	Subcommittee
SEP 2	Smart Energy Profile 2.0
SSbD	Safe and Sustainable by Design
SWOT	Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, Threats
TC	Technical Committee
TLBMC	Triple-Layered Business Model Canvas
TPST	Testing Protocol Software Tool
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
TSO	Transmission System Operator
UC	Use Case
UCs	Use Cases
UL	Underwriters Laboratories
USNC	United States National Committee (to IEC)
VPP	Virtual Power Plant
WP	Work Package
XML	eXtensible Markup Language

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Executive Summary

This deliverable - **D6.4 Final Exploitation Roadmap including Business Plan and IPR Report** - presents the updated and consolidated strategy for the **exploitation, business deployment, and long-term sustainability** of the InterSTORE project results. It directly builds upon the initial strategy outlined in D6.3 (Initial Exploitation Plan and IPR report) and expands it with new evidence gathered from two structured surveys and the final business model analysis of all InterSTORE use cases.

The document is structured around five complementary pillars:

1. Updated Exploitation Strategy and Plan - consolidating evidence collected through two dedicated surveys: one completed by each Key Exploitable Result (KER) owner, assessing ownership, protection, exploitation readiness, and next steps, and a second completed by Use Case (UC) leaders, evaluating the performance, relevance, and real-world applicability of each KER. This dual perspective ensures that exploitation planning is both technically grounded and market-informed.
2. Business Model and Business Plan - articulating how InterSTORE creates economic, social, and environmental value by applying a Triple Layered Business Model Canvas (TLBMC) across all UCs, while explicitly mapping each KER to concrete market opportunities and stakeholder needs.
3. Knowledge, Data, and Intellectual Property (IPR) Management - defining a robust framework for knowledge, data, and Intellectual Property (IP) management, balancing open-source continuity with clear ownership, licensing, and access-right arrangements fully aligned with Horizon Europe requirements.
4. Standardisation and Alignment with Global Frameworks - summarising how InterSTORE contributes to recognised interoperability standards, ensuring its tools remain compatible with Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers (IEEE) 2030.5, FIWARE, and emerging European data-space frameworks.
5. Conclusion on Marketing and Stakeholder Engagement Strategy - outlining actions for promoting adoption through collaboration with key international organisations, notably the Linux Foundation Energy (LFE), the SunSpec Alliance, and the IEEE 2030.5 community.

Table 1 D6.4 structure

InterSTORE has delivered **four complementary, open-source KERs** that together address interoperability, legacy integration, quality assurance and trusted data exchange in digitalised energy systems. Validated in real operational environments, the KERs form a coherent toolkit enabling scalable, vendor-neutral and secure deployment of flexibility, storage and EV-centric services across diverse grid contexts.

KER1 - Interoperable client/server library - and **KER2 - Legacy Protocol Converter (LPC)** - provide the technical backbone for interoperability and brownfield integration, showing consistently high relevance across most UCs, particularly those focused on flexibility monetisation, energy communities, advanced BESS operation and innovative frequency services. **KER3 - Testing Protocol Software Tool (TPST)** complements this stack by ensuring reliability and market readiness of IEEE 2030.5 implementations, with strongest impact in EV- and HESS-centric applications where conformance and validation are critical. **KER4 - Data Space Connector (DSC)** - enables trusted, governed and traceable data exchange, proving essential in data-intensive UCs involving hybrid storage, EV charging clusters and advanced flexibility coordination.

Overall, the combined application of the four KERs demonstrates strong exploitation potential across all nine UCs, with varying degrees of relevance reflecting the specific technical, market and governance needs of each context. This modular applicability underpins InterSTORE's capacity to support scalable replication, cross-sector integration and long-term market uptake in line with EU digitalisation and energy transition objectives. The integration of its tools within recognised global initiatives and the transition toward the CUPID framework ensure that the project's innovations will continue to evolve, be adopted, and generate measurable impact for Europe's smart and flexible energy systems.

1 Introduction

This deliverable, presents the **final and consolidated strategy for the exploitation of the InterSTORE project results**. It builds upon D6.3, which identified the project's exploitable outcomes, leading partners, related background and foreground IPR, and preliminary protection and ownership measures.

While D6.3 provided the foundation, this final roadmap expands the analysis by integrating the findings from two dedicated surveys conducted among project partners. The first survey, addressed to each KER owner, focused on IP identification, ownership, protection strategies, and future exploitation plans. The second survey, completed by each UC leader, assessed the performance, relevance, and market potential of each KER based on real implementation feedback. Together, these surveys provide an evidence-based assessment of the technological maturity, market readiness, and exploitation pathways of all InterSTORE results.

The deliverable outlines how InterSTORE's open-source software tools - developed to ensure interoperability, standardisation, and data sovereignty across distributed energy systems - will be maintained, scaled, and adopted beyond the project's lifetime. The results are framed around the project's four KERs, covering:

- **IEEE 2030.5-based interoperability between devices and EMS,**
- **legacy protocol conversion for brownfield assets,**
- **automated testing and quality assurance,**
- **and secure data-space-based exchange and governance.**

Finally, this report defines the business models, stakeholder engagement strategy, and IPR framework that underpin the project's sustainability. It also describes how InterSTORE's outcomes will continue under the **LFE** as part of the **CUPID** open-source portfolio - ensuring long-term visibility, scalability, and contribution to Europe's interoperable and decentralised energy ecosystem.

2 Updated Exploitation Strategy and Plan

InterSTORE updated exploitation strategy and plan build directly on the previous plan (Deliverable D6.3 - Initial Exploitation Plan and IPR report) and expand it through a structured evidence-based approach. **The update has been informed by two complementary surveys – hosted on SoSci Survey [1] by RWTH** – designed to assess the current status, performance, relevance and exploitation potential of the InterSTORE KERs.

The first survey – addressed to each KER owner – **gathered detailed information on the exploitation strategy, characterisation, IPR management, and planned post-project actions.** This questionnaire, structured in thematic sections (e.g., exploitation overview, commercial strategy, development phase, stakeholders' interests and power, IPR, expected impacts), follows standard methodologies of exploitation strategy and roadmaps definition in Horizon Europe projects. **The second survey** was distributed via SoSci Survey to all UC owners – where KERs have been tested – **to collect feedback on the relevance, performance, integration, and market potential of each KER when applied in real operational contexts.** UC owners were also invited to provide recommendations for improvement and a comparative assessment of all KERs.

Both questionnaires – whose MS Word version is provided in Annex 8.1 and 8.2 for full transparency – served as the main input sources for this chapter, allowing a cross-analysis between KER providers and end users. The results form the basis for the updated exploitation roadmap, highlighting priorities, market readiness levels, and concrete post-project actions to ensure long-term uptake of InterSTORE solutions.

2.1 KER1: Interoperable client/server library

InterSTORE first KER is an interoperable client/server software library that enables IEEE 2030.5 communication between devices and EMS systems over Neural Advanced Transport System (NATS). This library has the following features:

- It offers open-source, out-of-the-box support for IEEE 2030.5 messages in both Extensible Markup Language (XML) and JavaScript Object Notation (JSON) formats.
- It leverages next-generation NATS messaging as a communication protocol, providing superior performance, scalability, and reliability compared to other protocols.
- It includes a reference implementation as an open-source project, available for anyone to use and modify.

The ultimate aim of this interoperable client/server is to simplify the integration of IEEE 2030.5 devices and EMS systems and to encourage the adoption of this standard in the smart grid domain.

2.1.1 Exploitation Plan: KER1

SUN, WP2 leader, in agreement with InterSTORE consortium, has released the interoperable client/server software, under open-source Massachusetts Institute of Technology (MIT) license. The selection has been made after consulting with LFE, to assure the full engagement of the Open-Source Community on energy and the collection of feedback and continuous improvement, also after the project end, via [github: https://github.com/HorizontEurope-Interstore](https://github.com/HorizontEurope-Interstore).

The success of this tool is highly interconnected to the increased adoption of IEEE 2030.5 standard by additional countries and by the main energy and smart grid players, to enhance the software's usability and adoption.

Through the engagement of UC1-2-3-4-7-8-9 owners, the International Advisory Board (IAB) and through dedicated workshops in conjunction with the other funded projects under the same call (FLEXCHESS and PARMINEDES) InterSTORE collected user feedback and feature requests to guide future development and improvements. InterSTORE maintained a regular update cycle to address bugs, introduce new models' data models, and ensure the software remains relevant for the Use case (UC) owners, providing some customisation and up-to-date with industry standards.

2.1.1.1 *Exploitation Overview – KER1 Characterisation*

TRL: While having a Technology Readiness Level (TRL) of 2 at the beginning of InterSTORE, the library is estimated to reach TRL5/6 at the end of the project.

Brief Description: As detailed in previous paragraphs, this interoperable client/server library has been designed to provide an open source, out-of-the-box support for IEEE 2030.5 communication between devices and EMS.

Identification of the Problem/Need: This KER aims to respond to the need of integrating software libraries, open sourced under MIT licence, into devices or EMS systems to support IEEE 2030.5 over NATS.

Actors Involved: The main entities manifesting the need for this tool are private entities. This explains why partners such as CYG continuously participated in its development.

Type of Project Result: As detailed in the name itself, KER1 is to be classified as a software, with software libraries published on GitHub.

Temporality of Project Result: The effects of this result, therefore its impact, will be more visible in the long term and they highly depend on the success of fostering the inclusion of IEEE 2030.5 into products.

Exploitation Level: At its current status, the tool is moderately exploitable. SUN has already prepared the software libraries to be included into device firmware or EMS.

Development Phase: KER1 has already been developed, as mentioned above, but it is still to be fully exploited externally to the project. Up to this stage, the software has been exploited by CYG (CyberNOC).

Time to Exploitability: SUN expects KER1 to be fully ready for exploitation in less than one year (before the end of 2026), especially since IEEE 2030.5 popularity is spreading at a fast rate.

Exploitation Route: This KER is aimed at being technologically exploited by device and EMS manufacturers that need to include the software libraries for client/server.

Expected Commercial/Strategic Path for Deployment: For KER1 to be widely deployed, further development supported by research or government funding is necessary. The client/server software library could be further integrated into a broader commercial solution or service offering (e.g., bundled with hardware or platform from partners).

Geographical Scale: SUN sees the possibility for this tool being of interest to global audience.

Link to other KERs: The client/server software library is linked to KER2, the legacy system protocol converter, which is also owned by SUN, since the latter provides conversion of legacy protocols (ModBus, MQTT) to IEEE 2030.5.

2.1.1.2 Stakeholders Analysis

When looking at InterSTORE main stakeholders, the following ones play a primary and secondary role for the exploitation and further uptake of KER1, the interoperable client/server software library:

PRIMARY
<p>Industry Users (Organisations, SME, inverters' manufacturers, BESS manufacturers, Heat pump providers, etc.): In terms of their power-interest, SUN considers that it is appropriate to try to manage closely their needs. These entities are expected to have a high interest in incorporating IEEE 2030.5 into their products to foster interoperability. To ensure their engagement, it is important to focus on maximising the promotion of the client/server libraries.</p>
<p>Flexibility Service Providers (offering energy assets batteries, virtual power plant, energy transition service, ESCO, etc.): It is essential to keep them regularly informed on the development progress of the interoperable client/server software library, as it directly impacts their ability to integrate and manage flexible resources within evolving energy systems. According to SUN, it is very important to these stakeholders to use IEEE 2030.5 based protocols in order to enable value added services.</p>
<p>Regulatory Bodies and Standardisation (BRIDGE, 2ZeRo, InterConnect, Enershare, etc.): These stakeholders are primary and should have access to regular updates on the progress of this KER, as it contributes to shaping interoperability frameworks and supporting alignment with emerging standards in the energy sector. To ensure their engagement, it is therefore very important to focus on maximising the promotion of interoperability and new services with enabled IEEE 2030.5.</p>
<p>Academia & Research Institutions: The interoperable client/server software library represents a valuable asset for advancing research in energy system digitalisation and interoperability. It is important to keep them informed on its progress to foster collaboration opportunities, through open research questions and support knowledge transfer on IEEE 2030.5.</p>

Table 2 KER1 Primary stakeholders

SECONDARY
<p>End Users (energy communities' members, EV & Fleet owners, office's and campus employees, etc.): While end users are not directly concerned by this KER and may have only a secondary impact on its exploitation, it is still important to keep their needs and interests into account when further developing KER1. SUN expects them to be highly interested in staying informed on standards compliance and, in this case, IEEE 2030.5. To ensure their engagement, it is important to focus on maximising the promotion of IEEE 2030.5 and interoperability benefits.</p>

Transmission System Operator (TSO) (primary-secondary-tertiary reserve, Renewable Energy Sources (RES) integration, re-dispatch) & **Distribution System Operator (DSO)** (voltage level regulation, power quality, reactive power, integration of Renewable Energy Sources (RES)): Keeping these stakeholders informed on the development of such interoperable tools is important to secure alignment with energy transmission and distribution system's needs. Same as for end users, SUN expects these stakeholders to aim for being regularly informed on standards compliance, in this case IEEE 2030.5 and foster interoperability. To ensure their engagement, it is therefore very important to focus on maximising the promotion of interoperability and new services with enabled IEEE 2030.5.

Table 3 KER1 Secondary stakeholders

2.1.1.3 Exploitation Route Towards Impact

When looking at the expected impacts that InterSTORE is envisaged to contribute to in the long term, the contributions foreseen for KER1 are as follows: (i) KER1 is expected to make a moderate contribution to the achievement of industrial leadership in key and emerging technologies that work for people; (ii) a low-level contribution is expected towards the achievement of affordable and clean energy overall; (iii) however, the interoperable client/server software library is expected to highly contribute to securing, in the long term, a more efficient, clean, sustainable, secure and competitive energy supply through new solutions for smart grids and energy systems based on more performant renewable energy solutions. Looking forward, beyond InterSTORE duration, KER1 will contribute to these impacts by fostering the interoperability of devices and EMS and, hence, enabling new energy services and business models.

2.1.1.4 Actions to be taken Beyond the Project End

To ensure a successful further development, refinement and impactful uptake of the interoperable client/server software library, SUN will engage in strategic actions after InterSTORE end. At the current stage, this is the status of the different set of actions identification:

Immediate Actions: To ensure effective communication, training, and measurement of the KER in the early stages of implementation, SUN plans to conduct the following activities:

- Creating frameworks, guidelines, and tools based on research findings to facilitate the implementation and adoption of the new KER.
- Collaborate with internal and external stakeholders, to integrate the new KER into existing training programmes or initiatives.

Consolidation and Engagement Actions: To consolidate the gains made from the initial implementation and further engage stakeholders in the ongoing success of the new KER, SUN plans to conduct the following activities:

- Develop action plans based on feedback findings to address identified issues and capitalise on opportunities.
- Create multimedia materials such as videos, infographics, or presentations to visually communicate success stories and outcomes to a wider audience.

Expansion and Optimisation Actions: To optimise the implementation of the new KER and leverage external resources and expertise, for a maximised impact and reach, SUN plans to conduct the following activities:

- Scale up implementation efforts across relevant departments or teams by developing a roadmap for broader adoption and expansion.
- Identify additional areas or business units where the new KER can be applied and develop implementation plans tailored to each context.
- Provide ongoing training and support to employees to build capacity and confidence in implementing the new KER effectively.
- Explore opportunities for external collaboration or partnerships with other organisations, industry associations, or research institutions.

Monitoring and Adjustment Actions: To ensure that they effectively monitor performance, identify areas for improvement, and make timely adjustments to optimise outcomes and achieve strategic objectives, SUN plans to conduct the following activities:

- Conduct in-depth analyses of performance data to identify trends, patterns, and correlations that may inform strategic decisions and adjustments.
- Benchmark performance against industry standards, best practices, or competitors to gain insights into relative performance and identify areas for improvement.
- Document lessons learned, best practices, and recommendations from performance reviews to inform future planning and decision-making processes.

To carry out the above listed activities and progress towards TRL 9, including IP and legal requirements¹, SUN expects the cost's structure outlined in Table 6.

Activity	Sub-activity	Cost estimation range
IP and legal activities	None	None
Immediate Actions	Technical materials for potentials users; Technical demos, examples and guidelines	10.000-20.000 EUR
Consolidation and Engagement Actions	Engagement; Video, use-cases and other materials, conferences, fairs, etc.	15.000-30.000 EUR
Expansion and Optimisation Actions	Marketing and sales activities	50.000 EUR
Monitoring and Adjustment Actions	KPI monitoring and adjustments	20.000 EUR
Total		Around 100.000 EUR

Table 4 KER1 Cost structure of actions beyond project end

Sources of Coverage: SUN aims to cover the above-mentioned costs targeting (i) local/national public funds, (ii) business angels, (iii) private industries and (iv) other private investors.

2.1.2 Overall Feedback on performance from UCs: KER1

The evaluation of KER1 across multiple UCs has confirmed its strong technical performance, high interoperability, and valuable contribution to smart grid communication ecosystems,

¹ For IPR information, see section 4.3.1.

particularly in flexibility management and fast frequency services. **Use cases such as UC1, UC4, and UC7 demonstrated excellent or good operational outcomes, noting benefits in operational efficiency, product enhancement, and enabling new service models.** In these contexts, KER1 reliably bridged communication challenges and enabled IEEE 2030.5 integration through its open-source, NATS-based client/server library.

However, **the applicability of KER1 was uneven across the UCs**, being highly relevant for flexibility management and frequency services, but largely non-applicable in asset-centric or hardware-constrained scenarios like UC3, UC5, UC6, and UC9. This highlights a clear segmentation in its market potential - strongest among EMS operators, aggregators, and system operators managing fast, dynamic grid services, but less so for device manufacturers or operators requiring firmware-level solutions.

Market potential assessments varied by UC owner, but consensus emerged around existing barriers including low market readiness, competitive pressure from established proprietary protocols, and the novelty/effort trade-off for integration. Several actors, including CYG, CAP, and ENX, identified the need for improved ease of implementation, better documentation with varied use-case examples, and enhanced security features for NATS-based communication.

Notably, **KER1 consistently ranked among the top two or three exploitable results within InterSTORE activities**, with highest potential noted by UC1, UC4, UC7, and moderate to high market interest anticipated by most partners. Its exploitation potential would be further improved through actions such as packaging the library in a dockerised form, developing an automatic installer, enhancing its Safe and Sustainable by Design (SSbD) alignment, and proactively engaging standardisation bodies and system operators to accelerate adoption and market confidence.

In conclusion, KER1 has proven itself a **technically mature and highly interoperable solution with strong exploitation prospects in selected market segments**. Its future uptake depends on targeted refinements addressing ease of integration, security assurance, market awareness, and alignment with fast-moving digitalisation needs in grid flexibility services. More extensive feedback per each UC is provided in Annex 8.3.1.

2.2 KER2: Legacy system protocol converter

The LPC, is the second KER of InterSTORE project, this tool acts as a middleware that facilitates data exchange between devices using various communication protocols and EMS adhering to the IEEE 2030.5 standard. This KER has the following features:

- It supports multiple protocols: it handles IEEE 2030.5 messages in JSON and XML formats; it utilises next-generation NATS messaging for efficient communication, and translates MQTT and Modbus protocols into IEEE 2030.5 format.
- Built-in transformation framework: it allows users to define transformations for incoming messages to match the IEEE 2030.5 format, accommodating different device and system message formats.
- Flexible configuration: it uses a configuration file to specify connection details and transformations, supporting multiple message formats and structures for diverse applications.
- Versatile deployment: deployable via pre-built docker images, custom docker images, Java ARchive (JAR) files, or source code compilation, suitable for on-premise or cloud environments including Kubernetes, Docker, virtual machines, and bare-metal setups.

2.2.1 Exploitation Plan: KER2

The LPC ensures seamless message transformation between ModBus, MQTT, NATS, and IEEE 2030.5 XML and JSON assuring interoperability between devices and EMS, promoting the adoption of the IEEE 2030.5 standard in smart grid environments. Similarly to the client/server software library, the LPC has been released with MIT license: <https://github.com/Horizont-Europe-Interstore/Legacy-Protocol-Converter>.

InterSTORE has developed and promoted extensions plugins that enable seamless integration with existing tools and platforms used by target users. Docker Hub for direct access of

Docker images has also been made publicly available at <https://hub.docker.com/r/interstore/legacy-protocol-converter>. To promote the engagement and the adoption of the tool, dedicated tutorials and webinars have been recorded, since it is essential to educate users on how to deploy, configure, and integrate LPC into their systems to assure the adoption of the solution also after the project end and continuous development.

Collaboration with Industry Partners that are involved in the project has been assured through a co-design and co-development of the tool and ad hoc customisation has also been considered. Partnerships with the twin projects FLEXCHESS and PARMINEDES has also allowed to map new companies and organisations in the energy, IoT, and smart grid sectors that potentially might have an interest to integrate the LPC into their products and services.

Marketing and promotion have been assured by EASE and all the project partners through ad hoc events such as the participation to E-World 2024, ENLIT 2024, and through all InterSTORE UCs implementation in the 5 InterSTORE real-world pilot sites and by collecting success stories for marketing purposes.

2.2.1.1 Exploitation Overview - KER2 Characterisation

TRL: While having a TRL of 2 at the beginning of InterSTORE, the LPC is estimated to reach TRL6 at the end of the project.

Brief Description: As detailed in previous paragraphs, the LPC acts as a middleware, allowing devices that use different communication protocols to exchange data with EMS that use the IEEE 2030.5 standard.

Identification of the Problem/Need: This KER aims to respond to the technical need of transforming legacy protocols (Modbus, MQTT) to IEE2030.5.

Actors Involved: The main entities manifesting the need for this tool are private entities. This explains why SUN did the development and CYG regularly contributed to it.

Type of Project Result: KER2 is to be classified as open-sourced software.

Temporality of Project Result: The effects of this result, therefore its impact, will be more visible in the long term and, similarly to KER1, it highly depends on the success of fostering the inclusion of IEEE 2030.5 into products.

Exploitation Level: At its current status, the tool is highly exploitable. The LPC can already be used in any environment which currently uses ModBus or MQTT.

Development Phase: KER2 is already being exploited by InterSTORE partners and some other users.

Time to Exploitability: As mentioned above, the LPC is ready for usage and can be further exploited immediately after the project end (beginning of 2026).

Exploitation Route: The LPC is to be exploited technologically and exposed as open-source project on Github, to promote usage by device manufacturers and EMS providers.

Expected Commercial/Strategic Path for Deployment: For KER2 to be widely deployed, further development supported by research or government funding is necessary. This is the most obvious route, as the LPC itself is open sourced.

Geographical Scale: SUN sees a possibility for this tool being of interest to global audience.

Link to other KERs: The LPC has no direct link to any of the other KERs at current stage. However, there could be a potential link to KER1, since they both support IEEE 2030.5.

2.2.1.2 Stakeholders Analysis

When looking at InterSTORE main stakeholders, the following ones play a primary and secondary role for the exploitation and further uptake of KER2, the LPC:

PRIMARY
<p>Industry Users (Organisations, SME, inverters' manufacturers, BESS manufacturers, Heat pump providers, etc.): In terms of their power-interest, SUN considers that it is appropriate to try to manage closely their needs. These entities are expected to have a high interest in leveraging the LPC to convert older protocols, such as ModBus, MQTT to IEEE 2030.5. To ensure their engagement, it is important to inform them and support them in applying the LPC and contribute to its open-source use.</p>
<p>End Users (energy communities' members, EV & Fleet owners, office's and campus employees, etc.): End users are primarily concerned by this KER and it is important to keep them informed when further developing KER1. Similarly to industry users, these entities are expected to have a high interest in leveraging the LPC to convert older protocols, such as ModBus, MQTT to IEEE 2030.5. To ensure their engagement, it is important to inform them and support them in applying the LPC and contribute to its open-source use.</p>
<p>Flexibility Service Providers (offering energy assets batteries, virtual power plant, energy transition service, Energy Service Company (ESCO), etc.): It is essential to try to manage their needs when further developing the LPC as it directly impacts their ability to integrate and manage flexible resources within evolving energy systems. According to SUN they also need to be aware of the existing possibility to convert older protocols, such as Mod-Bus, MQTT to IEEE 2030.5. To ensure their engagement, it is important to inform them and support them in applying the LPC and contribute to its open-source use.</p>
<p>Regulatory Bodies and Standardisation (BRIDGE, 2ZeRo, InterConnect, Enershare, etc.): These stakeholders are primary and should have access to regular updates on the progress of this KER, as it contributes to shaping regulatory or policy frameworks based on the awareness that is it now possible to convert outdated protocols to IEEE 2030.5. To ensure their engagement, it is therefore very important to focus on maximising the promotion of the added value and efficiency of the LPC.</p>
<p>Academia & Research Institutions: The LPC represents a valuable asset for advancing research in energy system digitalisation. It is important to keep them informed on its progress to foster collaboration opportunities, through open research questions and support knowledge transfer on IEEE 2030.5.</p>

Table 5 KER2 Primary stakeholders

SECONDARY

Transmission System Operator (TSO) (primary-secondary-tertiary reserve, RES integration, re-dispatch) & Distribution System Operator (DSO) (voltage level regulation, power quality, reactive power, integration of RES): Keeping these stakeholders informed and their needs into account when further developing such converter is important to secure alignment with energy transmission and distribution system's needs. Therefore, they need to be aware of the existing possibility to convert older protocols, such as ModBus, MQTT to IEEE 2030.5. Continuous and transparent information is the best tool to keep them engaged.

Table 6 KER2 Secondary stakeholders

2.2.1.3 Exploitation Route Towards Impact

When looking at the expected impacts that InterSTORE is envisaged to contribute to in the long term, the contributions foreseen for KER2 are as follows: **(i)** KER2 is expected to make a moderate contribution to the achievement of industrial leadership in key and emerging technologies that work for people; **(ii)** a low-level contribution is expected towards the achievement of affordable and clean energy overall; **(iii)** however, the interoperable LPC is expected to highly contribute to securing, in the long term, a more efficient, clean, sustainable, secure and competitive energy supply through new solutions for smart grids and energy systems based on more performant renewable energy solutions. Looking forward, beyond InterSTORE duration, KER2 will contribute to these impacts by fostering interoperability and IEEE 2030.5 standard.

2.2.1.4 Actions to be taken beyond the project end

To ensure a successful further development, refinement and impactful uptake of the LPC, SUN will engage in strategic actions after InterSTORE end. At the current stage, this is the status of the different set of actions identification:

Immediate Actions: To ensure effective communication, training, and measurement of the KER in the early stages of implementation, SUN plans to conduct the following activities:

- Initiate internal training programs to ensure understanding and adoption.
- Identify key success metrics and establish baseline measurements.
- Develop a communication strategy outlining key messages, target audiences, and channels for dissemination.
- Collaborate with internal and external stakeholders, to integrate the new KER into existing training programs or initiatives.

Consolidation and Engagement Actions: To consolidate the gains made from the initial implementation and further engage stakeholders in the ongoing success of the new KER, SUN plans to conduct the following activities:

- Organise workshops or brainstorming sessions to encourage collaboration and idea generation for further improvement.
- Develop action plans based on feedback findings to address identified issues and capitalise on opportunities.
- Share success stories internally through company newsletters, intranet portals, or internal social media platforms to inspire and motivate.

Expansion and Optimisation Actions: To optimise the implementation of the new KER and leverage external resources and expertise, for a maximised impact and reach, SUN plans to conduct the following activities:

- Identify additional areas or business units where the new KER can be applied and develop implementation plans tailored to each context.
- Conduct pilot programs or phased rollouts in new areas to test scalability and effectiveness before full-scale implementation.
- Allocate resources and support to ensure successful implementation in new areas, including funding, personnel, and technology.
- Analyse performance data and metrics to identify bottlenecks, inefficiencies, or areas for improvement in the implementation process.

Monitoring and Adjustment actions: To ensure that they effectively monitor performance, identify areas for improvement, and make timely adjustments to optimise outcomes and achieve strategic objectives, SUN plans to conduct the following activities:

- Regularly review and analyse qualitative feedback from stakeholders, including employees, customers, and partners, to complement quantitative performance metrics.
- Benchmark performance against industry standards, best practices, or competitors to gain insights into relative performance and identify areas for improvement.
- Communicate performance new KER trends, and insights to stakeholders through periodic updates, progress reports, and presentations.

To carry out the above listed activities and progress towards TRL 9, including IP and legal requirements², SUN expects the cost's structure outlined in Table 10.

Activity	Sub-activity	Cost estimation range (€)
IP and legal activities	None	None
Immediate Actions	Promote LPC as open-source software	20.000 EUR
Consolidation and Engagement Actions	Engage user community	5.000 EUR
Expansion and Optimisation Actions	Improve the reach out of LPC GitHub and Docker Hub	15.000 EUR
Monitoring and Adjustment Actions	Monitoring the number of users	5.000 EUR
Total		Around 45.000 EUR

Table 7 KER2 Cost structure of actions beyond project end

Sources of Coverage: SUN aims to cover the above-mentioned costs targeting (i) local/national public funds, (ii) private investments, (iii) financial funds, (iv) business angels, (v) private industry.

² For IPR information, see section 4.3.2.

2.2.2 Overall Feedback on performance from UCs: KER2

The evaluation of the LPC across multiple UCs confirmed its strong role as a middleware solution enabling interoperability between heterogeneous assets and IEEE 2030.5-based EMS platforms. **In several pilots, including UC1, UC2, UC3, UC4, UC7, UC8, and UC9, the LPC was deemed highly relevant, supporting legacy assets and enabling services such as flexibility market participation, multiphysics storage integration, and fast frequency response.** Technical performance ranged from fair to excellent depending on the operational context, with particularly strong outcomes in UC3 and UC9, where seamless communication and secure system integration were achieved. In contrast, its relevance was limited in UC5 and UC6, where it was used only redundantly or faced poor integration results.

Integration and compatibility proved to be a recurring challenge across UCs, often requiring ad hoc adaptations, additional libraries, or tailored developments. While some deployments, such as in UC8, were smooth with only minor adjustments, others like UC1/UC2 and UC5 required significant effort to resolve compatibility issues, highlighting the need for greater plug-and-play functionality and enhanced usability. Despite these challenges, the LPC was consistently recognised as a powerful enabler for bridging diverse protocols, unlocking benefits such as reduced costs, improved data management, enhanced interoperability, and support for new business models.

Market demand for KER2 is generally considered high, with utilities, EMS/inverter manufacturers, installers, engineers, and system operators identified as the most relevant customer segments. However, barriers to adoption remain significant, including integration complexity, scalability issues, lack of stakeholder confidence, competitive pressure from existing solutions, and regulatory or policy constraints. UC owners highlighted the importance of improving ease of implementation, expanding the range of supported protocols, and strengthening security features to increase confidence and adoption.

Comparative assessments placed KER2 among the top exploitable results of InterSTORE, frequently ranked second in potential, and in some cases even considered the highest due to its ability to support existing HW without firmware modifications. While the tool is already deployable and operational in several environments, its exploitation potential will strongly depend on targeted refinements such as simplifying integration, expanding protocol coverage, improving security and documentation, and tailoring the solution to specific customer segments.

In conclusion, the LPC has demonstrated itself as a **versatile and impactful protocol converter with strong exploitation prospects across diverse smart grid applications.** Its future market success will rely on balancing its technical robustness with greater ease of adoption, ensuring regulatory compliance, and offering well-defined, market-ready versions that deliver true plug-and-play interoperability for legacy and modern energy systems alike. A more extensive assessment is provided in Annex 8.3.2.

2.3 KER3: Testing procedure and software tool

KER3 consists of the InterSTORE TPST, a fully automated solution designed to validate interoperability and functional compliance of systems implementing the IEEE 2030.5 standard. The TPST introduces an innovative testing approach by relying on a NATS-based messaging architecture rather than the traditional HTTP-based communication typically used in IEEE 2030.5 testing environments. This design choice enables lightweight, scalable, and event-driven testing workflows, aligned with modern cloud-native architectures.

The tool automatically executes predefined test cases and evaluates system behaviour by comparing expected and actual outcomes, generating clear pass/fail reports. Its development is aligned with SunSpec testing principles and covers multiple test categories, including core, communication, and basic interoperability tests. Built entirely on open-source components, the TPST leverages Cucumber to orchestrate client-side test flows and InterSTORE Java-based tools on the server side. It is platform-agnostic and can run on Windows, Linux, macOS, and embedded environments such as Raspberry Pi, ensuring flexibility for a wide range of users and deployment contexts.

2.3.1 Exploitation Plan: KER3

The exploitation strategy for KER3 is based on a comparative analysis with existing market solutions, notably the IEEE 2030.5 testing tool provided by Quality Logic. This analysis allowed the InterSTORE consortium to clearly define the unique value proposition of the TPST, particularly in terms of scalability, deployment flexibility, and cloud readiness.

Unlike traditional desktop-based testing solutions, the IEEE 2030.5 server integrated within the InterSTORE TPST can be deployed in cloud environments such as Amazon Web Services, Google Cloud, or Microsoft Azure. This enables DSOs, utilities, and platform operators to test and validate multiple devices and systems simultaneously under a unified server environment, rather than relying on one-to-one gateway connections. The TPST includes a dedicated, platform-agnostic "ad hoc server" that facilitates communication between deployed DERs and the cloud-hosted IEEE 2030.5 server, supporting seamless integration across heterogeneous infrastructures.

A key exploitation asset of KER3 is the embedded NATS messaging system, which records all client-server communications during testing. These messages are forwarded to validation components that assess compliance against IEEE 2030.5 procedures. This architecture allows interested stakeholders - such as DSOs and utilities - to subscribe to and analyse message streams for monitoring, diagnostics, and performance assessment, opening opportunities for advanced testing-as-a-service and quality-assurance offerings.

The applicability and maturity of KER3 were demonstrated in UC9, where the TPST was deployed together with an IEEE 2030.5 server to validate client-server integration in an EV charging cluster context. In this UC, the client natively supports IEEE 2030.5 and is provided and certified by Schneider Electric, offering a concrete and credible reference for future exploitation. This real-world validation strengthens the positioning of KER3 as a scalable, open-source testing solution for standard-compliant DER integration in both operational and market-oriented environments.

2.3.1.1 Exploitation Overview - Characterisation KER3

TRL: The TRL of the TPST was 7 at the beginning of InterSTORE and the KER development status is still within the frame of the same TRL, but with further refinements.

Brief Description: As detailed in the previous paragraphs, the testing software can be applied in two distinct ways. Thanks to its modular design, the back-end component can operate as an independent IEEE 2030.5 server, while the ad hoc server acts as a separate connector to the DER. In this configuration, the testing software validates the client (DER)-server inter-

action and determines whether the conformance tests are passed or not. Moreover, the expertise of the Automation of Complex Power Systems (RWTH-ACS) institute can be leveraged across different projects, in combination with other interoperable protocols.

Identification of the Problem/Need: This KER addresses the need to automatically verify whether devices and systems can correctly communicate using the IEEE 2030.5 standard. A key challenge in its development was the integration of the NATS messaging system, as the IEEE 2030.5 protocol natively supports only HTTP (RESTful APIs). Through a carefully designed modular architecture, this gap was successfully addressed by integrating NATS into the testing framework. This approach enables systems outside the IEEE 2030.5 ecosystem to seamlessly receive client-server interaction messages by subscribing to NATS streams. As a result, higher-level control platforms - such as utilities and DSOs - can access IEEE 2030.5 messages without needing to implement the protocol themselves.

Actors Involved: The primary entities identifying this need and contributing to the development of the TPST are public research and industrial stakeholders. Within InterSTORE, the work was led by ACS research group at RWTH Aachen University. The testing tool was validated at the ENX laboratory in Rome, where a native IEEE 2030.5-compliant Schneider Electric inverter was available for testing.

Type of Project Result: KER3 is to be classified as open-sourced software aimed at developing an application to test IEEE 2030.5 assets. Building on the results obtained during the development and testing, ACS has published a scientific article presented at the International Conference on Engineering, Technology, and Innovation (ICE).

Temporality of Project Result: The effects of this result/output are already visible, with the software being able to identify IEEE 2030.5 resources implemented on a mock server. In terms of short-term outcomes from the development and application of the TPST, the tool has significantly aided in understanding and testing IEEE 2030.5 field devices. For assets that are not commissioned and lack documentation, the testing software has been invaluable in identifying their features and functionality, effectively enabling analysis of these 'black box' devices.

Exploitation Level: At its current status, the tool is highly exploitable, providing an alternative to widely available paid solutions.

Development Phase: KER3 is fully developed, but has not yet been extensively exploited. Its further exploitation has been constrained by limitations in technical and production-level know-how, while the integration of NATS posed significant challenges to the overall system design. These challenges required several iterative modifications of the modular TPST architecture, including changes to development approaches and implementation techniques. During the development phase, experimentation was carried out using resources implemented within the IEEE 2030.5 ecosystem, such as the EPRI C Client software. In addition, collaboration with industry partners, including the SunSpec Alliance, provided essential resources - such as encryption certificates - that helped overcome development bottlenecks. Schneider Electric also provided guidelines for integrating the XW Pro client device with the IEEE 2030.5 server, which was successfully tested and validated using the TPST.

Time to Exploitability: The time to full exploitability is estimated to be around 3-5 years (2029-2032). The TPST will certainly get more visibility when more IEEE 2030.5 devices are integrated.

Exploitation Route: The TPST has strong potential for both scientific and technological exploitation. From a scientific perspective, its back-end component provides an IEEE 2030.5

server that can be used by DSOs, utilities, and platform operators to integrate and analyse native IEEE 2030.5 communications. Through NATS subscription, these stakeholders can receive native IEEE 2030.5 XML messages without the need to implement a full IEEE 2030.5 server themselves. In addition, the TPST supports automated batch testing, allowing multiple devices to be tested simultaneously. This capability is particularly valuable for rolling out new test cases and for performing periodic and large-scale interoperability testing.

Expected Commercial/Strategic Path for Deployment: For KER3 to be widely deployed, further development supported by research or government funding is necessary. There is always room for improvement, and the testing software can be refined further as more tests are conducted with real assets. The TPST can also be integrated into a broader commercial solution or service offering, for example bundled with partner HW or platforms. Its modular back-end and front-end allow flexible usage, and the testing software can be deployed on HW to test IEEE 2030.5 assets directly. Finally, there is potential for a spin-off or start-up being created based on this KER, offering a suite of testing software for distributed energy devices and for TSOs and DSOs, tailored to the specific protocols of interest.

Geographical Scale: RWTH/ACS sees a possibility for this tool being of interest to global audience, since it is open sourced and the IEEE 2030.5 is used globally.

Link to other KERs: The TPST has no direct link to any of the other KERs at current stage.

2.3.1.2 Stakeholders Analysis

When looking at InterSTORE main stakeholders, the following ones play a primary and secondary role for the exploitation and further uptake of KER3, the TPST:

PRIMARY
<p>Industry Users (Organisations, SME, inverters' manufacturers, BESS manufacturers, Heat pump providers, etc.): In terms of their power-interest, RWTH considers it appropriate to keep these entities continuously informed. They are expected to have a high interest in testing the software across various IEEE 2030.5 scenarios in accordance with Sunspec standards. To ensure their engagement, it is important to provide demonstrations, present at manufacturer meetings, offer support, and collaborate with them in EU funded projects.</p>
<p>Distribution System Operator (DSO) (voltage level regulation, power quality, reactive power, integration of RES): DSOs are primarily interested and manage them closely, when further deploying the TPST. They need to be aware that different voltage and power quality tests can be achieved. Same as for other stakeholders, to ensure their engagement, it is important to provide demonstrations, present at manufacturer meetings, offer support, and collaborate with them in EU funded projects.</p>
<p>Regulatory Bodies and Standardisation (BRIDGE, 2ZeRo, InterConnect, Enershare, etc.): These stakeholders are primary and should be managed closely when progressing on the KER development, as it contributes to shaping favourable regulatory or policy frameworks. These stakeholders need to be aware of the fact that the testing tool can be improved by introducing adequate standardisation. Same as for other stakeholders, to ensure their engagement, it is important to provide demonstrations, present at manufacturer meetings, offer support, and collaborate with them in EU funded projects.</p>

Academia & Research Institutions: The TPST represents a valuable asset for advancing research in energy system digitalisation, making close stakeholder management important. It provides an excellent starting point for future research: with IEEE 2030.5 features implemented in the testing tool; additional test cases can be easily developed. Its modular design allows the back-end to function as an IEEE 2030.5 server and the front-end as a client. Same as for other stakeholders, to ensure their engagement, it is important to provide demonstrations, present at manufacturer meetings, offer support, and collaborate with them in EU funded projects.

Table 8 Table 10 KER3 Primary stakeholders

SECONDARY
<p>End Users (energy communities' members, EV & Fleet owners, office's and campus employees, etc.): End users are considered secondary stakeholders for the TPST, but it is important to keep them informed during further development of KER3. They are expected to have a high interest in including IEEE 2030.5 assets for testing and in using the developed client-server solution. Same as for other stakeholders, to ensure their engagement, it is important to provide demonstrations, present at manufacturer meetings, offer support, and collaborate with them in EU funded projects.</p>
<p>Transmission System Operator (TSO) (primary-secondary-tertiary reserve, RES integration, re-dispatch): Keeping these stakeholders' needs into account when further developing the TPST is important to secure alignment with energy transmission and distribution system's needs. Therefore, they need to be aware that combining the IEEE 2030.5 with open Automated Demand Response (ADR) and International Electrotechnical Commission Standard (IEC) 61850 seems a good model. Same as for other stakeholders, to ensure their engagement, it is important to provide demonstrations, present at manufacturer meetings, offer support, and collaborate with them in EU funded projects.</p>
<p>Flexibility Service Providers (offering energy assets batteries, virtual power plant, energy transition service, ESCO, etc.): It is essential to try to keep them continuously informed on the further development of the TPST. According to RWTH, it is important for them to be aware that the testing tool can be used to test IEEE 2030.5-supported virtual power plants with batteries. Same as for other stakeholders, to ensure their engagement, it is important to provide demonstrations, present at manufacturer meetings, offer support, and collaborate with them in EU funded projects.</p>

Table 9 KER3 Secondary stakeholders

2.3.1.3 Exploitation Route Towards Impact

When looking at the expected impacts that InterSTORE is envisaged to contribute to in the long term, the contributions foreseen for KER3 are as follows: **(i)** KER3 is expected to make a high contribution to the achievement of industrial leadership in key and emerging technologies that work for people; **(ii)** a high contribution is expected towards the achievement of affordable and clean energy overall; **(iii)** the TPST is expected to also highly contribute to securing, in the long term, a more efficient, clean, sustainable, secure and competitive energy supply through new solutions for smart grids and energy systems based on more performant renewable energy solutions. Looking forward, beyond InterSTORE duration, KER3 will contribute to these impacts by fostering the use of an open-source and free testing tool in IEEE 2030.5, helping to integrate and test native IEEE 2030.5 devices.

2.3.1.4 *Actions to be taken Beyond the Project End*

To ensure a successful further development, refinement and impactful uptake of the TPST, RWTH will engage in strategic actions after InterSTORE end. At the current stage, this is the status of the different set of actions identification:

Immediate Actions: To ensure effective communication, training, and measurement of the KER in the early stages of implementation, SUN plans to conduct the following activities:

- Creating frameworks, guidelines, and tools based on research findings to facilitate the implementation and adoption of the new KER.
- Initiate internal training programs to ensure understanding and adoption.
- Develop a communication strategy outlining key messages, target audiences, and channels for dissemination.
- Schedule kick-off meetings to announce the new KER and set expectations.
- Provide resources and support materials to facilitate learning and implementation of new practices.
- Collaborate with internal and external stakeholders, to integrate the new KER into existing training programs or initiatives.

Consolidation and Engagement Actions: To consolidate the gains made from the initial implementation and further engage stakeholders in the ongoing success of the new KER, RWTH plans to conduct the following activities:

- Conduct feedback sessions and focus groups to gather insights from stakeholders across different levels and departments.
- Organise workshops or brainstorming sessions to encourage collaboration and idea generation for further improvement.

Expansion and Optimisation Actions: To optimise the implementation of the new KER and leverage external resources and expertise, for a maximised impact and reach, RWTH plans to conduct the following activities:

- Scale up implementation efforts across relevant departments or teams by developing a roadmap for broader adoption and expansion.
- Allocate resources and support to ensure successful implementation in new areas, including funding, personnel, and technology.
- Provide ongoing training and support to employees to build capacity and confidence in implementing the new KER effectively.

Monitoring and Adjustment actions: To ensure that they effectively monitor performance, identify areas for improvement, and make timely adjustments to optimise outcomes and achieve strategic objectives, RWTH plans to conduct the following activities:

- Continuously monitor key performance indicators (KPIs) using real-time data analytics tools and dashboards to track the effectiveness and impact of the implemented initiatives.
- Benchmark performance against industry standards, best practices, or competitors to gain insights into relative performance and identify areas for improvement.
- Document lessons learned, best practices, and recommendations from performance reviews to inform future planning and decision-making processes.

To carry out the above listed activities and progress towards TRL 9, including IP and legal requirements³, RWTH still has to identify the cost's structure.

Sources of Coverage: RWTH aims to cover costs targeting more local/national public funds.

2.3.2 Overall Feedback on performance from UCs: KER3

Overall, the feedback collected from the different UCs highlights that the **TPST (KER3) has only been marginally implemented and tested across the InterSTORE pilot activities**, with the exception of UC9, where the IEEE 2030.5 protocol client (natively supporting IEEE 2030.5)-server integration has been tested using this KER. The TPST has been developed and successfully tested for IEEE 2030.5 server-client integration, and power hardware-in-the-loop tests have been conducted to verify conformance with the IEEE 2030.5 standard as developed by SunSpec. The TPST holds significant potential for future application, particularly in supporting regulatory compliance, interoperability testing, and the validation of IEEE 2030.5 resources. In addition, the developed TPST includes an IEEE 2030.5 server that is directly applicable in production environments where systems operate fully within an IEEE 2030.5 framework. UC9 partners recognised that the TPST holds significant potential for future application, particularly in supporting regulatory compliance, interoperability testing, and validation of IEEE 2030.5 resources.

From a market perspective, **the expected demand for the TPST is high, and the SunSpec Alliance has already identified the software's potential and is ready to promote it**. The most promising customer segments include regulators, standardisation bodies, utilities, and manufacturers of inverters, EMSs, and other distributed energy assets. Ongoing efforts by the SunSpec Alliance aim to improve visibility and facilitate access for its clients to use the TPST globally. In this context, SunSpec is expected to play a key role as a reference standardisation and regulatory actor in the USA, Europe, and Australia, strengthening stakeholder participation beyond national borders.

Across all UCs, several recommendations converge on the **need to strengthen the TPST's usability and credibility**. These include developing a practical guide for self-testing, identifying accredited validation entities, and expanding the test library to cover the full set of IEEE 2030.5 attributes. Additional improvements could focus on enhancing user-friendliness, increasing the number of available test cases, and ensuring easier application by testing and certification entities.

When compared with the other KERs, KER3 ranks **among those requiring the most development effort** before reaching full exploitation readiness.

Although currently perceived as a standalone testing tool with limited **integration across the UCs**, the TPST remains a valuable asset for advancing digitalisation and interoperability in the energy domain. With **targeted technical improvements, regulatory recognition, and strategic engagement with industrial stakeholders**, the TPST could evolve into a reliable and commercially viable solution for testing and validating distributed energy systems. A more extensive assessment is provided in Annex 8.3.3.

³ For IPR information, see section 4.3.3.

2.4 KER4: InterSTORE Data Space Connector

InterSTORE Data Space Connector (DSC) relies on previous work carried out by ENG: True Connector and OneNet connector. The True Connector enables trusted data exchange as part of the IDS ecosystem - a virtual Data Space that leverages established standards, technologies, and governance models widely accepted in the data economy - to facilitate secure and standardised data sharing and linkage within a trusted business environment. The True Connector has been expanded and specified within the OneNet project for the energy domain, adding:

- FIWARE Context Broker fully integrated in the Connector Architecture;
- Additional Data Services (Data Quality, Data Harmonisation, etc.);
- Standardised Application Programming Interface (API) for any Energy Data.

The IDS Connector allows to exchange data and enrich it with metadata. An important aspect are usage conditions, which can be defined, administrated, and implemented by the Connector. The metadata is described by the ontology of the IDS Information Model. The main advantage of the IDS reference architecture and the use of an IDS Connector is the decentralised data storage. This enables data integration from different data sources and allows data access exclusively through other IDS Connectors. The architectural design of Interoperable Data Space Framework is structured to be modular, scalable and easily maintainable. The Interoperable Data Space Framework mainly consists of two components: the Data Space Middleware and the Energy Data Space Connector.

The Data Space Middleware implements all the central features of the Interoperable Data Space Framework including:

- Identity Management;
- Vocabularies and Ontology for Energy Domain;
- Data Catalogue discovery;
- Services Creation.

An IDS Connector is composed of various system services:

- Execution core container with message systems (message router/bus);
- Configuration manager to configure the connector (execution core container, application container management, network, firewalls, etc.);
- Data apps for data processing and handling;
- Application container management;
- Hardware/operating system.

Key Features are:

- Open graphical user interface;
- Blockchain integration for data exchange transaction and verification;
- New data exchange mechanisms for service providers (e.g., Service subscribe and push data);
- Integration and support of new standards and protocols (e.g., IEEE 2030.5).

The objective was to create a single page application that uses modern technologies and is completely decoupled from the back-end API. Furthermore, the new interface module must not have particular constraints on frameworks or proprietary libraries, so that it can be released under an open-source license and used/evolved even after the end of the InterSTORE project.

The new interface includes the following features:

- User management and user authentication;
- Dashboards;
- Connector settings;
- Viewing the macro services of the energy domain;
- Creation and management of services;
- Subscription of services with acceptance workflow;
- Data exchange (upload/download) on a service;
- Timeline with visualisation of smart contracts created on blockchain.

All transactions that take place within the Data APP call a blockchain-based transaction notarisation service which takes care of verifying the data entity and writing some identifying transaction information in the blockchain infrastructure exploiting smart contracts implementation. In this way any transaction is tracked and verifiable.

2.4.1 Exploitation Plan: KER4

The development and exploitation processes stemmed from the need to promote the OneNet connector, specifically developed for energy IDS. To assure the adoption of this connector, it was crucial to agree on an open source IP Licence that was accepted by Linux Energy Data Space. The Energy DSC is now available on InterSTORE github. Several activities have been implemented to assure the easy adoption and testing of the tools by project partners and cluster projects partners. On July 17th, 2023 - within the cluster meeting with FlexChess and Parminides project - a dedicated working session was held by ENG to present the Energy Data Space connector and promote its adoption by the cluster pilot demo owners. Ad hoc training sessions have been organised to assist project partners to install the connector and familiarise with it. InterSTORE has been included as part of int:net Energy Data Space Cluster Projects (EDSCP). This included the initial Data Spaces projects (ENERSHARE, DATA CELLAR, OMEGA-X, EDDIE, SYNERGIES) and the new ones (InterSTORE, TwinEU, InterStore, HedgeIoT, Odeon, Begonia).

2.4.1.1 Exploitation Overview - Characterisation KER4

TRL: While having a TRL of 5 at the beginning of InterSTORE, the DSC is estimated to reach TRL7 by the end of the project.

Brief Description: As detailed in previous paragraphs, KER4 is to be categorised as an energy Data Space framework.

Identification of the Problem/Need: This KER aims to respond to the technical need for interoperable, standardised, secure, and sovereign data sharing mechanisms in the energy sector. From a financial point of view, it aims to contribute to the reduction of operational costs, accelerate Return on Investment (ROI), and unlock new revenue streams from data-driven energy services. The DSC also addresses the environmental need to maximise RES integration, reduce grid curtailment, and lower Greenhouse Gases (GHG) emissions through coordinated data sharing. Finally, this KER can contribute to democratise the access to energy data, increase transparency, and enable increased participation of society in the energy transition.

Actors Involved: The main entities manifesting the need and collaborating to the development of the DSC, are private entities. These actors drive innovation, develop commercial services, and build enabling technologies. They have a strong interest in interoperable data exchange to offer new services, reduce operational costs, and access emerging energy markets. Aca-

demic institutions also contribute with applied research. Public actors shape the legal, regulatory, and technical frameworks needed for Data Spaces to operate. They support standardisation, provide funding, and enforce data sovereignty and consumer protection principles. Research centres contribute to design, testing, and validation. Finally, the energy industry is the primary user and beneficiary of the Data Space. It enables secure and scalable data sharing across stakeholders to optimise grid operations, improve asset management, enable flexibility markets, and accelerate the energy transition.

Type of Project Result: KER4 incorporates (i) methodologies/methods, (ii) processes, (iii) services, (iv) software, (v) scientific findings and new (vi) expertise: (i) methodologies for data governance, consent management, interoperability (Gaia-X/IDS-based), and stakeholder trust models; (ii) processes that define the orchestration of data access, participant onboarding, federation, and service integration; (iii) services that are enabled by the framework, including flexibility-as-a-service, real-time energy monitoring, peer-to-peer energy data sharing, and integration of distributed energy resources (DERs); (iv) software components such as connectors, identity providers, and data brokers developed or adapted to enable Data Space functionality; (v) supporting the dissemination and validation of technical components; (vi) expertise generated in digital energy ecosystems, data sovereignty, federated architectures, and semantic interoperability, which will be transferred to public and private stakeholders.

Temporality of Project Result: The effects of the DSC are already visible as an output. The Energy Data Space Framework delivered concrete, tangible results within the project timeframe, such as the architectural blueprint, governance model, software components (e.g., connectors, identity providers), and integration guidelines. These are formal deliverables. In terms of short/midterm outcomes stemming from KER3 as a result of InterSTORE project, there are as follows: the framework enables short-to medium-term changes in stakeholder behaviour and system architecture - including adoption by partners, alignment with Gaia-X/IDS standards, and integration into energy use cases such as flexibility management or energy communities. Finally, the DSC, also aims to drive long-term systemic change, including enhanced interoperability, wider adoption of data sharing models in the energy sector, acceleration of energy digitalisation, and creation of new data-driven business models and services across Europe.

Exploitation Level: At its current status, the tool is highly exploitable. Once piloted and validated, the Energy Data Space Framework can serve as a reference implementation across multiple domains (e.g., energy communities, flexibility markets, grid services). It is aligned with EU initiatives like Gaia-X, BRIDGE, and InterConnect, increasing its scalability and market relevance.

Development Phase: KER4 is fully developed, but it has not yet been extensively exploited. The Energy Data Space Framework has been fully developed within the project, including its reference architecture, governance model, semantic interoperability guidelines, and enabling software components (e.g., connectors, identity providers, and data exchange mechanisms). The framework has been successfully tested in a pilot environment involving real-world use cases. However, it has not yet been exploited commercially or adopted at scale beyond the project consortium. Formal exploitation and broader operational deployment could be planned for the post-project phase, once the necessary ecosystem and stakeholder commitments are in place.

Time to Exploitability: The overall time to full exploitability is estimated to be around 1-2 years (2027-2028). Initial exploitation by project partners and early adopters is feasible and could be expected to start directly at project completion. As already mentioned, the framework is

technically mature and was tested in pilots; however, full exploitation requires additional ecosystem readiness, regulatory clarity, and stakeholder onboarding.

Exploitation Route: The exploitation routes of the DSC can be multiple. From a scientific/academic point of view, the framework can contribute to ongoing academic research on federated data architectures, data governance, interoperability, and digitalisation in the energy sector. It provides a valuable foundation for scientific publications, further EU research projects, and curriculum development. From a technological point of view, the framework includes exploitable technical components such as software connectors, data exchange protocols, semantic models, and Gaia-X/IDS alignment, enabling further technological development and integration into digital energy platforms. KER4 can also fit a more socially oriented exploitation route: by enabling trusted and sovereign energy data sharing, the framework supports citizen empowerment (e.g., in energy communities), energy transition, and transparency - all of which have clear societal benefits. Finally, in terms of economic exploitation, the framework enables the creation of new data-driven services, facilitates the participation of SMEs and prosumers in flexibility markets, and supports new business models in the energy data economy, thus having strong economic potential.

Expected Commercial/Strategic Path for Deployment: For KER4 to be widely deployed, further development supported by research or government funding is required. The Energy Data Space Framework is a strategic, foundational result that aligns with ongoing European and national initiatives. While technically validated, its full deployment requires policy support, multi-stakeholder coordination, and further development in the context of large-scale pilots and cross-border collaborations. As such, follow-up projects funded by Horizon Europe, Digital Europe Programme, or national funding schemes are the most realistic and strategic path for scaling and institutionalising the framework. Moreover, integration into a broader commercial solution or service offering (e.g., bundled with hardware or platform from partners) would also help in enhancing the commercial/strategic path for wide deployment. Some partners (e.g., utilities, IT companies) may integrate elements of the framework (e.g., connectors, governance models, or APIs) into existing platforms or energy services, allowing indirect commercialisation through value-added offerings. This route supports progressive adoption.

Geographical Scale: ENG sees a possibility for this tool being of interest to global audience. Although initial deployment may focus on national contexts, the Energy Data Space Framework is built on open, international standards such as Gaia-X and IDS, which are designed for interoperability across borders. The energy transition is a global challenge, and the framework's modular and scalable design allows it to be adapted and adopted worldwide. Moreover, many project partners and associated initiatives have international reach, which facilitates global dissemination, cooperation, and integration in multiple energy markets.

Link to other KERs: KER4 is directly linked to KER2 (the LPC, owned by SUN): the converter enables the integration of legacy energy systems by translating legacy protocols into new standardised protocols, ensuring broader participation and seamless data sharing. It can be used to import data from other components into the Data Space or export data from the Data Space to other components.

2.4.1.2 Stakeholders Analysis

When looking at InterSTORE main stakeholders, the following ones play a primary and secondary role for the exploitation and further uptake of KER4, the DSC:

PRIMARY

Transmission System Operator (TSO) (primary-secondary-tertiary reserve, RES integration, re-dispatch): TSO's are primary stakeholders for the DSC, managing these stakeholders' needs when further developing KER4 is important to secure alignment with energy transmission and distribution system's needs. Their main needs are as follows: (i) System stability - access to real-time data for balancing (primary/secondary/tertiary reserves); (ii) Flexibility visibility - knowing what DER are available and when. (iii) Cross-border harmonisation - alignment with other European TSOs for grid operation and market integration; (iv) RES integration - forecasting and managing variable renewable energy sources; (v) Secure, standardised data flows - avoiding blackouts through accurate, timely information. To ensure their engagement, it is important to rely on the following: (i) Strategic partnerships in reserve markets and grid balancing use cases; (ii) Governance roles within the Data Space to help shape access rules, security protocols; (iii) Joint modelling/forecasting pilots using shared datasets and AI tools; (iv) EU-level harmonisation initiatives to align with cross-border frameworks (e.g., ENTSO-E). The overall goal is to engage them as system orchestrators and benefit from visibility into decentralised flexibility.

Distribution System Operator (DSO) (voltage level regulation, power quality, reactive power, integration of RES): DSOs are primarily interested and it is very important to manage them closely, when further deploying the DSC. Their main needs are as follows: (i) Grid observability - real-time awareness of voltage, load, and power quality at local level; (ii) Flexibility activation - ability to request/coordinate flexibility from end users and devices; (iii) Asset optimisation - better planning through data-driven investment decisions; (iv) Coordination with TSO - clarifying roles in local vs. system-wide flexibility; (v) Non-discriminatory access - managing fair access to local grid for all market participants. To ensure their engagement, it is important to rely on the following: (i) Local grid observability pilots using smart meter and IoT data via the Data Space; (ii) Training programs and shared tools for flexibility forecasting, planning, and activation; (iii) DSO/TSO coordination mechanisms built on shared data models and consent frameworks; (iv) Funding access support (e.g., EU Digital Europe, Horizon Europe) to de-risk innovation. The overall goal is to show value of the DSC towards operational efficiency and grid modernisation.

Flexibility Service Providers (offering energy assets batteries, virtual power plant, energy transition service, ESCO, etc.): It is essential to manage them closely and try to address their needs. According to ENG, the following is important for them: (i) Access to data - high-quality, real-time data to optimise flexibility offering; (ii) Market integration - ability to bid into multiple markets (capacity, balancing, congestion management); (iii) Revenue models - tools to quantify, track, and invoice for flexibility services; (iv) Interoperability - plug-and-play participation without costly customisation; (v) Forecasting tools - access to historical and predictive datasets. To ensure their engagement, it is important to rely on the following: (i) Plug-and-play data access layers to reduce friction for participating in multiple markets; (ii) Revenue-sharing models or KPIs that measure and reward flexibility contributions; (iii) Use case co-design around congestion management, self-consumption optimisation, etc.; (iv) Certification pathways to verify trusted service provider status. The overall goal is to enable monetisation and scalability by simplifying integration and validation.

Regulatory Bodies and Standardisation (BRIDGE, 2ZeRo, InterConnect, Enershare, etc.): These stakeholders are primary and should be managed closely when progressing on the KER development, as it contributes to shaping favourable regulatory or policy frameworks. Their main concerns, to be considered when further developing the DSC, are as follows: (i) Governance frameworks - clear rules on access, usage rights, liabilities; (ii) Standard compliance - promoting harmonisation across EU energy Data Spaces; (iii) Monitoring and KPIs - tools to assess effectiveness of regulations and data sharing models. (iv) Innovation support - ensuring that Data Space architectures enable new market entrants. (v) Cybersecurity & data protection - ensuring resilient, privacy-respecting data exchange. To ensure their engagement, it is important to rely on the following: (i) Involve early in governance definition (data access rights, usage policies, liability); (ii) Feedback loops into policy development from real-world pilots; (iii) Align with existing frameworks (e.g., BRIDGE, Data Act, RED II/III, Clean Energy Package); (iv) Public dashboards and transparency tools for KPIs and impact tracking. The overall goal is to position the Data Space as a regulatory enabler, not a compliance burden.

Table 10 KER4 Primary stakeholders

SECONDARY
<p>Industry Users (Organisations, SME, inverters' manufacturers, BESS manufacturers, Heat pump providers, etc.): In terms of their power-interest, ENG considers it appropriate to keep these entities continuously informed and try to meet their needs. They are expected to have a high interest in the following: (i) Interoperability standards - APIs, data formats, and interfaces that work with their products; (ii) Market access - ability to plug their systems into energy markets (e.g., flexibility, ancillary services); (iii) Business models - opportunities to monetise data or offer value-added services through Data Space; (iv) Compliance - clarity on how data sharing complies with General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), cybersecurity, Conformité Européenne (CE) marking. (v) Support for innovation - open access to real-world data for product optimisation and development. To ensure their engagement, it is important to deliver technical workshops and developer sandboxes to test integration with Data Space APIs and standards. Moreover, it is important to promote innovation partnerships with startups and SMEs to pilot applications and services. Clear documentation and onboarding tools to lower entry barriers are also fundamental. Finally, IP protection mechanisms for proprietary solutions shared in the Data Space are in their interest. The overall goal when targeting these stakeholders is to encourage adoption of the DSC by showing how participation boosts product interoperability and market access.</p>

End Users (energy communities' members, EV & Fleet owners, office's and campus employees, etc.): End users are considered secondary stakeholders for the DSC, but it is important to keep them informed during further development of KER4. They are expected to have a high interest in the following: (i) Data sovereignty - control over who accesses their consumption/production data; (ii) Cost savings & incentives - lower bills via dynamic tariffs, demand response, or energy sharing; (iii) Transparency - clear view of how their energy usage is used or monetised. (iv) Privacy and trust - secure, anonymised data management. (v) Ease of use - seamless integration with smart home/charging systems. To ensure their engagement, it is important to rely on the following: (i) Gamified or incentive-based participation (e.g., lower bills, tokens, local energy sharing rewards); (ii) Trust-building campaigns on data privacy, transparency, and sovereignty; (iii) Simple, user-friendly interfaces to manage consent, view data use, and opt in/out; (iv) Community ambassadors or pilot programs in real contexts (e.g., neighbourhoods, campuses). The overall goal is to build trust and create visible, localised value to motivate engagement.

Academia & Research Institutions: While these are secondary stakeholders, the DSC represents a valuable asset for advancing research in energy system digitalisation, making close stakeholder management important. The main needs of these stakeholders are as follows: (i) Open data access - anonymised, large-scale datasets for model development and testing; (ii) Sandbox environments - simulated spaces to test new algorithms, market models, or protocols; (iii) Knowledge transfer - active involvement in standardisation and advisory to industry; (iv) Cross-disciplinary collaboration - opportunities to work with industry on real use cases; (v) Publishing & impact - making results visible through impactful research enabled by Data Space participation. To ensure their engagement, it is important to rely on the following: (i) Open data sandboxes (with anonymised datasets) for Artificial Intelligence (AI), optimisation, forecasting; (ii) Joint research calls and demonstrators (EU, national, regional); (iii) Publication support to amplify visibility of results from Data Space participation; (iv) Interdisciplinary workshops combining energy, data governance, legal, and AI. The overall goal is to leverage academic credibility to validate concepts and foster continuous improvement.

Table 11 KER4 Secondary stakeholders

2.4.1.3 Exploitation Route Towards Impact

When looking at the expected impacts that InterSTORE is envisaged to contribute to in the long term, the contributions foreseen for KER4 are as follows: (i) the DSC is expected to make a high contribution to the achievement of industrial leadership in key and emerging technologies that work for people; (ii) a high contribution is expected towards the achievement of affordable and clean energy overall; (iii) the DSC is expected to also highly contribute to securing, in the long term, a more efficient, clean, sustainable, secure and competitive energy supply through new solutions for smart grids and energy systems based on more performant renewable energy solutions. Looking forward, beyond InterSTORE duration, in five years the Energy Data Space Framework is expected to support the large-scale deployment of smart, interoperable, and secure data exchange mechanisms across the energy sector. This will enable better integration of renewable energy sources, enhanced grid flexibility, and more efficient energy system management. By fostering a common data-sharing infrastructure, the framework will contribute to a more competitive, sustainable, and resilient energy supply, facilitating new business models and accelerating the digital and green transition of the energy domain.

2.4.1.4 *Actions to be taken Beyond the Project End*

To ensure a successful further development, refinement and impactful uptake of the DSC, ENG will engage in strategic actions after InterSTORE end. At the current stage, this is the status of the different set of actions identification:

Immediate Actions: To ensure effective communication, training, and measurement of the KER in the early stages of implementation, ENG plans to conduct the following activities:

- Creating frameworks, guidelines, and tools based on research findings to facilitate the implementation and adoption of the new KER.
- Initiate internal training programs to ensure understanding and adoption.
- Identify key success metrics and establish baseline measurements.
- Develop a communication strategy outlining key messages, target audiences, and channels for dissemination.
- Create informational materials such as brochures, presentations, or videos to support communication efforts.
- Schedule kick-off meetings to announce the new KER and set expectations.
- Provide resources and support materials to facilitate learning and implementation of new practices.
- Establish feedback mechanisms for employees to ask questions, share concerns, and provide input on the KER.
- Set up tracking systems or tools to monitor progress towards achieving key success metrics.

Consolidation and Engagement Actions: To consolidate the gains made from the initial implementation and further engage stakeholders in the ongoing success of the new KER, ENG plans to conduct the following activities:

- Conduct feedback sessions and focus groups to gather insights from stakeholders across different levels and departments.
- Organise workshops or brainstorming sessions to encourage collaboration and idea generation for further improvement.
- Establish cross-functional teams or task forces to address specific challenges or opportunities identified during feedback sessions.
- Analyse feedback and insights gathered to identify common themes, areas of strength, and areas for improvement.
- Develop action plans based on feedback findings to address identified issues and capitalise on opportunities.
- Showcase success stories or case studies highlighting tangible outcomes and benefits achieved through the implementation of the new KER.
- Create multimedia materials such as videos, infographics, or presentations to visually communicate success stories and outcomes to a wider audience.
- Share success stories internally through company newsletters, intranet portals, or internal social media platforms to inspire and motivate employees.
- Leverage success stories externally through press releases, industry publications, or social media channels to enhance the organization's reputation and credibility.
- Invite stakeholders to participate in events or webinars where success stories are shared and discussed, providing opportunities for learning and networking.

Expansion and Optimisation Actions: To optimise the implementation of the new KER and leverage external resources and expertise, for a maximised impact and reach, ENG plans to conduct the following activities:

- Scale up implementation efforts across relevant departments or teams by developing a roadmap for broader adoption and expansion.
- Identify additional areas or business units where the new KER can be applied and develop implementation plans tailored to each context.
- Conduct pilot programs or phased rollouts in new areas to test scalability and effectiveness before full-scale implementation.
- Allocate resources and support to ensure successful implementation in new areas, including funding, personnel, and technology.
- Establish clear communication channels and support mechanisms to address challenges and facilitate smooth implementation across multiple departments or teams.
- Analyse performance data and metrics to identify bottlenecks, inefficiencies, or areas for improvement in the implementation process.
- Implement iterative improvements and adjustments to optimise processes and enhance outcomes.
- Develop standardised procedures and best practices based on successful implementation experiences to ensure consistency and quality across different areas or teams.
- Provide ongoing training and support to employees to build capacity and confidence in implementing the new KER effectively.
- Explore opportunities for external collaboration or partnerships with other organisations, industry associations, or research institutions.
- Identify potential collaborators or partners with complementary expertise, resources, or networks to enhance the impact and reach of the new KER.
- Initiate discussions or negotiations with potential collaborators to establish mutually beneficial partnerships or joint initiatives.
- Develop partnership agreements outlining roles, responsibilities, and expectations for collaboration, including resource sharing, knowledge exchange, and joint decision-making.
- Monitor and evaluate the effectiveness of external collaborations or partnerships, and make adjustments as needed to ensure alignment with organisational goals and objectives.

Monitoring and Adjustment actions: To ensure that they effectively monitor performance, identify areas for improvement, and make timely adjustments to optimise outcomes and achieve strategic objectives, ENG plans to conduct the following activities:

- Continuously monitor key performance indicators (KPIs) using real-time data analytics tools and dashboards to track the effectiveness and impact of the implemented initiatives.
- Set up automated alerts or triggers to notify relevant stakeholders of any significant deviations from expected performance targets or thresholds.
- Conduct in-depth analyses of performance data to identify trends, patterns, and correlations that may inform strategic decisions and adjustments.
- Regularly review and analyse qualitative feedback from stakeholders, including employees, customers, and partners, to complement quantitative performance metrics.
- Benchmark performance against industry standards, best practices, or competitors to gain insights into relative performance and identify areas for improvement.
- Conduct root cause analyses to investigate underlying factors contributing to performance discrepancies or challenges and develop targeted action plans to address them.

- Establish cross-functional teams or task forces dedicated to monitoring and optimising specific aspects of performance, such as efficiency, quality, or customer satisfaction.
- Implement regular performance reviews and assessments at predetermined intervals, such as quarterly or semi-annually, to evaluate progress against strategic goals and objectives.
- Solicit input and feedback from stakeholders during performance reviews to gain diverse perspectives and identify blind spots or overlooked opportunities.
- Communicate performance new KER trends, and insights to stakeholders through periodic updates, progress reports, and presentations.
- Provide opportunities for stakeholders to ask questions, share concerns, and provide input during performance review meetings to foster transparency and accountability.
- Document lessons learned, best practices, and recommendations from performance reviews to inform future planning and decision-making processes.

To carry out the above listed activities and progress towards TRL 9, including IP and legal requirements⁴, ENG expects the cost's structure outlined in Table 17.

Activity	Sub-activity	Cost estimation range (€)
IP and legal activities	IP and Legal Management for TRL 9 deployment; Formalising Ownership and Licensing Agreements; Legal Advice and Support on IPR Management; Monitoring Compliance and Enforcement; IPR Documentation and Reporting; Support for Open-Source Licensing and Contribution Management	70.000 - 100.000 EUR
Immediate Actions		110.000 - 150.000 EUR
Consolidation and Engagement Actions		90.000 - 120.000 EUR
Expansion and Optimisation Actions		170.000 - 220.000 EUR
Monitoring and Adjustment Actions		150.000 - 210.000 EUR
Total		Around 590.000 - 800.000 EUR

Table 12 KER3 Cost structure of actions beyond project end

Sources of Coverage: ENG aims to cover the above-mentioned costs targeting (i) private investments, (ii) banks, (iii) financial funds, (iv) business angels, (v) private industry and (vi) other private investors, (v) own investments. Additional sources of coverage could be, as in the case of InterSTORE, European Union funding programmes (Horizon Europe, Innovation Fund), international cooperation grants, or public-private partnership schemes.

⁴ For IPR information, see section 4.3.4.

2.4.2 Overall Feedback on performance from UCs: KER4

Overall, the DSC (KER4) has demonstrated strong potential as a tool for secure and standardised data exchange across multiple UCs, particularly in contexts where data sovereignty, interoperability, and controlled sharing are key. In UC1 and UC2, the DSC was slightly relevant and enabled CYG to send DSO balancing offers, though integration challenges arose due to Kubernetes-Docker compatibility, highlighting the need for alternative implementation approaches. **In UC3 and UC9, the DSC performed excellently and met expectations,** facilitating seamless service provisioning, data sharing with partners, and secure cloud deployment, albeit requiring some modifications to access roles and virtual machine configurations. In UCs with less extensive use (UC4, UC7, UC8, UC5/UC6), the tool's relevance varied, with observed benefits including improved operational efficiency, enhanced data management, and potential for new business models and revenue streams.

Market demand for the DSC is consistently perceived as high, especially among aggregators, B2B partners, and energy system operators, though barriers such as stakeholder confidence, technical integration, and competitive alternatives remain. Recommendations for improvement focus on enabling broader deployment to end users, enhancing usability (e.g., timeline functionality), expanding documented use cases, and providing clear implementation examples to showcase potential business applications.

Comparatively, KER4 ranks among the highest in exploitation potential across the InterSTORE KERs, benefiting from a mature, modular, and user-friendly design, with strong applicability in data-driven energy applications. Its flexibility, security features, and capacity to create new services position the DSC as a commercially ready tool, capable of supporting a wide range of energy-sector data-sharing scenarios. More extensive feedback per each UC is provided in Annex 8.3.4.

3 Business Plan and Business Model

3.1 Overall InterSTORE Business Model

As thoroughly assessed in deliverable **D4.4 - Corporate social and environmental responsibility business models (RWTH)** - since InterSTORE project seeks to enable, enhance, and expand flexibility services across distributed energy systems, business modelling plays a critical role. It aims to align technical innovations with feasible service and market delivery models. This modelling work is directly linked to exploitation planning and supports the uptake of InterSTORE KERs. **This section builds entirely on the methodologies and outcomes documented in D4.4, as well as the feedback collected from KERs and UCs owners detailed in previous sections of the current deliverable.**

The business modelling and planning process in InterSTORE, developed under **T4.4 - Societal impact through TRIPLE LAYER BUSINESS MODEL CANVAS**, is based on a UC-driven framework - converting technical developments into viable service and market models. At the core of this approach is the TLBMC [2], which evaluates value creation along economic, social, and environmental dimensions. To strengthen the contextual analysis, Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities and Threats (SWOT) and Political, Economic, Social and Technological (PEST) analysis tools are integrated to assess enabling factors, regulatory environments, and long-term risks and opportunities. Through the combination of these methodologies, both technical feasibility and systemic value creation across different levels of implementation are assessed. Business modelling is tailored to the characteristics of each InterSTORE UC, ensuring that differences in value chain structure, stakeholder landscape, market access, and data requirements are fully captured. At the same time, this approach allows the identification of key dependencies, such as interoperability needs, consumer engagement mechanisms, or digital infrastructure constraints. **The process serves as a validation instrument, linking the operational outcomes of the UCs with exploitation pathways, including the evaluation and support of KERs.** More specifically, the process helps demonstrate how business value can be unlocked through interoperability, flexibility aggregation, and data valorisation - reinforcing InterSTORE's impact in real-world energy systems.

3.1.1 KERs Outcomes from the Overall InterSTORE Business Model

The overall InterSTORE Business Model - outlined in D4.4 - highlights how interoperability, trust, and standardisation collectively unlock economic, social, and environmental value across the energy ecosystem. The integrated framework demonstrates that the four KERs form a coherent value chain - each addressing a specific bottleneck in the digitalisation and integration of DERs:

- **Interoperability as the core value engine:** The analysis confirms that market access, reduced integration costs, and faster time-to-market depend on open, vendor-neutral interoperability. This is the cornerstone of KER1 (interoperable client/server library) and KER2 (legacy protocol converter), which together facilitate smooth communication between devices and EMS, supporting both greenfield deployments and integration of existing (brownfield) systems at DSOs, campuses, and residential sites.
- **Trusted Data Spaces enabling monetisable data flows:** Scalable and secure energy services - such as settlement, diagnostics, and carbon-aware dispatch - require trusted, governed data exchange. Here, KER4 plays a pivotal role by enabling verifiable, permissioned data sharing among OEMs, aggregators, and community operators, paving the way for new data-as-a-service business models and value creation.
- **Quality assurance as a catalyst for adoption:** Market actors increasingly demand transparent verification of standards compliance before integrating assets. KER3 (testing

tool) directly responds to this need by reducing certification risks and engineering time, streamlining procurement, and boosting stakeholder confidence in Virtual Power Plant (VPP) and DER onboarding processes.

- **Economic results to leverage for exploitation:** The InterSTORE ecosystem demonstrates tangible financial benefits, including:
 - Revenues from multi-market flexibility services and avoided energy or network costs through aggregated hybrid DER portfolios.
 - Lower integration and commissioning costs thanks to IEEE 2030.5 compatibility and connector reuse, leading to shorter sales cycles for OEMs and integrators.
 - New recurring income streams from diagnostics, performance benchmarking, and carbon-aware optimisation—enabled by KER1/2 for data capture and KER4 for governed data exchange.
- **Social results to leverage:** The KERs collectively contribute to higher user acceptance through transparency, participatory governance, and data sovereignty. By integrating dashboards, guidelines, and governance templates with KER4, and validating them through KER3 test results, InterSTORE strengthens social trust and supports citizen-centred energy participation.
- **Environmental results to leverage:** The InterSTORE KERs enable higher renewable energy hosting capacity, reduced curtailment, and extended asset lifetimes through predictive maintenance and hybrid control. They can thus be positioned as key enablers of measurable sustainability KPIs – such as avoided curtailment and lifecycle efficiency gains – of particular relevance to DSOs and municipalities.
- **Replication and market uptake strategy:** To maximise impact, replication should prioritise sectors with strong interoperability needs and clear ROI potential – such as aggregators, DSOs, and Original Equipment Manufacturer (OEM) after-sales services. KERs should be offered as a coherent package that include also the following: (i) reference architectures and adapters (KER1/2), (ii) conformance and validation reports (KER3), and (iii) data-sharing agreements and consent policies (KER4). These offerings can be reinforced through pilot evidence, aligned KPIs, and the TLBMC developed within InterSTORE.

3.2 KERs Contribution to InterSTORE UCs Business Models

Leveraging the analysis carried out in D4.4 – to define the business models associated to each of InterSTORE UCs – and the outcomes of the surveys filled by UC owners on the relevance, performance and exploitation potential of the four KERs of the project, **below potential contributions of each KER to the business models of the UCs – where they performed better – are outlined.**

3.2.1 KER1: Interoperable client/server library

3.2.1.1 UC1: DES Flexibility Market Monetisation & UC2: Energy community DES utilisation

Across UC1 and UC2, KER1 acts as a core interoperability enabler, facilitating efficient and standardised data exchange between distributed energy resources and energy management platforms via IEEE 2030.5. By reducing integration complexity and costs, it supports scalable market participation for aggregators and prosumers (UC1) while strengthening local energy autonomy and collective energy management in communities (UC2). Beyond economic efficiency, KER1 fosters social inclusion and trust by enabling transparent, real-time visibility of asset performance, revenues, and flexibility potential, supporting the transition from passive consumers to active prosumers. Environmentally, its open and interoperable design enables

optimised coordination of renewables and storage, contributing to higher renewable integration, reduced curtailment, and lower emissions at both grid and community levels. A more extensive assessment is provided in Annex 8.5.1.1.

3.2.1.1.1 SWOT & PEST Analysis

The table below outlines the most relevant factors positively or negatively impacting the realisation of the business models of these UCs and, therefore of KER1, if applied in such contexts.

Dimension	Consolidated Analysis (SWOT-PEST)
<i>Strengths</i> (Internal & Enabling Context)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Strong alignment with EU Green Deal, digitalisation and consumer empowerment policies supports adoption and scalability. - Ability to monetise DER flexibility and reduce dependence on fossil-based energy, particularly under rising electricity prices. - Use of recognised standards (e.g. IEEE 2030.5, Open Data Space connectors) enhances interoperability, trust and replicability across Member States. - Smart EMS, optimisation and forecasting tools enable high DER penetration and effective community-level energy management.
<i>Weaknesses</i> (Internal & Structural Barriers)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - High upfront CAPEX for EMS, ICT infrastructure and DER integration may limit short-term feasibility, especially for smaller or less-resourced communities. - Limited data quality, digitalisation gaps and fragmented regulatory frameworks across Member States can hinder smooth implementation. - Weak local engagement, governance capacity and digital skills may reduce uptake and operational effectiveness.
<i>Opportunities</i> (External & Market Drivers)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Increasing public demand for clean, affordable and local energy systems creates favourable social acceptance. - Rising electricity prices strengthen incentives for flexibility monetisation, self-consumption and community energy models. - Policy support for energy communities, harmonised regulations and standardised flexibility markets can accelerate deployment. - New business models enabled by interoperability, platform-based services, gamification and transparent flexibility tools support long-term sustainability.
<i>Threats</i> (External Risks & Constraints)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Market volatility and uncertain investment conditions may delay large-scale deployment. - Risk of technology lock-in if standards or platforms are not widely adopted or remain insufficiently open. - Digital divide and insufficient digital literacy may exclude vulnerable user groups, undermining social fairness.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Cybersecurity, data privacy and GDPR compliance risks could reduce trust if not properly addressed.
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Table 13 KER1-UC1&UC2 SWOT-PEST analysis

3.2.1.2 UC4: Innovative Frequency Services & UC7: Adaptive BESS Management for Autonomous Grid Operation

For UC4 and UC7, KER1 functions as a key interoperability backbone enabling standardised, low-latency communication between hybrid energy storage systems, control platforms, and grid operators. By supporting advanced services such as frequency regulation, virtual inertia, and autonomous grid operation, it enhances grid stability and resilience in systems with high renewable penetration. Economically, KER1 can lower integration and transaction costs while increasing the monetisation potential of hybrid flexibility assets across multiple ancillary and balancing markets. Socially, its transparent and secure data exchange framework strengthens trust, traceability, and user confidence in digitalised flexibility solutions, fostering broader acceptance of autonomous and hybrid grid operations. Environmentally, KER1 enables more efficient coordination and optimisation of HESS, supporting higher renewable integration, reduced curtailment, and improved lifecycle management of storage assets. A more extensive assessment is provided in Annex 8.5.1.2.

3.2.1.2.1 SWOT & PEST Analysis

The table below outlines the most relevant factors positively or negatively impacting the realisation of the business models of these UCs and, therefore of KER1, if applied in such contexts.

Dimension	Consolidated Analysis (SWOT-PEST)
<i>Strengths</i> (Internal & Enabling Context)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Contribution to enhanced hybrid flexibility services (fast frequency response, virtual inertia, oscillation damping), addressing stability needs in low-inertia grids. - Potential reduction of CAPEX and balancing service costs compared to single-technology solutions, while extending battery lifetime through hybridisation. - High interoperability enabled by IEEE 2030.5 and advanced EMS supports multi-service provision and replicability across EU markets. - Alignment with EU objectives on renewables integration, grid stability, digitalisation and interoperable energy systems.
<i>Weaknesses</i> (Internal & Structural Barriers)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Complex system design and operation due to multi-component HESS architectures, increasing implementation and operational risks. - Significant upfront investment costs and need for specialised expertise for HESS deployment, operation and maintenance. - Scalability challenges in diverse grid contexts and limited experience with large-scale hybrid solutions. - User concerns related to affordability and the technical novelty of hybrid energy storage systems.

<p><i>Opportunities</i> (External & Market Drivers)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Growing EU demand for inertia, fast frequency response and balancing services in increasingly renewables-dominated and low-inertia grids. - Increasing interest in resilient power systems, autonomous microgrids and island-mode operation, where HESS offer clear advantages. - Emerging market opportunities for technology providers delivering interoperable, standard-compliant hybrid storage and control solutions. - Policy momentum towards open, replicable and interoperable solutions can accelerate market uptake.
<p><i>Threats</i> (External Risks & Constraints)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Regulatory uncertainty and incomplete remuneration schemes for virtual inertia and fast frequency response services may weaken investment signals. - Competition from alternative flexibility and grid-stability solutions could limit market penetration. - Cybersecurity and data-privacy risks associated with increased reliance on IEEE 2030.5 communication and open Data Spaces. - Limited investor confidence in complex and relatively novel hybrid storage solutions.

Table 14 KER1-UC4&UC7 SWOT-PEST analysis

3.2.2 KER2: Legacy system protocol converter

3.2.2.1 UC3: Grid Supporting BESS & UC8: Multiphysics Flexibility Optimisation for Home Management Systems and their Global Integration

For UC3 and UC8, KER2 acts as a critical enabler for integrating legacy energy assets into modern, interoperable energy management ecosystems. By translating protocols such as Modbus and MQTT into IEEE 2030.5, the LPC lowers technical and economic barriers to participation for DSOs, campus operators, technology providers, and aggregators, while allowing existing batteries, PV systems, and heat pumps to connect seamlessly with advanced EMS platforms. Economically, KER2 reduces integration effort, CAPEX, and vendor lock-in risks, accelerating deployment and market participation of grid-supporting and residential flexibility assets. Socially, it promotes inclusiveness by preventing technological exclusion of legacy systems, supporting user trust, skills development, and community-level acceptance of digital energy solutions. Environmentally, KER2 extends asset lifetimes, reduces e-waste, and supports higher renewable integration through improved coordination and optimisation of distributed resources. A more extensive assessment is provided in Annex 8.5.2.1.

3.2.2.1.1 SWOT & PEST Analysis

The table below outlines the most relevant factors positively or negatively impacting the realisation of the business models of these UCs and, therefore of KER2, if applied in such contexts.

Dimension	Consolidated Analysis (SWOT-PEST)
<i>Strengths</i> (Internal & Enabling Context)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Reduction of engineering time and deployment costs for BESS through IEEE 2030.5-based interoperability and re-use of standardised solutions across user segments. - Improved scalability and cost efficiency enabled by sector coupling and cross-domain flexibility optimisation. - Support to consumer-centric models by enhancing prosumer participation, collective flexibility and energy democracy, particularly in community and household contexts. - Contribution to local demand balancing, increased grid resilience and deferred grid reinforcement needs.
<i>Weaknesses</i> (Internal & Structural Barriers)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - High upfront CAPEX remains a significant barrier for small operators and households, despite long-term system benefits. - Limited household engagement due to low digital literacy, poor understanding of digitalised energy systems and reluctance to change consumption habits. - Additional hardware requirements may increase environmental footprint if not accompanied by dedicated circularity and standardisation strategies.
<i>Opportunities</i> (External & Market Drivers)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Strong alignment with EU and national policies on sector coupling, demand-side flexibility, digitalisation and prosumer empowerment. - Growing market opportunities for aggregators and technology providers delivering interoperable, consumer-centric flexibility services. - Proven cost savings through upscaling improve competitiveness and support wider deployment of distributed energy storage. - System-level benefits, including avoided or deferred grid reinforcement, reduced system costs for DSOs and enhanced local resilience.
<i>Threats</i> (External Risks & Constraints)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Regulatory uncertainty and heterogeneous implementation of interoperability and data governance frameworks across EU jurisdictions. - Risk of social exclusion of low-income or digitally vulnerable households, potentially undermining fairness and public acceptance. - Investor hesitancy due to perceived complexity, long pay-back periods and uncertainty of emerging business models.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Insufficient clarity on circular economy requirements for sector-coupling technologies could slow sustainable scaling.
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Table 15 KER2-UC3&UC8 SWOT-PEST analysis

3.2.3 KER3: Testing procedure and software tool

3.2.3.1 UC9 - Management of EV Charging Clusters as HESS

For UC9, KER3 provides a quality-assurance and validation layer that strengthens the technical reliability and market readiness of EV charging clusters operated as hybrid energy systems and VPPs. By offering automated testing and reporting of IEEE 2030.5-compliant communication, the TPST reduces integration, validation, and certification costs for TSOs, aggregators, BSPs, and EMS developers, while lowering deployment risks. Economically, KER3 supports scalable flexibility market participation by preventing interoperability errors, minimising downtime, and improving operational continuity. Socially, it enhances trust, transparency, and accountability in digitalised flexibility services through reproducible, standard-based validation, while its open-source design supports capacity building and wider access to compliance tools. Environmentally, KER3 contributes indirectly to more efficient and sustainable EV and DER integration by reducing resource-intensive testing processes, avoiding system inefficiencies, and enabling precise, standards-compliant operation of aggregated assets. A more extensive assessment is provided in Annex 8.5.3.1.

3.2.3.1.1 SWOT & PEST Analysis

The table below outlines the most relevant factors positively or negatively impacting the realisation of the business models of this UC and, therefore of KER3, if applied in such contexts.

Dimension	Consolidated Analysis (SWOT-PEST)
<i>Strengths</i> (Internal & Enabling Context)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Facilitation of EV charger integration into HESS frameworks and aggregation of small-scale DERs, including PV and EV assets, accelerating decarbonisation pathways. - Virtualisation of storage and compliance with standardised protocols support interoperable and scalable deployment. - Contribution to demand-side flexibility and aggregator participation through smart platforms and coordinated DER operation. - Alignment with policy objectives promoting flexible grids, consumer rights and clean energy integration.
<i>Weaknesses</i> (Internal & Structural Barriers)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Limited access to live flexibility markets and lack of technical expertise for DER set-up and coordination may constrain large-scale deployment. - Readiness gaps of DER assets and insufficient user awareness reduce operational effectiveness and participation levels. - High hardware and set-up costs hinder participation of small companies and prosumers.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Weak alignment between DER characteristics and market signals, combined with limited investment capacity, may delay uptake.
<i>Opportunities</i> (External & Market Drivers)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Expansion of flexibility markets and growing platform ecosystems for VPP management enable new business models and revenue streams. - Reduction of entry barriers through consolidation of interoperable smart platforms facilitating participation of diverse stakeholders. - Increasing public awareness of the need for flexible energy provision and remote management supports wider acceptance. - Availability of subsidies and investment support for smart grids and clean energy solutions across EU markets.
<i>Threats</i> (External Risks & Constraints)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Regulatory fragmentation across national jurisdictions affecting consumer participation rights and aggregator integration. - Competitive pressure from alternative DER technologies and established market actors with higher technical and market expertise. - Cybersecurity, data privacy and safety risks associated with increased interconnectivity and remote control of assets. - Market volatility and price fluctuations creating uncertainty in revenue predictability and reducing user motivation.

Table 16 KER3- SWOT-PEST analysis

3.2.4 KER4: InterSTORE Data Space Connector

3.2.4.1 UC3: Grid Supporting BESS

For UC3, KER4 provides a trusted data-exchange backbone that strengthens the operation and monetisation of grid-supporting BESS through secure, standardised, and decentralised data sharing. By leveraging IDS-based Data Spaces and blockchain-enabled traceability, the InterSTORE DSC enables DSOs, aggregators, and technology providers to exchange operational and performance data under controlled access conditions, reinforcing trust, data sovereignty, and regulatory compliance. Economically, KER4 can reduce data management and integration costs while enabling new data-driven services and revenue models, supporting scalable and vendor-neutral interoperability. Socially, it promotes transparency, accountability, and stakeholder confidence by ensuring permission-based data sharing and preserving control over sensitive information. Environmentally, KER4 indirectly supports more efficient grid-supporting BESS operation by enabling real-time, data-driven optimisation, improved asset monitoring, and longer system lifetimes, contributing to more sustainable and resilient digital energy ecosystems. A more extensive assessment is provided in Annex 8.5.4.1.

3.2.4.1.1 SWOT & PEST Analysis

The table below outlines the most relevant factors positively or negatively impacting the realisation of the business models of this UC and, therefore of KER4, if applied in such contexts.

Dimension	Consolidated Analysis (SWOT-PEST)
<i>Strengths</i> (Internal & Enabling Context)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Reduction of engineering time and deployment costs for BESS through IEEE 2030.5-based interoperability and re-use of standardised solutions across user segments. - Improved scalability and cost efficiency enabled by sector coupling and interoperable data exchange. - Support to demand-side flexibility and prosumer participation, contributing to balanced local demand and increased grid resilience. - Strong alignment with EU and national policies on digitalisation, sector coupling and interoperability.
<i>Weaknesses</i> (Internal & Structural Barriers)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - High upfront CAPEX remains a significant barrier for small operators and households despite long-term system benefits. - Limited household engagement due to low digital literacy, insufficient understanding of digitalised systems and reluctance to change consumption habits. - Additional hardware requirements may increase environmental footprint if not supported by appropriate circular economy and standardisation strategies.
<i>Opportunities</i> (External & Market Drivers)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Growing political and regulatory support for sector coupling, demand-side flexibility and prosumer participation across EU markets. - Market opportunities for aggregators and technology providers to deliver consumer-centric, interoperable flexibility services. - Proven cost savings through upscaling enhance competitiveness and accelerate deployment of distributed energy storage. - System-level benefits, including avoided or deferred grid reinforcement, resulting in reduced costs for DSOs and improved local grid resilience.
<i>Threats</i> (External Risks & Constraints)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Regulatory uncertainty and heterogeneous implementation across EU Member States affecting interoperability and data exchange. - Investor reluctance due to perceived complexity, uncertainty of business models and long payback periods. - Risk of social exclusion of low-income or digitally vulnerable households, potentially undermining fairness and acceptance. - Insufficient clarity on circular economy requirements could slow sustainable scaling.

Table 17 KER4-UC3 SWOT-PEST analysis

3.2.4.2 UC5 - Hybrid Floating Storage Flexibility Monitoring

In UC5, KER4 provides a trusted digital framework for hybrid floating storage systems by enabling secure, standardised, and sovereign data exchange across multi-technology assets, including Li-ion, vanadium flow, and second-life batteries. Through blockchain-enabled traceability and semantic data catalogues, the InterSTORE Data Space Connector supports transparent validation of performance, lifetime, and sustainability metrics, strengthening regulatory compliance and confidence in second-life battery deployment. Economically, KER4 can reduce administrative and verification costs while facilitating participation in flexibility and balancing markets through reliable data sharing. Socially, it enhances acceptance of circular storage solutions by ensuring transparent, verifiable, and secure access to safety and performance information. Environmentally, KER4 supports data-driven optimisation, extended asset lifetimes, and measurable reductions in e-waste and resource use, reinforcing the sustainability value of hybrid energy storage systems. A more extensive assessment is provided in Annex 8.5.4.2.

3.2.4.2.1 SWOT & PEST Analysis

The table below outlines the most relevant factors positively or negatively impacting the realisation of the business models of this UC and, therefore of KER4, if applied in such contexts.

Dimension	Consolidated Analysis (SWOT-PEST)
<i>Strengths</i> (Internal & Enabling Context)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Support to hybrid and second-life battery systems enabling load balancing, peak shaving and frequency regulation, thereby improving system efficiency and asset utilisation. - Contribution to circular economy objectives through battery reuse, extended material lifetimes and reduced lifecycle costs. - Promotion of IEEE 2030.5 and other interoperability standards via the DSC, supporting scalability and long-term regulatory compliance. - Increased prosumer trust and willingness to participate through transparent, user-centric and standard-compliant digital solutions.
<i>Weaknesses</i> (Internal & Structural Barriers)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Technical complexity in the design, operation and management of hybrid and second-life storage systems. - Significant upfront investment requirements and uncertain return on investment. - Performance variability and limited predictability of second-life battery lifespan may constrain replication and up-scaling. - Low user participation and response rates can reduce flexibility potential.
<i>Opportunities</i> (External & Market Drivers)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Strong alignment with EU and national policies promoting flexibility, digitalisation, circular economy and electrification. - Growing demand for e-mobility and electrification increases the value of flexible and distributed storage solutions.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Opportunities for aggregators and DSOs to efficiently monetise flexibility and promote user-centric market structures. - Operational cost reductions and deferred grid reinforcement create additional system-level economic benefits.
<i>Threats</i> (External Risks & Constraints)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Regulatory uncertainty regarding aggregator roles, battery certification requirements and liability for second-life batteries. - Strong competition from more mature or technologically advanced storage and flexibility solutions. - Cybersecurity and data privacy risks associated with increased digitalisation, AI-based optimisation and interoperability. - Persisting uncertainty on investment conditions may slow large-scale adoption.

Table 18 KER4-UC5 SWOT-PEST analysis

3.2.4.3 UC9 - Management of EV Charging Clusters as HESS

In UC9, KER4 enables secure, standardised, and decentralised data exchange for the management of EV charging clusters as hybrid energy storage systems. By leveraging data-space principles and blockchain-based verification, the InterSTORE Data Space Connector supports trusted interoperability between DERs, aggregators, and system operators, facilitating reliable VPP operation and flexibility provisioning. Economically, KER4 can improve market efficiency and scalability by automating data sharing, reducing operational overhead, and enabling data-driven business models for aggregators and BSPs. Socially, it strengthens trust, accountability, and inclusiveness by ensuring transparent, auditable, and sovereign data exchanges, allowing prosumers and smaller actors to participate under fair conditions. Environmentally, KER4 supports data-driven optimisation of EV charging, storage, and renewable integration, contributing to higher renewable utilisation, reduced curtailment, and lower reliance on fossil-based balancing resources. A more extensive assessment is provided in Annex 8.5.4.3.

3.2.4.3.1 SWOT & PEST Analysis

The table below outlines the most relevant factors positively or negatively impacting the realisation of the business models of this UC and, therefore of KER4, if applied in such contexts

Dimension	Consolidated Analysis (SWOT-PEST)
<i>Strengths</i> (Internal & Enabling Context)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Facilitation of EV charger integration into HESS frameworks and aggregation of small-scale DERs, including PV and EV assets, accelerating decarbonisation pathways. - Virtualisation of storage and compliance with standardised protocols support interoperable, scalable and market-ready deployment. - Support to demand-side flexibility and aggregator participation through smart platforms and coordinated DER operation.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Alignment with EU policy objectives promoting flexible grids, consumer rights and clean energy investments.
<i>Weaknesses</i> (Internal & Structural Barriers)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Limited access to real-time flexibility markets and lack of technical expertise for DER set-up and coordination constrain large-scale deployment. - Readiness gaps of DER assets and insufficient user awareness reduce participation and operational performance. - High hardware and set-up costs hinder participation of small companies and prosumers. - Weak alignment between DER characteristics and market signals, combined with limited investment capacity, may delay uptake.
<i>Opportunities</i> (External & Market Drivers)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Expansion of flexibility markets and growing VPP platform ecosystems enable scalability and new business cases across EU energy markets. - Reduction of entry barriers through consolidation of interoperable smart platforms facilitating participation of diverse stakeholders. - Availability of subsidies and investment support for smart grids, clean energy and flexible infrastructure. - Increasing public awareness of the need for flexible and digitally enabled energy systems supports acceptance.
<i>Threats</i> (External Risks & Constraints)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Regulatory fragmentation across national jurisdictions affecting aggregator integration and consumer participation. - Competitive pressure from alternative DER technologies and established market actors with stronger market expertise. - Cybersecurity, data privacy and safety risks associated with increased interconnectivity and remote control. - Market volatility and price fluctuations creating uncertainty in revenue predictability and reducing user motivation.

Table 19 KER4- SWOT-PEST analysis

4 Knowledge, Data and IPR Management

4.1 Intellectual Property Rights

The InterSTORE project has implemented a comprehensive and structured **Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) management framework** in full compliance with Horizon Europe rules and the Grant Agreement (GA No. 101096511). This framework ensures legal certainty, protects partners' legitimate interests, and supports the effective exploitation, dissemination, and long-term sustainability of project results.

In line with Horizon Europe requirements, all partners identified and declared pre-existing intellectual property, know-how, and data ("**Background**") necessary for the implementation of the project or the exploitation of its results. Background includes any tangible or intangible assets held by beneficiaries prior to accession to the Grant Agreement, including rights held through ownership, licensing agreements, or other legal arrangements. Only intellectual property rights for which applications were filed before accession to the Grant Agreement were considered Background, unless explicitly agreed otherwise. **Participation in InterSTORE did not affect ownership of Background**, which remained entirely with the respective partners. **All declared Background and any associated restrictions were documented in the Consortium Agreement.**

All project-generated outcomes are defined as "**Results**" under Horizon Europe terminology, replacing the former concept of "Foreground". Results include any tangible or intangible outputs of the project, such as data, software, know-how, documentation, and intellectual property rights, whether or not they are protectable. In accordance with Article 16 of the Grant Agreement, **Results are owned by the beneficiaries that generated them.** Joint ownership applies where Results are jointly created and cannot be separated or individually attributed.

Access rights to Background and Results are granted among partners only where necessary for project implementation or for the exploitation of their own Results. Such access is provided under fair and reasonable conditions, which may include royalty-free or financial terms depending on the scope and purpose of use. Unless otherwise agreed, access rights are non-exclusive and do not include the right to sub-license. Requests for access may be made until one year after the end of the project, in accordance with the Grant Agreement and Consortium Agreement provisions.

Protection of Results was assessed on a case-by-case basis, taking into account exploitation potential, commercial relevance, and the legitimate interests of all partners. Exploitation of Results includes their use in further research, product and service development, standardisation activities, and market deployment. **Partners may exploit their Results through transfer or licensing, provided that Grant Agreement obligations are respected and that other beneficiaries' access rights are preserved.** Exclusive licences may only be granted where all concerned beneficiaries have waived their access rights.

Dissemination and open access were carried out in accordance with Article 17 of the Grant Agreement. Results were disseminated as soon as feasible in publicly accessible formats,

while ensuring that protection, confidentiality, and legitimate interests were not compromised. **Public project outputs**, including reports, software artefacts, and selected datasets, **are made openly available through the InterSTORE Zenodo repository** (as further detailed in Deliverables D2.4, D5.1, D5.3, and D7.4), ensuring long-term accessibility and compliance with Horizon Europe Open Science requirements. At the same time, operational and sensitive data generated within the use cases was managed through governed data-sharing mechanisms aligned with data-space principles, rather than unrestricted publication. Partners were required to notify each other in advance of any planned dissemination, allowing time for objections where necessary. Confidential information identified as sensitive was handled in accordance with Article 13 of the Grant Agreement and protected throughout the project and beyond where required by law or agreement/

Through this integrated and balanced approach, **InterSTORE ensured responsible knowledge management, safeguarded intellectual property, and enabled both open innovation and effective exploitation**, thereby reinforcing the project's contribution to the European research and innovation ecosystem.

4.2 Open-Source Licensing

Open-source licensing defines the legal conditions under which software can be used, modified, and redistributed, enabling transparency, interoperability, and collaborative development. Within InterSTORE, **open-source licenses are a key enabler for broad adoption, long-term sustainability, and alignment with European open-science and open-innovation principles**. Different license models provide varying levels of permissiveness and control, allowing projects to balance openness with industrial and commercial requirements. The selection of appropriate licenses is therefore essential to support interoperability, reuse, and exploitation of project results while safeguarding partners' interests.

4.2.1 IPR Management and InterSTORE Open-Source Tools

The project has implemented a comprehensive IPR management strategy to ensure that all software results are properly protected, traceable, and exploitable by both the consortium partners and external users. A key element of this strategy has been the release of all software tools as **open source on GitHub**, making the project outcomes openly available to the research and industrial communities.

This approach supports transparency, fosters collaboration, and maximises the long-term impact and sustainability of the project's technological assets. This section provides an overview of the open-source tools released by the consortium, their hosting locations, the adopted licensing scheme, and the measures taken to ensure proper license management and compliance.

4.2.1.1 Open-Source Policy

Already at the early stages of the project, the consortium agreed to adopt a unified open-source policy, aligned with the project's exploitation and dissemination objectives. The open-source release of the project tools aims to:

- **promote transparency and reproducibility of results;**
- **facilitate collaboration and technology transfer between academia and industry;**

- ensure sustainability and long-term visibility of project outcomes beyond its lifetime.

To achieve these goals, the consortium adopted a permissive licensing approach, selecting the **MIT License as the default option for most software components**. This license was chosen for its simplicity, flexibility, and wide compatibility - allowing unrestricted reuse, modification, and redistribution with minimal conditions (attribution only). The permissive nature of the MIT license encourages both research and commercial uptake, ensuring that the developed tools can be integrated, extended, or embedded in third-party solutions with no major legal constraints.

4.2.1.2 Inventory of Open-Source Tools

4.2.1.2.1 WP2 Tools

The following table lists all the open-source tools developed in WP2 of the InterSTORE project.

Tool/Component	Description	Repository/Location	License	Responsible Partner	Release Tag/Version
Interoperable client/server for Distributed Energy Storage - KER1	Interoperable Client/Server for IEEE 2030.5 communication between devices and EMS systems	https://github.com/Horizont-Europe-Interstore/Client-Server	MIT	CYG	May 13, 2025
Legacy systems protocol converter - KER2	Legacy Systems Protocol Converter for IEEE 2030.5	https://github.com/Horizont-Europe-Interstore/Legacy-Protocol-Converter	MIT	SUN	v1.5.2 (Oct 2, 2025)
Testing procedures and software tools - KER3	IEEE 2030.5 Testing procedures and software tools	https://github.com/Horizont-Europe-Interstore/Testing-procedure-and-software-tools	MIT	RWTH	v1.3.0 (Nov 2025)
Interoperable Data Spaces Framework - KER4	Energy Data Space Connector Framework	https://github.com/Horizont-Europe-Interstore/Data-Space-Connector	MIT	ENG	v1.3.2 (Mar 28, 2025)

Table 20 InterSTORE WP2 open-source tools

4.2.1.2.2 Other Project Tools

The following table lists all the other tools developed in the InterSTORE project.

Tool/Component	Description	Repository/Location	License	Responsible Partner	Release Tag/Version
Data Space Valorisation Cases	Four valorisation cases leveraging on data exchange from the InterSTORE Data Space	https://github.com/Horizont-Europe-Interstore/DataSpace_Valorization_Cases	MIT	INESC	Sep 10, 2025

HESS sizing tool	HESS hybrid-isation sizing tool	https://github.com/Horizont-Europe-Interstore/Hybrid-Storage-Sizing-Model	MIT	INESC	Apr 18, 2024
HESDD dispatch	HESS dispatch	Battery dispatch (including HESS) micro service for HEMS	Proprietary - EULA	INESC	May 30, 2024

Table 21 InterSTORE other WPs open-source tools

4.2.1.2.3 License Management

Proper license management was essential to ensure legal compliance and consistency across all open-source repositories. **Each GitHub repository includes the following:**

- **LICENSE file containing the full text of the MIT License;**
- **README file referencing in details the installation steps and usage guidelines.**

Each release version was tagged in Git and corresponds to a reviewed, license-cleared codebase. This systematic approach guarantees that all project outputs hosted on GitHub are fully compliant with open-source licensing requirements and can be reused safely by external developers, researchers, and companies.

4.2.1.3 Ownership and Governance

Ownership of each software component remains with the partner(s) that developed it, as defined in the project's Consortium Agreement. By releasing their code under the MIT License, partners grant the public the right to use, modify, and distribute the software under very permissive conditions. Each repository is maintained by a designated technical partner responsible for reviewing contributions, managing releases, and ensuring the overall quality of the codebase. Contributions from external users are handled transparently through GitHub's pull request system, ensuring traceability and respect of license conditions.

4.2.1.4 Sustainability and Future Use

All open-source repositories are hosted on GitHub and will remain publicly available after the end of the project, ensuring that the developed tools continue to generate value over time. The GitHub organisation will serve as the long-term access point for the project's software results, preserving both source code and documentation.

4.3 KERs IPR Overview

To ensure a consistent and transparent approach to IP management across the four InterSTORE KERs, dedicated surveys – as outlined in Annex 2 – were conducted with the respective KER owners. The objective of these surveys was to identify, document, and assess the IP aspects associated with each KER – in line with Horizon Europe's IPR requirements and best practices – and to complement on what is reported in the previous section.

The surveys collected structured information on five main dimensions:

✓ IP identification , addressing whether the KER introduces new knowledge, processes, or technologies, and whether any background IP was used in its development;
✓ Ownership and rights allocation , clarifying the entities holding IPR ownership and the existence of any formalised or joint ownership agreements;
✓ Protection strategy , examining whether protection measures such as patents, copyrights, or open-source licences have been implemented;
✓ Next steps , identifying planned actions for securing or managing IP;

✓ **Support needs**, exploring whether partners foresee the need for further legal, technical, or administrative assistance in IPR matters.

Table 22 KERs IPR survey dimensions

This systematic collection of information supports the project's overall IPR management framework, ensuring that all exploitable results are properly tracked, their ownership is clearly attributed, and protection or exploitation pathways are well defined. The following tables present a synthesis of the information gathered from KER owners through these surveys.

4.3.1 KER1: Interoperable client/server library

KER1 involves **new know-how** developed within the project. **No background IP was used** in its creation. **The ownership of the KER lies with SUN**, and the result has been **open-sourced under an MIT licence**, ensuring free access and reuse in line with open innovation principles. **No formal ownership or joint ownership agreements** were deemed necessary given the open-source model adopted. As a result, **no specific IPR protection measures** - such as patents or trademarks - have been pursued. **No additional support or further steps are currently planned** for IPR management, as the licensing framework already guarantees the intended accessibility and exploitation potential of the KER.

4.3.2 KER2: Legacy system protocol converter

KER2 involves **new software** developed within the project. **No background IP was used** in its creation. **The ownership of the KER lies with SUN**, and the result has been **open-sourced**, ensuring free access and reuse in line with open innovation principles. **Ownership agreements have been formalised, while no joint ownership arrangements are in place**. **No specific IPR protection measures** - such as patents, trademarks, or copyrights- have been pursued, as the software has been released under an open-source model. **No additional support or further steps are currently planned** for IPR management, as the open-source approach already guarantees the intended accessibility and exploitation potential of the KER.

4.3.3 KER3: Testing procedure and software tool

KER3 involves **new knowledge and a utility model** developed within the project. **Background IP was used** in its creation. **The ownership of the KER lies with ACS/RWTH, with formal ownership and joint ownership agreements in place**. The joint ownership is open-source, ensuring free access and reuse in line with open innovation principles. **No specific IPR protection measures** - such as patents or trademarks - have been pursued, as the KER has been released under an open-source approach. **No additional support or further steps are currently planned** for IPR management, as the open-source model already guarantees the intended accessibility and exploitation potential of the KER.

4.3.4 KER4: InterSTORE Data Space Connector

KER4 involves **new knowledge and the development of the Energy Data Space Framework**, which includes software and documentation released under open-source licenses (MIT and GPL). **Background IP was used** in its creation, specifically the OneNet Connector. **The ownership of the KER currently lies with ENG, with no formal ownership or joint ownership agreements yet established**. Access and usage terms among partners are pending formalisation. **No specific IPR protection measures** - such as patents or trademarks - have been pursued at this stage. The next steps include formalising access and usage terms

among partners to ensure alignment with the selected open-source licenses and enable future exploitation. **No additional support or further steps are currently required** for IPR management.

5 Standardisation

5.1 Standardisation in connection with exploitation

In general, standardisation makes new trends visible, knowledge is disseminated worldwide, economic growth is stimulated by higher productivity and improved quality, and bundled knowledge in form of printed and digital documents is accessible to everyone worldwide for application.

The following chapters show the **connection of InterSTORE to Technical Committees (TC), Subcommittees (SC) and Working Groups (WG) of IEC/CENELEC and how updates of their standardisation work are disseminated**. Furthermore, the incorporation of results into existing or future standards is described.

5.2 Matrix: InterSTORE WPs and IEC/CENELEC Technical Committees

Due to the vast number of technical expert groups at IEC and CENELEC a structured approach was chosen to show InterSTORE Work Package (WP) requirements and existing expert groups in a matrix [33] [92]. The full matrix can be found in Annex 8.4.

The matrix shows IEC and CENELEC TC, SC, WG and their relevance to the InterSTORE work WP: WP1: Requirements, Use Cases, Specifications; WP2: Open-Source Interoperability Toolkit; WP3: Dimensioning, Testing and Integration; WP4: Multiservice and Flexibility Monetisation; WP5: Pilots Demonstration; WP6: Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation.

The relevance is ranked in ascending importance:

- **Level 1** - awareness: subject should be known, action is currently not necessary;
- **Level 2** - follow: activity which should be monitored (passive work);
- **Level 3** - contribution: activity which requires action and submittance (active work).

Key words for the TC, SC, WG and key words for the InterSTORE WP facilitate the search for InterSTORE partners.

The matrix can be used as follows: WP2 is working in the field of information exchange, key words are communication and protocol converter. Similar key words are used in IEC/TC 57 WG 10. Hence WP2 is connected via level 3 to IEC/TC 57 WG 10. The matrix is a living document and it changed/could have changed while the project was progressing. Reasons for this are:

- Changes in the InterSTORE project activity or WP scope, e.g., due to changes in project objectives, new technical developments affecting the subsequent deliverables and regulatory changes.
- Changes in expert groups or the scope of a TC, e.g., due to new technical developments, new regulatory requirements.

Hence, **the matrix was dependent on feedback from the InterSTORE project partners**.

Required feedback includes:

- Update of key words describing the InterSTORE WP scope;
- Update of the relevance level (1 - awareness, 2 - follow, 3 - contribution);

- Active review of the project progress: changes of the WP scope or project activities;
- Active review of standardisation documents.

In summary, the matrix is a strategic tool which links the InterSTORE project to the selected TC/SC and associated WG. It is a living document requiring contribution from all InterSTORE project partners.

5.3 Regular standardisation/regulation update newsletters

This chapter explains how regular **standardisation/regulation update newsletters** informed the InterSTORE project partners about relevant standardisation and regulation activities.

- Set-up of a "Standardisation/Regulation Blog";
- Every InterSTORE team member was encouraged to use this chat possibility for standardisation and regulation discussions or questions;
- VDE DKE posted newsletters with news or progress of the in D1.1 - Report on Standardisation, activities and regulatory requirements identified relevant TC and SC IEC/TC 120, IEC/TC 21, IEC/TC 57, IEC/TC 8 (SC 8A, SC 8B, SC 8C), CLC/TC 8x, IEC/TC 69, as well as information about IEEE 2030.5, ENTSO-E network codes, IEC/SyC Smart Energy and ISO/IEC JTC 1;
- If interested, draft documents of any TC can be provided. Contacts to the TC expert community are possible in case of deeper interest or if suitable input can be contributed.

Date	Blog subject
23.04.2024	Welcome
23.04.2024	IEC/TC 120
21.05.2024	IEC/TC 57
25.06.2024	IEEE 2030.5
30.07.2024	IEC/TC 8 + CLC/TC 8x
06.11.2024	IEC/TC 69
15.01.2025	ENTSO-E network codes (part 1)
24.02.2025	ENTSO-E network codes (part 2)
01.04.2025	EU Trusted Data Framework
07.05.2025	IEC/SyC Smart Energy
15.05.2025	CEN-CLC-ETSI CG SG (Coordination Group "Smart Grids")
15.07.2025	ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 41
30.10.2025	ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 42

Table 23 Overview blog posts (until November 2025)

The figure below gives an overview of IEC and CENELEC expert groups which were evaluated as important for InterSTORE.

In summary, this chapter describes the procedures to keep all project partners up to date regarding standardisation and regulation news and updates.

Figure 1 Identified relevant TCs

5.4 Incorporation of results into standards

The progress of the InterSTORE project may lead to updates of standards, technical specifications, or technical reports. Such updates can result from different situations:

- Feedback, e.g., from the pilots, may indicate that information is missing in existing standards. Then the existing standards need to be complemented.
- Progress in the project shows that new developments need to be added in existing standards.
- In the event of a major new technical development, it may be necessary to write a completely new standard.

In the case of the InterSTORE project, it was decided to use the **IEEE 2030.5 standard**. An excursus to IEEE can be found in section 5.5.3. IEC and CENELEC standards are not affected at the moment. However, standardisation experts have been informed about InterSTORE during various dissemination events. Awareness of the connection to the related TC, SC or WG and their activities is essential. An overview of the IEC/CENELEC TC/SC/WG with InterSTORE WG can be found in the matrix in Annex 2.

5.5 Excursus: Standardisation in the USA and Australia

5.5.1 USA

Unlike European countries, the USA has more than 10 national standardisation organisations or associations which develop voluntary consensus standards. In most cases they are also connected globally. With regards to electrotechnology, the USA is a full member of the IEC via U.S. National Committee (USNC), which is a committee of American National Standards Institute (ANSI). Below is an overview of the national standardisation organisations related to electrotechnology:

ANSI/USNC [93]:

Among its leadership roles in all major global and regional standards and accreditation organizations, the is the sole USA representative to the International Organisation for Standardization (ISO), and, through the USNC, to the IEC. ANSI promotes the use of USA standards internationally, advocates USA policy and technical positions in international and

regional standardisation organisations and encourages the adoption of international standards as national standards where they meet the needs of the user community.

IEEE [94]:

The IEEE is the world's largest professional association with more than 395,000 members in around 150 countries. IEEE standards cover a variety of industries including energy, biomedicine and healthcare, IT, telecommunications, transportation, nanotechnology and data security.

ISA [95]:

The International Society of Automation (ISA) (formerly the Instrument Society of America) is a non-profit North American organisation that publishes standards and conducts training programs for automation professionals. ISA also participates in the development of international standards and makes adaptations to standards on electrical equipment for use in potentially explosive atmospheres.

NEMA [96]:

The National Electrical Manufacturers Association (NEMA), the trade association of the US electrical industry, publishes more than 500 standards, application guides and technical documents. NEMA defines standards for electrical connections and develops manufacturing standards for electrical products. NEMA also participates in the standardisation activities of ISO and IEC.

SAE [97]:

The Society of Automotive Engineers (SAE International) is a professional association and standards development organisation for the engineering industry, with a special focus on transport sectors such as automotive, aerospace and commercial vehicles.

UL [98]:

The Underwriters Laboratories (UL) enterprise is a global safety science company. Its subsidiary organisation - UL Standards & Engagement - develops, amongst others, standards for electrical and electronic products. It is accredited in the USA and Canada.

5.5.2 Australia [99]

The national Australian standardisation organisation is called "Standards Australia". Its purpose includes:

- Standards development: offering stakeholders from a variety of sectors a range of pathways to develop or update new or existing standards.
- International participation: participating in the development and adoption of a wide range of International Standards.
- Accreditation of standards development organisations: assessing and approving other organisations to develop Australian Standards.

For every new standard, Standards Australia brings together key parties and stakeholders to form a technical committee. These committees collaborate to develop standards, which are of value to Australia, its businesses, and its people. With stronger standards in place,

Australia can enjoy greater economic efficiency and increased prominence on the international stage. Robust standards also help support local communities by building a safer, more sustainable environment. Although Standards Australia develops standards, they are not responsible for enforcing, regulating or certifying compliance with those standards. Standards Australia is a full member of the IEC.

5.5.3 IEEE and InterSTORE

Of special interest to InterSTORE is IEEE 2030.5 which is described in D1.1 - Report on Standardisation, activities and regulatory requirements.

Smart Energy Profile Application Protocol (IEEE 2030.5):

As InterSTORE decided to use IEEE 2030.5 as a fundamental starting point of the project it is essential to understand its role in comparison within the international standards of CENELEC and IEC.

In the USA, Australia, Canada, Japan and many other countries (Figure 3), DER integration applications employ the IEEE 2030.5 standard, formerly known as Smart Energy Profile 2 (SEP 2) as the communications protocol. As far as the IEEE 2030.5 structure and content is concerned, the IEC 61968 data model is used for the majority of the semantics in the IP-based IEEE 2030.5 standard, which is independent of the underlying physical transport (Wi-Fi, ZigBee, etc.). The IEC 61850-7-420 logical node classes for DER components are adopted by the IEEE 2030.5 standard. The IEEE authorised an update to IEEE 2030.5 in 2018 that adopted changes to bring it into compliance with IEC 61850 extensions for DER.

Figure 2 IEEE 2030.5

Figure 3 Global interest in IEEE 2030.5 as of May 2021

Therefore, IEEE 2030.5 standard focuses on the interoperability of EMS and devices within a smart grid environment. It defines the communication protocols and data models for ex-

changing information between various components, such as smart meters, renewable energy systems, electric vehicles, and energy management systems. IEEE 2030.5 provides a framework for secure, reliable, and efficient communication and control within smart grid infrastructures. In D1.1, IEEE 2030.5 is also compared to IEC 61850 and 61968 in detail, and advantages using it are shown.

In summary, the USA has several national standard developing groups which makes the overview more difficult than in Europe. Australia, on the other hand, is structured similarly to Europe, having one national standardisation organisation. Both countries are full members of the IEC. IEEE 2030.5 is of special interest in both countries, USA and Australia.

As described in D1.1 in detail, the comparison to the IEC standards 61850 and 61968 shows overlap, and advantages for InterSTORE using IEEE 2030.5 are listed.

6 Conclusion

Since its inception, the InterSTORE project has demonstrated a **strong and consistent commitment to ensuring the long-term exploitation and uptake** of its interoperable open-source tools by engaging early and continuously with leading stakeholders in the energy and interoperability domains. From the outset, the project established **close collaboration with the LFE [100], aligning its objectives with LFE's mission to promote open-source solutions for the energy transition**. This collaboration has recently culminated in **InterSTORE's inclusion in the LFE portfolio of projects [101]**, confirming its strategic relevance and sustainability beyond the project's lifetime. The consortium's active participation in the LFE Summit Europe 2025 and the dedicated InterSTORE pitch session further strengthened its visibility and network within the open-source energy community.

In parallel, InterSTORE has also **proactively engaged a broad and diverse stakeholder group**, bringing together representatives from industry, research, academia, and standardisation bodies, to act as first adopters and multipliers of its interoperability tools. Several **dedicated stakeholder meetings were organised throughout the project** to present, validate, and refine its main developments, as documented in the project's open dissemination channels. These interactions have ensured that **InterSTORE tools respond to real-world needs and are well positioned for market uptake**.

This deliverable is complementary to all these efforts to secure a successful exploitation, by presenting an integrated analysis of the project's KERs, combining the findings of the two targeted surveys conducted among KER owners and UC leaders. This analysis confirms the technical robustness and market relevance of all four InterSTORE tools:

- **KER1 (Interoperable Client/Server Library)** enabling scalable IEEE 2030.5 communication across devices and EMS;
- **KER2 (Legacy Protocol Converter)** bridging legacy assets and new interoperability standards;
- **KER3 (Testing Protocol Software Tool)** ensuring quality assurance, certification readiness, and faster market adoption;
- **KER4 (Data Space Connector)** establishing trusted, governed data exchange for new data-driven services.

Results from the business model and business plan chapter show that **InterSTORE solutions generate clear economic value by lowering integration costs, enabling new service revenues, and improving the ROI for hybrid and distributed energy systems**. The TLBMC applied across UCs demonstrates complementary economic, social, and environmental benefits - ranging from enhanced interoperability and system resilience to increased user acceptance and reduced lifecycle emissions.

The IPR and ownership review further confirms a **sound governance framework ensuring open-source continuity while safeguarding the freedom to operate for all contributors**. KERs are released under permissive licences (e.g., MIT), facilitating future exploitation both within and beyond the consortium.

Moreover, **InterSTORE has strategically aligned its results with major international standards, particularly the IEEE 2030.5 Standard**, which defines interoperability requirements for distributed energy resources. Project partners have actively contributed to the dissemination

and promotion of InterSTORE tools that integrate and are compatible with IEEE 2030.5 through **participation in high-level IEEE events and conferences**, including **ICSmartGrid 2024**, **IEEE PowerTech 2025**, and **ICSmartGrid 2025**, as well as through the publication of the **white paper “The Role of IEEE 2030.5 Interoperability Standard in Distributed Energy Resources Integration.”** [102] These actions not only validate the project’s technical soundness, but also position its outcomes within the global framework of recognised interoperability practices.

Strong connections have also been established with the SunSpec Alliance [83], another major organisation supporting open data standards and certification for distributed energy systems. This collaboration, together with the project’s ongoing involvement in LFE, provides a solid foundation for exploitation and future scaling. Importantly, **in February 2026**, following the end of the funded period, InterSTORE - under its new open-source identity CUPID, hosted by LFE - **will take part in a joint webinar with IEEE and SunSpec Alliance**. This initiative will give the project access to an extensive international audience and community of potential adopters, further expanding its reach and impact.

Overall, the synthesis of economic, social, and environmental findings across chapters clearly demonstrates that InterSTORE has evolved from a research-driven initiative into a sustainable, open-source ecosystem supported by recognised standards, active stakeholder engagement, and well-defined exploitation pathways. Its results - spanning interoperability, protocol translation, testing, and secure data exchange - could be considered as a toolbox that might contribute significantly to build more digitalised, decentralised and decarbonised energy systems.

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8 Annexes

8.1 Annex – KERs Owners Survey

Overall InterSTORE Stakeholder Groups

First, **exploitation stakeholders** of InterSTORE project as a whole need to be classified. Below InterSTORE stakeholder groups are reported. **Please fill the table with the following information:**

1. Choose whether the stakeholders are primary or secondary:
 - **Primary:** direct interest in a project and its dealings; direct impact due to the project's performance and able to impact the project performance as well.
 - **Secondary:** non direct interest in a project, but reasonable influence over a project dealing; the project does not depend directly upon them for survival of its immediate interests.
2. Choose the positioning of each stakeholder within the "Power-Interest Grid":
 - **Keep into account;**
 - **Keep informed;**
 - **Meet their needs;**
 - **Manage closely.**
3. What is important to the stakeholder?
 - **What matters the most for the specific stakeholder in relation to InterSTORE KERs.**
4. Strategy for engaging the stakeholder:
 - **How to facilitate the stakeholders' knowledge and uptake of InterSTORE KERs.**

Stakeholder groups	Pri- mary/Sec- ondary	Power-Interest Grid	What is important to the stake- holder?	Strategy for en- gaging the stake- holder
Industry Users: Organisations, SME, inverters' manufacturers, BESS manufac- turers, Heat pump providers, etc.	Choose an item.	Choose an item.		
End Users: en- ergy communi- ties' members, EV & Fleet owners, office's	Choose an item.	Choose an item.		

and campus employees, etc.				
<u>TSO: Transmission System Operator (primary-secondary-tertiary reserve, RES integration, re-dispatch)</u>	Choose an item.	Choose an item.		
<u>DSO: Distribution System Operator (voltage level regulation, power quality, reactive power, integration of RES)</u>	Choose an item.	Choose an item.		
<u>Flexibility Service Provider: offering energy assets batteries, virtual power plant, energy transition service, ESCO, etc.</u>	Choose an item.	Choose an item.		
<u>Regulatory Bodies and Standardisation: BRIDGE, 2ZeRo, InterConnect, Enershare, etc.</u>	Choose an item.	Choose an item.		
<u>Academia & Research Institutions</u>	Choose an item.	Choose an item.		

Exploitation Framework

This subsection provides an overview of the exploitation-related concepts that are useful to gain a further understanding of the activities that will be carried out for this purpose. The exploitation overview intends to identify the partner's expectations and claims of the results and to characterise them in order to define the most suitable exploitation pathway.

Characterisation of results

Identification of the problem/need

The nature of the problem that the result is trying to address, and where it comes from, will be described through the following categories:

- **Technical:** Need for higher performance, higher durability, different standards and features, etc.
- **Financial:** Need for lower CAPEX or OPEX, higher revenues, safer value chains, faster ROI, etc.
- **Environmental:** Need to reduce GHG emission, reduce pollutants, reduce impact on nature, etc.
- **Social:** Need to reduce impact on society, safer value chains, better work conditions, etc.

Actors involved

The considered segments of society manifesting the need are the following:

- **Private entities:** Private companies, high education institutions, non-governmental institutions.
- **Public entities:** Governmental bodies, research centres, high education institutions.
- **Industry:** Group of companies that develop similar activities and make up a sector of the economy, i.e., energy, construction, chemical, transport and mobility, etc.

Type of project result

Project's results could be either new or building upon former technologies/methods/products, etc. In either case, the outputs of the project may be classified using the following concepts:

- **Methodology/Method:** A method is a systematic sequence of steps aimed at solving a problem or executing an action. A methodology is the use of a method or methods in a particular field of study.
- **Process:** A group of methods used in the development stage of a product/service.
- **Product:** Tangible good derived from the combination of processes and methods intended to cover a need and with the potential to be commercialised.
- **Service:** Activities that benefit a group of people in a market, without providing tangible assets.
- **Algorithms:** A sequence of instructions or rules put together to produce a service or enable a computation action.
- **Software:** Operating system used by a digital equipment or program.
- **Website:** Virtual platform, containing a set of interconnected web pages, created to share information online.
- **Scientific articles:** Written publications containing research findings or theories supported by data and explained through a methodology.
- **Product design:** The process of creating a product that addresses a specific need in a given market. It involves research and development actions.
- **Name of a product/service:** A new name that identifies a new or existing product or service.
- **Expertise:** Skill or knowledge on a specific subject.
- **Data base:** Organised collection of data/information.

Exploitation level

The exploitation level of the project's results will be explained through the following definitions:

- **Not exploitable:** It is not possible to exploit the results by the end of the project.
- **Weakly exploitable:** It is unlikely that the results will be exploitable by the end of the project.

- Moderately exploitable: There is an exploitation potential that will be furthered explored.
- Highly exploitable: There is a concrete possibility that these results can be exploited.

Development phase

The development stage of the results of the project will be classified using the following categories:

- Under development: The result has a low level of development or is being developed by the project and requires further resources to become exploitable.
- Developed not exploited: The result has been developed but requires further research or resources to become exploitable.
- Being exploited: The result is fully developed and being exploited.

Time to exploitability

Based on their features, different results can be exploited with different timings:

- More than 5 years;
- Between 3 and 5 years;
- Between 1 and 2 years;
- Less than 1 year;
- Immediately at the end of the project.

Exploitation route

The exploitation route of the results will be defined through the following areas:

- Scientific/Academic/Technological: Research; Thesis; Journal article; Knowledge transfer; development and creation of new technology, design or manufacturing process.
- Societal: Social activity; Policy/regulation.
- Economic: Spin-off; Start-up, marketable product or service; Patent.

Geographical scale

The following geographical levels may be useful to identify the scalability of the project's results:

- Local: The exploitation of the result is only possible and significant in the area where it was developed or deployed. There are existing barriers for further exploitation beyond the local site.
- National: The exploitation is only significant at a national level. There are existing barriers for further exploitation.
- Global: The exploitation of the result is possible and significant at an international level.

Link to other KERs

KER owners will identify whether and how their results depend on other KERs to progress.

Technology Readiness Level (This could also be SRL, MRL...)

The project characterisation should also indicate the expected TRL advancement that the result should reach by the end of the project.

- TRL start: The TRL of the KER at the beginning of the project.
- TRL end: The TRL of the KER by the end of the project.

Please fill the characterisation table below, including all relevant information for the KER that you own. **Please always provide a justification/explanation to each of your choices in the justification section.**

Intellectual Property Rights (IPR)

Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) refer to legal protections granted to the creators and owners of intellectual assets. These rights enable individuals and organisations to control and benefit from their innovations by preventing unauthorised use or reproduction. IPR encompasses patents, copyrights, trademarks, trade secrets, and design rights, among others. In the context of Horizon Europe projects, effective IPR management ensures that research outputs are protected, appropriately shared among partners, and successfully exploited by other stakeholders for societal and commercial benefits.

Please fill the table below providing as many details as possible on background and foreground IPR, as well as future IPR strategies related to your KER.

Intellectual Property Identification		
Does the KER involve new knowledge, processes, technologies, or products?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	
What type of intellectual property is associated with the KER?	Choose an item.	
Has any background intellectual property been used in developing this KER?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	If yes, provide details:
Ownership and Rights Allocation		
Who are the main owners of the IPR related to this KER?		
Have ownership agreements been formalised?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	
Are there joint ownership agreements in place?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	If yes, specify the co-owners:
What are the agreed terms for access and use of this intellectual property among partners?		
Protection Strategy		
Have any IPR protection measures been taken?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	If yes, specify (e.g., patent filed, trademark registered, copyright secured, confidentiality agreements signed):
If applicable, provide details on patent applications (e.g., patent number, filing date, jurisdiction)		
If IPR protection has not been pursued, provide reasons (e.g., cost, lack of novelty, preference for open access)		
Next Steps and Support Needed		

What additional support is required for IPR management (e.g., legal advice, patent attorney, licensing consultant)?	
What are the next steps for securing or managing IPR related to this KER?	
Do you require assistance from the European Commission's Horizon IP Scan or other IPR support services?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No

Exploitation Route Towards Impact

The aim of this subsection is to identify the expected impact(s) your result will contribute to and assign a level of contribution. **Add a description on how the result is expected to contribute to these impacts 5 years after the end of the project.**

KER#		
Call's expected impact	Level of contribution	How the result will contribute to the expected impact (5 years after the end of project)?
1. Industrial leadership in key and emerging technologies that work for people	Choose an item.	
2. Affordable and clean energy	Choose an item.	
3. More efficient, clean, sustainable, secure and competitive energy supply through new solutions for smart grids and energy systems based on more performant renewable energy solutions	Choose an item.	

Actions to be taken beyond the project end

This section aims to be a tool designed to help you identify and plan all the activities to be performed after the end of the project, in order to make your KER ready to be shared with the European Community.

Actions: All the different actions necessary to create a solid end users/beneficiaries/community approach, including Immediate actions, Consolidation and Engagement activities, Expansion and Optimisation actions, Monitoring and Adjustment actions. In most cases, it is reasonable that you have already in place most of the services, agreements, competences here listed. In this case, it is suggested to check those boxes that will require some investment for further customisation against the KER.

Financial Costs: Here it is possible to insert a rough estimation of the cost of the checked activities. Please consider that these costs will not be covered by the project (as they start after its end) and they will contribute to the calculation of the revenues and return on the investment.

Other sources of coverage: The funds that you may ask to cover expenses after the end of the project.

The survey is structured as a checklist, to facilitate the user filling it. All the suggestions are “universal”, i.e. applicable to different KERs and situations. It is highly recommended to customise them for your own results. Therefore, when choosing “other”, please also provide an explanation.

Exploitation Roadmap: KER N#	
Owner:	
Actions	<p><i>Briefly describe actions planned to be executed within 3-5 years after the end of the project (select the relevant ones).</i></p> <p>Immediate Actions (these actions will provide a more comprehensive approach to immediate action, ensuring effective communication, training, and measurement of the KER in the early stages of implementation):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="checkbox"/> Creating frameworks, guidelines, and tools based on research findings to facilitate the implementation and adoption of the new KER. <input type="checkbox"/> Initiate internal training programs to ensure understanding and adoption. <input type="checkbox"/> Identify key success metrics and establish baseline measurements. <input type="checkbox"/> Develop a communication strategy outlining key messages, target audiences, and channels for dissemination. <input type="checkbox"/> Create informational materials such as brochures, presentations, or videos to support communication efforts. <input type="checkbox"/> Schedule kick-off meetings to officially announce the new KER and set expectations. <input type="checkbox"/> Provide resources and support materials to facilitate learning and implementation of new practices. <input type="checkbox"/> Establish feedback mechanisms for employees to ask questions, share concerns, and provide input on the KER. <input type="checkbox"/> Collaborate with internal and external stakeholders, to integrate the new KER into existing training programs or initiatives. <input type="checkbox"/> Set up tracking systems or tools to monitor progress towards achieving key success metrics. <input type="checkbox"/> Define clear objectives and targets for each key success metric to guide future actions and decision-making. <input type="checkbox"/> Other:

	<p><u>Consolidation and Engagement actions</u> (these activities will help consolidate the gains made from the initial implementation and further engage stakeholders in the ongoing success of the new KER):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="checkbox"/> Conduct feedback sessions and focus groups to gather insights from stakeholders across different levels and departments. <input type="checkbox"/> Organise workshops or brainstorming sessions to encourage collaboration and idea generation for further improvement. <input type="checkbox"/> Establish cross-functional teams or task forces to address specific challenges or opportunities identified during feedback sessions. <input type="checkbox"/> Analyse feedback and insights gathered to identify common themes, areas of strength, and areas for improvement. <input type="checkbox"/> Develop action plans based on feedback findings to address identified issues and capitalise on opportunities. <input type="checkbox"/> Showcase success stories or case studies highlighting tangible outcomes and benefits achieved through the implementation of the new KER. <input type="checkbox"/> Create multimedia materials such as videos, infographics, or presentations to visually communicate success stories and outcomes to a wider audience. <input type="checkbox"/> Share success stories internally through company newsletters, intranet portals, or internal social media platforms to inspire and motivate employees. <input type="checkbox"/> Leverage success stories externally through press releases, industry publications, or social media channels to enhance the organization's reputation and credibility. <input type="checkbox"/> Invite stakeholders to participate in events or webinars where success stories are shared and discussed, providing opportunities for learning and networking. <input type="checkbox"/> Other: <p><u>Expansion and Optimisation actions</u> (these activities will help optimise the implementation of the new KER and leverage external resources and expertise to maximise their impact and reach):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="checkbox"/> Scale up implementation efforts across relevant departments or teams by developing a roadmap for broader adoption and expansion. <input type="checkbox"/> Identify additional areas or business units where the new KER can be applied and develop implementation plans tailored to each context. <input type="checkbox"/> Conduct pilot programs or phased rollouts in new areas to test scalability and effectiveness before full-scale implementation.
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	<p><input type="checkbox"/> Allocate resources and support to ensure successful implementation in new areas, including funding, personnel, and technology.</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Establish clear communication channels and support mechanisms to address challenges and facilitate smooth implementation across multiple departments or teams.</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Analyse performance data and metrics to identify bottlenecks, inefficiencies, or areas for improvement in the implementation process.</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Implement iterative improvements and adjustments to optimise processes and enhance outcomes.</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Develop standardised procedures and best practices based on successful implementation experiences to ensure consistency and quality across different areas or teams.</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Provide ongoing training and support to employees to build capacity and confidence in implementing the new KER effectively.</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Explore opportunities for external collaboration or partnerships with other organisations, industry associations, or research institutions.</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Identify potential collaborators or partners with complementary expertise, resources, or networks to enhance the impact and reach of the new KER.</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Initiate discussions or negotiations with potential collaborators to establish mutually beneficial partnerships or joint initiatives.</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Develop partnership agreements outlining roles, responsibilities, and expectations for collaboration, including resource sharing, knowledge exchange, and joint decision-making.</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Monitor and evaluate the effectiveness of external collaborations or partnerships, and make adjustments as needed to ensure alignment with organizational goals and objectives.</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Other:</p> <p>Monitoring and Adjustment actions (these activities will help ensure that the organisation effectively monitors performance, identifies areas for improvement, and makes timely adjustments to optimise outcomes and achieve strategic objectives):</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Continuously monitor key performance indicators (KPIs) using real-time data analytics tools and dashboards to track the effectiveness and impact of the implemented initiatives.</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Set up automated alerts or triggers to notify relevant stakeholders of any significant deviations from expected performance targets or thresholds.</p>
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	<p><input type="checkbox"/> Conduct in-depth analyses of performance data to identify trends, patterns, and correlations that may inform strategic decisions and adjustments.</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Regularly review and analyse qualitative feedback from stakeholders, including employees, customers, and partners, to complement quantitative performance metrics.</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Benchmark performance against industry standards, best practices, or competitors to gain insights into relative performance and identify areas for improvement.</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Conduct root cause analyses to investigate underlying factors contributing to performance discrepancies or challenges and develop targeted action plans to address them.</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Establish cross-functional teams or task forces dedicated to monitoring and optimising specific aspects of performance, such as efficiency, quality, or customer satisfaction.</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Implement regular performance reviews and assessments at predetermined intervals, such as quarterly or semi-annually, to evaluate progress against strategic goals and objectives.</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Solicit input and feedback from stakeholders during performance reviews to gain diverse perspectives and identify blind spots or overlooked opportunities.</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Communicate performance new KER trends, and insights to stakeholders through periodic updates, progress reports, and presentations.</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Provide opportunities for stakeholders to ask questions, share concerns, and provide input during performance review meetings to foster transparency and accountability.</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Document lessons learned, best practices, and recommendations from performance reviews to inform future planning and decision-making processes.</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Other:</p>
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Financials
Costs

Please provide an estimation of the costs for each activity towards TRL 9, by specifying the sub-activity from the previous checked lists:

Activity	Sub-activity	Cost estimation range (€)
IP and legal activities		
Immediate Actions		
Consolidation and Engagement Actions		

	Expansion and Optimisation Actions			
	Monitoring and Adjustment Actions			
	Total			
Other sources of coverage	<i>Possible alternative sources for covering the previously introduced costs:</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="checkbox"/> Local/national public funds (please provide details): <input type="checkbox"/> Private investments: <input type="checkbox"/> Banks <input type="checkbox"/> Financial funds <input type="checkbox"/> Business angels <input type="checkbox"/> Private industry <input type="checkbox"/> Other private investors (please specify) <input type="checkbox"/> Own investments 			

8.2 Annex – UCs Owners Survey

Relevance and Applicability

KER	How relevant is this KER to your specific UC?	How was the KER applied or tested within your UC?	What specific problems does this KER address in your operational context?	Additional comments
KER1: Interoperable client/server library	Choose an item.			
KER2: Legacy system protocol converter	Choose an item.			
KER3: Testing procedure and software tool	Choose an item.			
KER4: InterSTORE Data Space Connector	Choose an item.			

Performance and Effectiveness

KER	How would you rate the performance of the KER in achieving the desired outcomes of your UC?	How could this KER benefit your organisation? (Select all that apply and feel free to elaborate below)	Did the KER meet your expectations in terms of performance? Why or why not?	Additional comments
KER1: Interoperable client/server library	Choose an item.	Choose an item. If other, please specify:	Choose an item. Justification:	
KER2: Legacy system protocol converter	Choose an item.	Choose an item. If other, please specify:	Choose an item. Justification:	
KER3: Testing procedure and software tool	Choose an item.	Choose an item. If other, please specify:	Choose an item. Justification:	
KER4: InterSTORE Data Space Connector	Choose an item.	Choose an item. If other, please specify:	Choose an item. Justification:	

Integration and Compatibility

KER	How easily was the KER integrated into existing systems or processes?	Were there any compatibility issues encountered? If so, how were they addressed?	Does the KER require significant modifications to be fully operational in your environment? If so, which ones?	Additional comments
KER1: Interoperable client/server library	Choose an item.			
KER2: Legacy system protocol converter	Choose an item.			
KER3: Testing procedure and software tool	Choose an item.			
KER4: InterSTORE Data Space Connector	Choose an item.			

Market Potential and Demand

KER	Based on your experience, what is the potential demand for this KER in the market?	Which are the customer segments/industries that would benefit most from this KER?	What are the main barriers to market entry or adoption for this KER?	Additional comments
KER1: Interoperable client/server library	Choose an item.		Choose an item. Other:	
KER2: Legacy system protocol converter	Choose an item.		Choose an item. Other:	
KER3: Testing procedure and software tool	Choose an item.		Choose an item. Other:	
KER4: InterSTORE Data Space Connector	Choose an item.		Choose an item. Other:	

Recommendations for Improvement

KER	What aspects of the KER could be enhanced to increase its exploitation potential?	Are there additional features or functionalities that should be considered?	How can the KER be better tailored to meet industry needs or standards?	Additional comments
KER1: Interoperable client/server library				
KER2: Legacy system protocol converter				
KER3: Testing procedure and software tool				
KER4: InterSTORE Data Space Connector				

Comparative Assessment

Among the four KERs, which do you believe has the highest potential for successful exploitation? Please rank them from highest to lowest potential and explain your reasoning.	Justification	Which KERs require the most development before they can be commercially or practically exploited? Please rank accordingly.	Justification
1. Choose an item.		1. Choose an item.	
2. Choose an item.		2. Choose an item.	
3. Choose an item.		3. Choose an item.	
4. Choose an item.		4. Choose an item.	

8.3 Annex – Extensive UCs Feedback on KERs Performance

Feedback on performance from UCs: KER1

UC1: DES Flexibility Market Monetisation & UC2: Energy community DES utilisation

Relevance and Applicability: The interoperable client/server library is highly relevant for UC1 and UC2 and it has been implemented in CYG (CYG) Flexibility Management Platform, which can then natively speak IEEE2030.5. In both UCs’ operational context, KER1 enables bridging differences in communication by enlarging the portfolio of available options for CyberNoc. Additionally, the new approach enables various new communication scenarios.

Performance and Effectiveness: UC1 and UC2 owner considers KER1 performance in achieving the desired outcomes of the UCs as excellent. The use of the client/server library can benefit CYG in the following ways:

- Improve operational efficiency;
- Enhance existing product/services;
- Enable new product/services or business models;
- Strengthen competitive advantage;
- Improve data management or interoperability.

KER1 successfully met the expectations defined for UC1 and UC2. While some challenges arose during its implementation and integration with CYG’s internal infrastructure, these were resolved, after which communication over the system proceeded smoothly.

Integration and Compatibility: KER1 integration was moderately easy, with some modification and effort required during integration, as mentioned above. The few compatibility issues encountered were addressed by deep diving into library specification and extensive mapping specifications. This KER does not require significant modifications to be fully operational in UC1 and UC2.

Market Potential and Demand: Based on KER1 performance in UC1 and UC2 and CYG's experience, the market demand for the client/server library is moderate – interest exists, but adoption might be limited by some barriers. The customer segments/industries that would benefit the most from KER1 are aggregators, EMS operators and standardisation bodies. At the current stage of development, the main barriers to market entry or adoption are market readiness (low awareness or demand from potential customers) and strong competition. For the latter, according to CYG, the rate between the benefit the novelty brings and time & money needed for the integration is significantly low.

Recommendations for Improvement: To increase the exploitation potential of KER1, CYG recommends to create an automatic instalment app, which connects directly to the users' system. Additional features or functionalities to be considered include security measures, with particular attention to the use of open NATS. It is essential to assess its potential vulnerabilities, including the risk of unauthorised access to the EMS and the possibility of disrupting or tampering with the messaging transmitted through it. To ensure that KER1 is better aligned with industry needs and standards, it should aim for excellence in a specific aspect, whether it be simplicity of implementation, security of communication, or market-leading interoperability.

Comparative Assessment: When compared to the other KERs stemming from InterSTORE activities, KER1 has the highest potential of being successfully exploited, based on its performance in UC1 and UC2. This is justified by the fact that it is the most interoperable solution on the market, hence it has the biggest success chance. When ranking the KERs based on the scale of their development needs (from highest to lowest), before they can be commercially or practically exploited, KER1 is positioned in the second place. The main development needed is the simplification of implementation guidelines.

UC3: Grid supporting BESS & UC8: Multiphysics flexibility optimisation for Home Management Systems and their global integration

Relevance and Applicability: The interoperable client/server library is not relevant for UC3 and UC8. It is not applicable because the client/server library cannot be installed directly on assets. However, FZJ participated in the discussion for its development.

Performance and Effectiveness; Integration and Compatibility: Since KER1 was not tested in UC3 and UC8, there is no feedback on these two aspects.

Market Potential and Demand: Market demand for KER1 is expected to be high, but some market development actions may be needed. According to FZJ, the main customer segments should be inverter and EMS manufacturers as well as operators of already existing systems, while EAT identified utilities and aggregators as the key target groups. The main barriers to market entry or adoption might be regulatory or policy constraints (compliance with industry standards, legal requirements, or lack of supportive policies) and the competitive landscape (presence of alternative solutions limiting market entry).

Recommendations for Improvement: Since KER1 was not tested in UC3, no feedback was collected. Based on UC8 experience, EAT suggested that a dockerised form would facilitate

integration and that the current documentation should cover more examples to support developers.

Comparative Assessment: When compared to the other KERs stemming from InterSTORE activities, KER1 has been positioned differently by the two UC owners. According to FZJ (UC3), KER1 has the second lowest potential of being successfully exploited, while EAT (UC8) considered KER1 to have the second highest potential. In EAT's assessment, when ranking KERs based on the scale of their development needs, KER1 is positioned in the first place in UC8 and ranked second in UC3. This is conditioned by the fact that the KER has not been implemented in this context.

UC4: Innovative Frequency services & UC7: Adaptive BESS management for autonomous grid operation

Relevance and Applicability: The interoperable client/server library is highly/moderately relevant for UC4 and UC7. It has been used to test and validate high-power fast frequency services, such as virtual inertia, fast peak shaving, and (in UC7) voltage dip tests. It enabled reliable data exchange between components, allowing performance comparison with traditional Controller Area Network (CAN)-based communication, and showed acceptable results. In the operational context of both UCs, KER1 supported in addressing the challenge of system compatibility between different software components and devices.

Performance and Effectiveness: UCs owner considers KER1 performance in achieving the desired outcomes as good in UC4 and as excellent in UC7. In both cases, the use of the client/server library can benefit HES when enhancing existing products/services. KER1 successfully met the expectations defined for both UC4 and UC7, supporting especially fast high-power services that are important for system operators.

Integration and Compatibility: KER1 integration was moderately easy, with some modification and effort required during integration. This KER does not require significant modifications to be fully operational in UC4 and UC7.

Market Potential and Demand: Based on KER1 performance and HES's experience in both UCs, the market demand for the client/server library is considered high, but some market development actions may be needed. The customer segments/industries that would benefit the most are system operators in the European Union (EU) and beyond. At the current stage of development, the main barrier to market entry or adoption might be the competitive landscape, due to the strong presence of alternative solutions limiting market entry.

Recommendations for Improvement: No additional recommendations for improvement were put forward by HES, based on UC4 and UC7 experience.

Comparative Assessment: When compared to the other KERs stemming from InterSTORE activities, KER1 has the highest potential of being successfully exploited, based on its performance in UC4 and UC7. When ranking the KERs based on the scale of their development needs (from highest to lowest), KER1 is positioned in the third place for UC4 and in the first place for UC7.

UC5: Hybrid floating storage flexibility monitoring & UC6: Management of battery systems for Node capacity increase in REC

Relevance and Applicability: The interoperable client/server library is not relevant for UC5 and UC6, hence, it has not been used.

Performance and Effectiveness; Integration and Compatibility: Since KER1 was not tested in UC5 and UC6, there is no feedback on these two aspects.

Market Potential and Demand: CAP expects market demand for KER1 to be high, but some market development actions may be needed. The main customer segments identified are aggregators, DSO, TSO, charging point operators, and REC managing entities. The main barrier might be the competitive landscape, with strong presence of alternative solutions potentially limiting market entry. In contrast, for UC6, market demand for KER1 is expected to be moderate – interest exists but adoption may be limited by certain barriers. The main customer segments should be DSO and TSO, with the main barrier being lack of stakeholder confidence and hesitancy from key industry players or end-users.

Recommendations for Improvement: In UC5, to increase the exploitation potential of KER1, CAP recommends simplifying the access to IEEE 2030.5 client and server to implement the library. Additional features or functionalities to be considered include embedding IEEE 2030.5 client and server in the documentation. KER1 is considered well aligned with industry needs and standards. For UC6, no specific recommendations were provided. The solution is nevertheless considered well aligned with industry needs and standards and ready for use.

Comparative Assessment: When compared to the other KERs stemming from InterSTORE activities, CAP sees KER1 as having the third highest potential of being successfully exploited in UC5, while in UC6 it has the highest potential, since it enables the NATS communication, which is faster and unleashes fast service provision. When ranking the KERs based on the scale of their development needs (from highest to lowest), KER1 is positioned in the second place according to UC5 and in the third place according to UC6. However, both rankings are conditioned by the fact that the interoperable client/server library has not been used in these UCs.

UC9: Management of EV charging clusters as HESS

Relevance and Applicability: The interoperable client/server library is not relevant for UC9 and, hence, it has not been used.

Performance and Effectiveness; Integration and Compatibility: Since KER1 was not tested in UC9, there is no feedback on these two aspects.

Market Potential and Demand: ENX expects market demand for KER1 to be low – limited demand with significant challenges for market adoption. The main customer segments should be B2B. The main barrier to market entry or adoption might be the market readiness, with low awareness or demand from potential customers.

Recommendations for Improvement: To improve the exploitation potential of KER1, documentation should cover more scenarios. No specific feedback on additional features or functionalities, as well as alignment with industry needs and standards has been provided.

Comparative Assessment: When compared to the other KERs stemming from InterSTORE activities, KER1 has the least potential of being successfully exploited. When ranking the KERs based on the scale of their development needs (from highest to lowest), before they can be commercially or practically exploited, KER1 is positioned in the first place and to overcome this, it is critical to better tailor it to a target/segment of customers.

Feedback on performance from UCs: KER2

UC1: DES Flexibility Market Monetisation & UC2: Energy community DES utilisation

Relevance and Applicability: The LPC is highly relevant for UC1 and UC2 and it has been installed in a separate hardware (HW) and placed next to each household in the pilot to translate from the original platform to IEEE 2030.5. In both UCs' operational context, KER2 enables connection to assets that natively do not support IEEE 2030.5

Performance and Effectiveness: UC1 and UC2 owner considers KER2 performance in achieving the desired outcomes of the UCs as fair. The use of the LPC can benefit CYG in the following ways:

- Reduce cost or resource consumption;
- Enable new product/services or business models;
- Strengthen competitive advantage;
- Improve data management or interoperability;

KER2 overall met the expectations defined for UC1 and UC2. However, even if the translation works, it is not always straightforward, since the devices - from which the signals originate - have various types and versions of the same protocol. Hence, the LPC needed to be additionally adapted to the needs of each particular group.

Integration and Compatibility: KER2 integration proved to be difficult, since significant challenges were met and system changes were necessary. The compatibility issues encountered were addressed by checking each UC separately, testing the communication and identifying custom solutions. To be fully operational in UC1 and UC2, higher understandability is needed, since at current stage it depends on the device to which UCs are connecting.

Market Potential and Demand: Based on KER2 performance in UC1 and UC2 and CYG's experience, the market demand for the LPC is very high - strong market interest with clear demand and adaptation potential. The customer segments/industries that would benefit the most from KER2 are installers and engineers. At the current stage of development, the main barriers to market entry or adoption are technical challenges such as integration difficulties, scalability issues, or need for further development. Furthermore, according to CYG, the rate between the benefit the novelty brings and time & money needed for the integration is significantly low.

Recommendations for Improvement: To increase the exploitation potential of KER2, CYG recommends creating LPC versions for specific device and/or protocol, which then prove to be a real plug & play. Additional features or functionalities to be considered include security measures aimed at testing the LPC and verifying where the breach could happen. To ensure that KER2 is better aligned with industry needs and standards, it should aim for excellence in a specific aspect, whether it be simplicity of implementation, security of communication, or market-leading interoperability.

Comparative Assessment: When compared to the other KERs stemming from InterSTORE activities, KER2 has the second highest potential of being successfully exploited, based on its performance in UC1 and UC2. This is justified by the fact that it supports KER1 and it is definitely something that all installers need. When ranking the KERs based on the scale of their development needs (from highest to lowest), before they can be commercially or practically exploited, KER2 is positioned in the fourth place as it is already ready for use. Nevertheless, the services coverage of the LPC is still very limited.

UC3: Grid supporting BESS & UC8: Multiphysics flexibility optimisation for Home Management Systems and their global integration

Relevance and Applicability: The LPC is highly relevant for both UC3 and UC8. In UC8, EATON used it to transform protocols Modbus/MQTT to NATS in IEEE 2030.5 format. In UC3, FZJ deployed the LPC on a RaspberryPi (low-cost single board computer) to interface the inverter-driven assets and the Information and Communication Technology (ICT) platform with the energy management algorithm. Since DERs in the multiphysics storage system are supporting distinct communication protocols, the LPC enabled unified communication in UC8 operational context. In UC3, the LPC gave FZJ the possibility to easily integrate any Modbus-speaking asset with their MQTT-based ICT platform using a generic tool.

Performance and Effectiveness: The performance of KER2 was good in UC8 and excellent in UC3. The use of the LPC can benefit FZJ and EATON in the following ways:

- Improve operational efficiency;
- Reduce cost or resource consumption;
- Enhance existing product/services;
- Enable new product/services or business models;
- Strengthen competitive advantage;
- Improve data management or interoperability;
- Facilitate entry into new markets.

Overall, based on its use in UC8, the LPC performed as expected, enabling the creation of IEEE 2030.5 messages easily and running seamlessly during the operations. In UC3 the tool proved to work as expected when it comes to the communication between inverters and ICT platform.

Integration and Compatibility: KER2 integration proved to be easy in UC8 – only minor adjustment were needed, but overall integration was smooth. In UC3 the integration difficulties were moderate - some modification and effort were required during the integration. Indeed, the initial version of the tool did not work as expected when it comes to the Modbus communication, but coordination with SUN helped in solving the issue. The compatibility issues encountered were addressed by SUN by implementing a second library (Python-based) to make sure that Modbus communication works properly on all the assets.

Market Potential and Demand: According to UC8 and UC3 perspective, market demand for KER2 is expected to be moderate to high, with some barriers tackling and market development actions needed. According to FZJ and EATON, the main customer segments should be utilities, inverter and EMS manufacturers as well as operators of already existing systems. The main barriers to market entry or adoption might be regulatory or policy constraints (compliance with industry standards, legal requirements, or lack of supportive policies) and the competitive landscape (presence of alternative solutions limiting market entry).

Recommendations for Improvement: To further improve the LPC, EATON recommends to refine the graphical user interface to help users define mappings.

Comparative Assessment: When compared to the other KERs stemming from InterSTORE activities, KER2 has been positioned differently by the two UC owners. According to FZJ (UC3), KER2 has the highest potential of being successfully exploited. The possibility to use the LPC also with already existing HW, without acting on the firmware is more relevant, and less challenging than acting on the firmware. Then, once the devices are connected and data is collected, safe and reliable data sharing is also important. EATON (UC8) considered KER2 to have the third highest potential. When ranking KERs based on the scale of their development needs, KER2 is positioned in the third place for both UCs owners.

UC4: Innovative Frequency Services & UC7: Adaptive BESS Management for Autonomous Grid Operation

Relevance and Applicability: The LPC is highly relevant for UC4 and UC7. In both UCs, it was applied to interface legacy systems for delivering fast frequency support. The LPC enabled the integration of existing equipment with modern control and monitoring setups, allowing successful execution of services like virtual inertia with high compatibility performance comparison with traditional CAN-based communication, and showed acceptable results. In the operational context of UC4 and UC7, since the focus of these UCs was fast service, the main need to be addressed was the speed of the system after the implementation. After the final test, the LPC showed the capability and usefulness for fast high-power services as well.

Performance and Effectiveness: In both UC4 and UC7, the owner considers KER2 performance in achieving the desired outcomes as good. In both cases, the use of the LPC can benefit HES when enhancing existing products/services. KER2 successfully met the expectations defined for both UC4 and UC7. In UC4, it can support high power fast services. In UC7, it also supports a wide range of services, especially for fast high-power services such as virtual inertia and voltage dip test, which are important for system operators.

Integration and Compatibility: KER2 integration was moderately easy, with some modification and effort required during integration. Any compatibility issues have been solved through the support of InterSTORE project partners. To be fully operational in UC4 and UC7, the LPC does not require any major modification.

Market Potential and Demand: Based on KER2 performance and HES's experience in both UCs, the market demand for the LPC is considered high, but some market development actions may be needed. The customer segments/industries that would benefit the most are system operators in the EU and beyond. At the current stage of development, the main barrier to market entry or adoption might be technical challenges, such as integration difficulties, scalability issues, or need for further development.

Recommendations for Improvement: No additional recommendations for improvement were put forward by HES, based on UC4 experience and UC7.

Comparative Assessment: When compared to the other KERs stemming from InterSTORE activities, KER2 has the second highest potential of being successfully exploited, based on its performance in UC4 and UC7. When ranking the KERs based on the scale of their development needs (from highest to lowest), KER2 is positioned in the first place for UC4 and in the second place for UC7.

UC5: Hybrid Floating Storage Flexibility Monitoring & UC6: Management of Battery Systems for Node Capacity Increase in REC

Relevance and Applicability: The LPC is not relevant for UC5 and UC6. It has been only redundantly used in UC5 with the existing system, to validate the development.

Performance and Effectiveness: KER2 performed poorly in UC5 – it served its intended function, but without seamless integration. In UC5 operational context it can definitely help to improve data management or interoperability.

Integration and Compatibility: KER2 integration in UC5 was difficult – significant challenges or system changes were necessary.

Market Potential and Demand: CAP expects market demand for the LPC to be moderate to high, with some barriers tackling and market development actions needed. The main customer segments identified are aggregators, DSO, TSO, charging point operators, and REC managing entities. The main barrier, based on UC5, might be the competitive landscape, with strong presence of alternative solutions potentially limiting market entry. For UC6 the main barrier might be the lack of stakeholder confidence and hesitancy from key industry players or end-users.

Recommendations for Improvement: Additional features or functionalities to be considered for KER2 include other protocols converters beyond MQTT and ModBUS. The solution is nevertheless considered well aligned with industry needs and standards and ready for use.

Comparative Assessment: When compared to the other KERs stemming from InterSTORE activities, CAP sees KER2 as having the second highest potential of being successfully exploited. When ranking the KERs based on the scale of their development needs (from highest to lowest), KER2 is positioned in the fourth place according to UC5 and UC6.

UC9: Management of EV Charging Clusters as HESS

Relevance and Applicability: The LPC is moderately relevant for UC9 and it was used to translate the Modbus/IEEE 2030.5 protocol in MQTT. In the operational context of UC9, the LPC was required to implement a release for ENX, enabling registration on the ENX platform and establishing a secure connection through Infocert certificate exchange. In addition, the LPC application includes asset tag management functionality.

Performance and Effectiveness: ENX, UC9 owner, considers the performance of KER2 excellent for UC9 needs. The use of the LPC can benefit ENX in the following ways:

- Improve operational efficiency;
- Enhance existing product/services;
- Improve data management or interoperability.

Overall, the LPC met the expectations of ENX, proving to be a powerful tool to enable communication of diverse devices using different protocols.

Integration and Compatibility: The integration of the LPC in UC9 was moderately easy – with some modification and effort required during integration. Any compatibility issues were addressed with tailored development for ENX specific architecture and systems. To be fully operational in the UC9 context, the LPC requires resolving security issues to integrate it into the Information Technology (IT) platform to enable secure Infocert certificate exchange, as well as ad hoc software developments to adapt the LPC to the IT platforms.

Market Potential and Demand: ENX expects market demand for KER2 to be moderate – interest exists but adoption maybe limited by certain barriers. Customer segments include all energy systems related sectors. The main barrier to market entry or adoption might be the regulatory or policy constraints, such as compliance with industry standards, legal requirements, or lack of supportive policies. The potential of the protocol to reach widespread use might also prove to be a critical barrier for the LPC market access.

Recommendations for Improvement: To improve the exploitation potential of KER2 it is fundamental to increment the variety of protocols supported. No specific feedback on additional features or functionalities has been provided. To secure alignment with industry needs and standards, as stated above, extension to other protocols is critical.

Comparative Assessment: When compared to the other KERs stemming from InterSTORE activities, KER2 has the second highest potential of being successfully exploited. The LPC is

useful in specific fields where protocol conversion is required. When ranking the KERs based on the scale of their development needs (from highest to lowest), before they can be commercially or practically exploited, KER2 is positioned in the second place and to overcome this, it is critical to better tailor it to a target/segment of customers.

Feedback on performance from UCs: KER3

UC1: DES Flexibility Market Monetisation & UC2: Energy community DES utilisation

Relevance and Applicability: The TPST is not relevant for UC1 and UC2 and it was not implemented by CYG.

Performance and Effectiveness: Since KER3 was not implemented in UC1 and UC2, little feedback was provided to assess its performance and effectiveness. If it were to be applied, the TPST would benefit CYG in the following ways:

- Support regulatory compliance or reporting;
- Facilitate entry into new markets;
- Contribute to sustainability or Environmental, Social and Governance (ESG) goals.

Integration and Compatibility: KER3 was not integrated at all in UC1 and UC2 and CYG considers it as a standalone tool non compatible with their software.

Market Potential and Demand: Based on CYG assumptions, market demand for the TPST is expected to be high - considerable demand, but some market development may be needed. Main interested customer segments are regulators and standardisation bodies. The main barrier to market entry could be market readiness - low awareness or demand from potential customers. Additionally, another barrier would be the strong competition and existence of other alternatives.

Recommendations for Improvement: To increase the exploitation potential of KER3, CYG recommends creating a practical guide for self-testing and identifying an accredited body to validate successful test results. Additional features or functionalities to be considered include testing that the implementation of client/server library is working. To ensure that KER3 is better aligned with industry needs and standards, it should aim for getting recognition and trust as reliable testing approach, which users can rely on.

Comparative Assessment: When compared to the other KERs stemming from InterSTORE activities, KER3 has the second least potential of being successfully exploited, based on assumptions of CYG. This is justified by the fact that it is lacking strong regulatory support needed to enhance its visibility. When ranking the KERs based on the scale of their development needs (from highest to lowest), before they can be commercially or practically exploited, KER3 is positioned in the first place as it needs to be expanded on all IEEE 2030.5 attributes.

UC3: Grid Supporting BESS & UC8: Multiphysics Flexibility Optimisation for Home Management Systems and their Global Integration

Relevance and Applicability: The TPST is slightly relevant for UC3 and not relevant for UC8. Therefore, it was not used.

Performance and Effectiveness; Integration and Compatibility: Since the TPST was not used, no feedback was provided.

Market Potential and Demand: According to UC8 and UC3 perspective, market demand for KER3 is expected to be high - considerable demand, but some market development may be needed. According to FZJ and EATON, the main customer segments should be utilities, inverter and EMS manufacturers as well as operators of already existing systems. The main barriers to market entry or adoption might be regulatory or policy constraints (compliance with industry standards, legal requirements, or lack of supportive policies) and market readiness, such as low awareness or demand from potential customers.

Recommendations for Improvement: To increase the exploitation potential of the TPST, FZJ recommends to expand this framework to ease applicability also for testing the LPC.

Comparative Assessment: When compared to the other KERs stemming from InterSTORE activities, KER3 has the lowest potential of being successfully exploited, according to both UC3 and UC8 owners. When ranking KERs based on the scale of their development needs, KER3 is positioned in the first and second place.

UC4: Innovative Frequency Services & UC7: Adaptive BESS Management for Autonomous Grid Operation

Relevance and Applicability: The TPST is not relevant for UC4 and moderately relevant for UC7. In UC4, the testing tools were used to validate the performance of high-speed services like virtual inertia and peak shaving. The procedures helped benchmark the response times and effectiveness of the system when compared to a CAN-based setup, ensuring the LPC and interoperable tools met required performance levels. Different KPIs like RoCoF and Nadir have been used for detailed validation. In UC7, the application was very similar, but with a focus on speed services, such as voltage dip test and Automatic Transfer Switch Test (ATS) test.

Performance and Effectiveness; Integration and Compatibility: Since the TPST was not used extensively enough, no feedback was provided.

Market Potential and Demand: Based on HES expertise, the market demand for the TPST is considered high, but some market development actions may be needed. The customer segments/industries that would benefit the most are system operators in the EU and beyond. At the current stage of development, the main barrier to market entry or adoption might be technical challenges, such as integration difficulties, scalability issues, or need for further development.

Recommendations for Improvement: No additional recommendations for improvement were put forward by HES, based on UC4 and UC7 experience.

Comparative Assessment: When compared to the other KERs stemming from InterSTORE activities, KER3 has the third highest potential of being successfully exploited. When ranking the KERs based on the scale of their development needs (from highest to lowest), KER3 is positioned in the third/fourth place for UC4 and UC7, respectively.

UC5: Hybrid Floating Storage Flexibility Monitoring & UC6: Management of Battery systems for Node Capacity Increase in REC

Relevance and Applicability: The TPST is not relevant for UC5 and UC6.

Performance and Effectiveness; Integration and Compatibility: Since the TPST was not used, no feedback was provided.

Market Potential and Demand: CAP expects market demand for the TPST to be low/very low - limited demand with significant challenges for market adoption or, in a worst-case scenario, no clear market need or adoption potential. The main customer segments could be testing laboratories. The main barriers might be the competitive landscape, with strong presence of alternative solutions potentially limiting market entry and lack of stakeholder confidence and hesitancy from key industry players or end-users.

Recommendations for Improvement: To ensure that KER3 is better aligned with industry needs and standards, CAP mentions for UC5 easier use of the testing procedures and fostered application by testing entities in UC6.

Comparative Assessment: When compared to the other KERs stemming from InterSTORE activities, CAP sees KER3 as having the least potential of being successfully exploited. When ranking the KERs based on the scale of their development needs (from highest to lowest), KER3 is positioned in the first place. However, both rankings are conditioned by the fact that the TPST has not been extensively used in these UCs.

UC9: Management of EV Charging Clusters as HESS

Relevance and Applicability: The TPST is moderately relevant for UC9 and it was used to test E2E flows. In the operational context of UC9, the TPST was not addressing any specific problem.

Performance and Effectiveness: ENX, UC9 owner, considers the performance of KER3 good for UC9 needs. The use of the TPST can benefit ENX in the following ways:

- Improve operational efficiency;
- Enhance existing product/services;
- Improve data management or interoperability.

Overall, the TPST went beyond the expectations of ENX, proving its usefulness as a tool for testing purposes and also in providing the results of the tests of IEEE 2030.5 client-server integration in ENX LAB

Integration and Compatibility: The integration of the TPST in UC9 was moderately easy - with some modification and effort required during the process. No specific compatibility issues were encountered. To be fully operational in the UC9 context, the TPST does not require any tailored modifications.

Market Potential and Demand: ENX expects market demand for KER3 to be moderate - interest exists but adoption may be limited by certain barriers. Customer segments include mainly B2B. The main barrier to market entry or adoption might be the competitive landscape, due to the strong presence of alternative solutions limiting market entry. Other critical market barriers might be resistance to change or the complexity of the procedure itself. By expanding beyond the testing of IEEE 2030.5, the TPST can be an umbrella for testing different protocols because of its modular design.

Recommendations for Improvement: To improve the exploitation potential of KER3 it is fundamental to include more test cases and uses. No specific feedback on additional features or functionalities has been provided. To secure alignment with industry needs and standards, a more user-friendly interface is critical.

Comparative Assessment: When compared to the other KERs stemming from InterSTORE activities, KER3 has the third highest potential of being successfully exploited. The exploitation potential of the TPST highly depends on the identification of a specific target customer

that would significantly appreciate its functionalities. When ranking the KERs based on the scale of their development needs (from highest to lowest), before they can be commercially or practically exploited, KER3 is positioned in the third place. According to ENX, the TPST is to be categorised already as a commercial product. The TPST development has included back end IEEE2030.5 server that can be used in production.

Feedback on performance from UCs: KER4

UC1: DES Flexibility Market Monetisation & UC2: Energy Community DES Utilisation

Relevance and Applicability: The DSC is slightly relevant for UC1 and UC2. In the context of these UCs, via the DSC, the Flexibility Management Platform sends DSO balancing offers. KER4 addresses the need for a new approach to sharing data, that is fast and secure.

Performance and Effectiveness: UC1 and UC2 owner considers KER4 performance in achieving the desired outcomes of the UCs as good. The use of the DSC can benefit CYG in the following ways:

- Improve operational efficiency;
- Enable new product/services or business models;
- Improve data management or interoperability.

KER4 overall met the expectations defined for UC1 and UC2. This data-sharing approach appears to be well-designed and practical. However, since the CyberNoc Flexibility Management Platform is based on Kubernetes, deploying a Docker component alongside it introduced significant challenges. Consequently, the implementation process was far from straightforward for CYG.

Integration and Compatibility: KER4 integration proved to be difficult, since significant challenges were met and system changes were necessary. The compatibility issues encountered were mitigated by bridging the operational differences between Kubernetes and Docker; however, running the two systems side by side continues to pose a challenge. To be fully operational in UC1 and UC2, it is crucial to run open data spaces as code and not as container.

Market Potential and Demand: Based on CYG assumptions, market demand for the TPST is expected to be high - considerable demand, but some market development maybe needed. Main interested customer segments are energy market participants. The main barrier to market entry could be the competitive landscape, with strong presence of alternative solutions limiting market entry.

Recommendations for Improvement: To increase the exploitation potential of KER4, CYG recommends enabling different implementation options. No additional features or functionalities to be considered were identified by CYG. To ensure that KER3 is better aligned with industry needs and standards, it should aim for being the best at one aspect: either simplicity of implementation or security of communication or be the most interoperable solution on the market.

Comparative Assessment: When compared to the other KERs stemming from InterSTORE activities, KER4 has the second least potential of being successfully exploited, based on assumptions of CYG. This is justified by the fact that there is a lot of competition in this segment. When ranking the KERs based on the scale of their development needs (from highest to lowest), before they can be commercially or practically exploited, KER4 is positioned in the third place, but there is only one option of implementation that works.

UC3: Grid Supporting BESS & UC8: Multiphysics Flexibility Optimisation for Home Management Systems and their Global Integration

Relevance and Applicability: The DSC is not relevant for UC8, but highly relevant for UC3. In the latter, this KER has been deployed on a dedicated system to provide/consume services with/from partners. Particularly, FZJ shared data collected on their pilot site from the two battery systems integrated by means of the InterSTORE solution. In the context of UC3, the DSC enhances the possibility to easily share data with external partners, while maintaining control on authorised access.

Performance and Effectiveness: While it was not used in UC8, in UC3 the DSC performed excellently. The use of the DSC can benefit FZJ in the following ways:

- Improve operational efficiency;
- Reduce cost or resource consumption;
- Enhance existing product/services;
- Enable new product/services or business models;
- Strengthen competitive advantage;
- Improve data management or interoperability;
- Create new revenue streams.

KER4 overall met the expectations defined for UC3. The tool proved to work as expected when it comes to the possibility of providing/consuming services while maintaining control on the authorisations.

Integration and Compatibility: KER4 integration proved to be moderately easy and only some modifications and effort were required during the integration. Initial difficulties in integrating the tool in the system (due to specific safety requirements on the pilot) were solved discussing implementation solutions with ENG. The DSC does not require additional modifications to be fully operational in UC3.

Market Potential and Demand: Based on FZJ and EAT assumptions, market demand for the DSC is expected to be high - considerable demand, but some market development may be needed. Main interested customer segments are aggregators. The main barriers to market entry could be market readiness - low awareness or demand from potential customers - and lack of stakeholder confidence - hesitancy from key industry players or end-users.

Recommendations for Improvement: Additional features or functionalities identified by FZJ include improving local data management to facilitate data transfer during container updates, as well as enabling the deletion or modification of previously provided data.

Comparative Assessment: When compared to the other KERs stemming from InterSTORE activities, KER4 has the first/second potential of being successfully exploited, based on assumptions of FZJ and EAT. According to the latter, the DSC is enabler of a wide range of applications. When ranking the KERs based on the scale of their development needs (from highest to lowest), before they can be commercially or practically exploited, KER4 is positioned in the fourth place.

UC4: Innovative Frequency Services & UC7: Adaptive BESS Management for Autonomous Grid Operation

Relevance and Applicability: The DSC is not relevant for UC4 and slightly relevant for UC7. As the focus of UC4 was fast event and high-power short-term services, the DSC was not

directly used for real-time control. While in UC7, the developed tool supported the sharing of performance data and configuration files.

Performance and Effectiveness; Integration and Compatibility: The use of the DSC was not extensive enough to evaluate its performance and effectiveness, as well as integration and compatibility matters, in the two UCs.

Market Potential and Demand: Based on HES assumptions, market demand for the DSC is expected to be high - considerable demand, but some market development maybe needed. Main interested customer segments are system operators. The main barrier to market entry could be technical challenges, such as integration difficulties, scalability issues, or need for further development

Recommendations for Improvement: No specific recommendations for the improvement of the DSC were provided by HES.

Comparative Assessment: When compared to the other KERs stemming from InterSTORE activities, KER4 has the least potential of being successfully exploited, based on assumptions of HES. When ranking the KERs based on the scale of their development needs (from highest to lowest), before they can be commercially or practically exploited, KER4 is positioned in the second position when UC4 is concerned and in the last position in the context of UC7.

UC5: Hybrid Floating Storage Flexibility Monitoring & UC6: Management of Battery Systems for Node Capacity Increase in REC

Relevance and Applicability: The DSC is moderately relevant for UC5 and UC6. In both UCs it was used for data sharing (e.g., from EV charging events in UC6). In UC5, the DSC was applied to address the problem of trusted, data sharing, enabling data sovereignty. Similarly, in UC6 it was an efficient way of sharing data with interested parties.

Performance and Effectiveness: The DSC performed excellently in UC5 and well in UC6. This KER can benefit the two UCs in the following ways:

- Reduce cost or resource consumption;
- Enable new product/services or business models;
- Improve data management or interoperability;
- Create new revenue streams;
- Contribute to sustainability or ESG goals;
- Facilitate data sharing.

KER4 overall met the expectations defined for UC5 and UC6. The tool was easy to use and data was shared without difficulties.

Integration and Compatibility: KER4 integration proved to be very easy - seamless integration with no modification required - in UC5. However, difficulties were encountered - significant challenges or system changes were necessary - when integrating it into UC6. Overall, the DSC does not require additional modifications to be fully operational in UC5 and UC6.

Market Potential and Demand: CAP expects market demand for the DSC in UC5 to be high - considerable demand, but some market development maybe needed - and low - limited demand with significant challenges for market adoption - in UC6. The main customer segments are expected to be aggregators, DSO, TSO, charging point operators, REC managing entities, industry overall and cooperatives. The main barriers might be technical challenges - integration difficulties, scalability issues, or need for further development - and lack of stakeholder confidence - hesitancy from key industry players or end-users.

Recommendations for Improvement: To enhance the exploitation potential of the DSC, it is essential to extend the deployment of data space connectors to end users. Further improvement could be achieved by enhancing the timeline feature to provide greater clarity and usability. To ensure that KER4 is better aligned with industry needs and standards, CAP mentions for UC5 to avoid that the tool is limited to static IP addresses.

Comparative Assessment: When compared to the other KERs stemming from InterSTORE activities, CAP sees KER4 as having the highest potential of being successfully exploited in UC5, due to its remarkable development level and feasible use cases, and the second least potential in UC6. When ranking the KERs based on the scale of their development needs (from highest to lowest), KER4 is positioned in the last place. The DSC seems to be the most developed and user friendly.

UC9: Management of EV charging clusters as HESS

Relevance and Applicability: The DSC is highly relevant for UC9 and it was used to exchange data with partners.

Performance and Effectiveness: ENX, UC9 owner, considers the performance of KER4 good for UC9 needs. The use of the DSC can benefit ENX in the following ways:

- Enhance existing product/services;
- Enable new product/services or business models;
- Improve data management or interoperability;
- Create new revenue streams.

Overall, the DSC met ENX's expectations. This tool has the potential to enhance additional use cases and generate further revenue by enabling the activation of new services.

Integration and Compatibility: The integration of the DSC in UC9 met some difficulties, meaning that significant challenges or system changes were necessary. Specific compatibility challenges arose due to the lengthy process of deploying the software on a cloud environment compliant with cybersecurity requirements. For full operational deployment within the UC9 context, the DSC needs specific modifications concerning user access roles and the configuration of virtual machines.

Market Potential and Demand: ENX expects market demand for KER4 to be very high - strong market interest with clear demand and adaptation potential. Customer segments include mainly B2B. The main barrier to market entry or adoption might be the lack of stakeholder confidence, with hesitancy from key industry players or end-users. Another critical market barrier might be data privacy issues.

Recommendations for Improvement: To enhance the exploitation potential of KER4, it is essential to identify and document the use cases arising from data exchange. No specific feedback on additional features or functionalities has been provided. To secure alignment with industry needs and standards, it is critical to highlight with examples the potential of implementing new businesses.

Comparative Assessment: When compared to the other KERs stemming from InterSTORE activities, KER4 has the highest potential of being successfully exploited. A significant added value of the DSC is its suitability for use in various fields. When ranking the KERs based on the scale of their development needs (from highest to lowest), before they can be commercially or practically exploited, KER4 is positioned in the fourth place. According to ENX, the DSC is to be categorised already as a commercial product.

8.4 Annex – Standardisation Matrix

Matrix IEC and CENELEC TC/SC/WG with InterSTORE WP

1 = awareness
2 = follow
3 = contribution

Technical Committee (TC) Subcommittee (SC) Working Group (WG)	Title of TC/SC/WG	Key words (TC/SC/WG)	WP	InterSTORE WP1	InterSTORE WP2	InterSTORE WP3	InterSTORE WP4	InterSTORE WP5	InterSTORE WP6
			Title	Requirements, Use Cases, Specifications	Open-Source Interoperability Toolkit	Dimensioning, Testing and Integration	Multiservice and Flexibility Monetization	Pilots Demonstration	Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation
			Key words (WP)	-identify user acceptance -hybrid storage use cases -specify tools + software	-develop toolkit + interoperable client/server for DES + legacy systems protocol converter	-methodology for HESS -integrate software tools -validation in lab	-new EMS to provide HESS -energy data space technology enabler -user acceptance	-testing procedure -integrate software + products in ICT infrastructure -collect test data	-promotion + transfer to stakeholders -collaboration with similar projects -IPR
IEC/TC 8	System aspects of electrical energy supply	power systems		2	3	2	1	3	1
WG 11	Power Quality	control, protection, grid integration, frequency		2	3	2	1	3	1
SC 8A	Grid Integration of Renewable Energy Generation	connection requirements, grid integration		2	3	2	1	3	1
-WG 2	Renewable energy power prediction	forecast, benchmarking, prognosis, renewables		2	3	2	1	3	1
-WG 6	Connection of Renewable Energy with HVDC System	HVDS, system, TSO		2	3	2	1	3	1
-WG 7	Integrating distributed PV into DC systems and use cases	renewables, grid integration		3	3	2	1	3	1
-WG 8	Modeling of renewable energy generation for power system dynamic analysis	modeling, simulation		2	3	2	1	3	1
SC 8B	Decentralized electrical energy systems	renewables, grid integration, DSO		2	3	2	1	3	1
-WG 3	Microgrid monitoring, control and energy management systems	islanding, generation, market, emergency, renewables, virtual power plants		2	3	2	1	3	1
-WG 4	Virtual Power Plants	generation, market, emergency, renewables, microgrids		2	3	2	1	3	1
-WG 5	Direct current and hybrid distribution systems	DSO, grid integration		2	3	2	1	3	1
-WG 6	Demand side resources utilization	market, renewables, demand response, flexibility		2	3	2	1	3	1
-WG 8	Decentralized multiple energy systems	flexibility, renewables, grid integration		2	3	2	1	3	1
SC 8C	Network management in Interconnected Electric Power Systems	DSO, grid integration, renewables		2	3	2	1	3	1
-WG 2	Electricity market integration	market, renewables, demand response, flexibility		2	3	2	1	3	1
-WG 3	Power system stability and security in planning, design, operation and control	grid integration, frequency, voltage		2	3	2	1	3	1
-WG 4	Power system resilience	resilience, renewables, DSO		2	3	2	1	3	1
-WG 6	Carbon Emission Management in Interconnected Electric Power Systems	emission, renewables, grid integration		2	3	2	1	3	1
-WG 7	Electric power system restoration	system restoration, resilience, renewables, DSO		2	3	2	1	3	1
-WG 8C-1	Guidelines for inertia management of renewable penetrated power system-Part1: Framework design	flexibility, grid integration, frequency, voltage		2	3	2	1	3	1
CLC/TC 8x	System Aspects of Electrical Energy Supply	power systems		2	3	2	1	3	1
WG 1	Physical characteristics of electrical energy (former BTTF 68-6)	voltage, frequency, public distribution networks		2	3	2	1	3	1
WG 3	Requirements for connection of generators to distribution networks	connection requirements, protection, grid integration, frequency		2	3	2	1	3	1
WG 6	System aspects for HVDC grid	HVDS, system, TSO		2	3	2	1	3	1

8.5 Annex – KERs Detailed Contribution to InterSTORE UCs Business Models

KER1: Interoperable client/server library

UC1: DES Flexibility Market Monetisation & UC2: Energy community DES utilisation

Utility & Target Users

In UC1 and UC2, KER1 enables efficient data exchange between distributed energy assets and the CYG Flexibility Management Platform, supporting communication via IEEE 2030.5. This enhances interoperability, allowing aggregators, EMS operators, and community managers to efficiently integrate DERs and coordinate flexibility or self-consumption services. By simplifying communication and integration, KER1 could strengthen both market participation (UC1) and local energy autonomy (UC2).

TLBMC

Economic Layer

For UC1 and UC2, KER1 could contribute to the deployment of economically viable and scalable DERs across multiple market contexts. By ensuring interoperability and compliance with the IEEE 2030.5 standard, KER1 can enable cost-effective integration of diverse DER assets into the CYG Flexibility-as-a-Service (FaaS) platform [3]. This interoperability can reduce integration costs, facilitating broader participation of prosumers, aggregators, and communities in energy and flexibility markets. In UC1, KER1 could support the economic layer by enabling real-time communication and data exchange necessary for automated market participation, dynamic pricing, and ancillary service provision, thereby improving revenue optimisation and for commercial and industrial users. In UC2, it could support the creation of local energy trading frameworks and peer-to-peer flexibility exchanges, enhance community self-sufficiency and reduce reliance on centralised systems [4] [5] [6].

Social Layer

KER1 could be a digital enabler of participation, inclusivity, and trust across both UC1 and UC2. By ensuring interoperable communication and efficient data exchange, KER1 may support the social transition from passive consumption to active prosumer engagement. In UC1, this interoperability fosters transparent market participation by providing users with clear visibility of their assets, revenues, and flexibility potential – thereby fostering energy literacy and democratised access to market benefits. This is in line with recent research on the evolution of the “active prosumer” and energy democratisation [7] [8]. In UC2, KER1 facilitates collective energy management and local governance, allowing communities to interact with real-time energy data and make joint decisions based on shared values and sustainability goals [9] [10]. Through its standardised, open design, KER1 could indirectly lower in future technical and economic barriers to entry, mitigating social inequalities linked to digital access or proprietary systems.

Environmental Layer

KER1 could also contribute to the materialisation of the environmental value of both UC1 and UC2. Through the adoption of open communication protocols (e.g., IEEE 2030.5), KER1 facilitates real-time coordination and optimisation of DERs, facilitating higher renewable energy integration and reduced curtailment of variable resources. In UC1, this capability could directly support grid decarbonisation by ensuring that flexibility dispatch decisions incorporate carbon intensity metrics and lifecycle environmental performance indicators, thus aligning

technical operation with emissions reduction objectives. In UC2, KER1 could strengthen local environmental autonomy by supporting interoperable control of community-based energy storage and generation assets. This promotes self-consumption of renewables, lower transmission losses, and smarter resource allocation at the community scale, in line with research on decentralised energy systems and environmental justice [11] [12]. The standardisation introduced by KER1 also facilitates environmental traceability, embracing transparent tracking of system efficiency, component reuse, and end-of-life management.

UC4: Innovative Frequency Services & UC7: Adaptive BESS Management for Autonomous Grid Operation

Utility & Target Users

KER1 could strengthen the utility of UC4 and UC7 by enabling standardised communication and coordination among HESS, control units, and grid operators. This interoperability supports advanced services such as frequency regulation, virtual inertia, and autonomous grid operation, improving grid stability under high renewable penetration. For TSOs/DSOs, it could support in providing fast-response flexibility and new ancillary services; aggregators can monetise hybrid assets in balancing markets; and industrial or campus users benefit from increased reliability and resilience [19] [20] [21] [22] [23] [24] [25] [26].

TLBMC

Economic Layer

The use of KER1 could contribute to strengthening the economic value of UC4 and UC7 in the long-term by enabling standardised, low-latency communication between HESS, DERs, and market platforms. Through compliance with IEEE 2030.5 and integration with HyDEMS, KER1 can support hybrid assets in efficiently exchanging operational data with TSOs, DSOs, and aggregators, ensuring that flexibility services can be efficiently validated, priced, and remunerated [27] [28] [20] [19]. This interoperability could indirectly contribute to reducing transaction and integration costs typically associated with connecting heterogeneous storage systems and markets, accelerating market entry for hybrid flexibility providers. It could also support in increasing the monetisation potential of frequency response, virtual inertia, and balancing services by supporting hybrid systems in participating in multiple markets concurrently under harmonised data protocols [29] [30].

Social Layer

KER1, whenever applied, may indirectly strengthen the social dimension of UC4 and UC7 by enabling transparent, reliable, and secure communication between hybrid energy assets, operators, and end users [31] [32]. Through its interoperable architecture, based on IEEE 2030.5, it may ensure that data exchanges within HESS are traceable, auditable, and easily interpretable. This transparency could enhance user trust, stakeholder confidence, and the overall social acceptance of digitalised flexibility solutions [32]. Moreover, by ensuring standardised communication across platforms, KER1 can support system operators, communities, and commercial users in accessing consistent and understandable information on energy performance and flexibility provision. This fosters, in the long term, greater user empowerment and engagement, as participants in hybrid or autonomous grid environments can make informed decisions based on reliable data [5]. Moreover, the library's secure design might mitigate one of the key social risks associated with digital infrastructures - cybersecurity and data privacy [5] [33] - by enabling trustworthy information sharing without compromising sensitive data.

Environmental Layer

KER1 might indirectly enhance the environmental performance of UC4 and UC7 by enabling more efficient and coordinated operation of HESS. Through standardised and efficient data exchange, the library can support precise monitoring and optimisation of energy flows, minimising inefficiencies that lead to unnecessary energy losses. This interoperability ensures that renewable generation can be integrated and utilised to its fullest extent, thereby reducing curtailment and the reliance on fossil-based balancing reserves [34]. Moreover, KER1's interoperability framework could contribute to lifecycle sustainability by improving the management and predictive maintenance of hybrid assets.

KER2: Legacy system protocol converter

UC3: Grid Supporting BESS & UC8: Multiphysics Flexibility Optimisation for Home Management Systems and their Global Integration

Utility & Target Users

In UC3 and UC8, KER2 could play a significant role in enabling interoperability across heterogeneous systems, consequently expanding the range of users who can effectively participate in energy management and flexibility services. By translating legacy communication protocols such as Modbus and MQTT into the IEEE 2030.5 standard, the LPC allows distributed assets - such as batteries, photovoltaic (PV) systems, and heat pumps - to efficiently connect with advanced EMS platforms and hybrid optimisation tools. This interoperability could significantly reduce technical integration barriers for DSOs, campus operators, and building managers [39] [40], enabling faster deployment and lower operational costs. For technology providers and aggregators [41] [42] [27], KER2 could act as a bridge between legacy infrastructure and new digital ecosystems, supporting multi-asset coordination without requiring costly hardware upgrades. End users, including prosumers and energy community members [4] [37], would benefit indirectly through improved reliability, reduced energy costs, and greater access to flexibility markets. Overall, through its application in UC3 and UC8, KER2 may improve the usability and inclusiveness of interoperable energy systems, facilitating the integration of legacy assets into modern digital energy architectures.

TLBMC

Economic Layer

In UC3 and UC8, KER2 - if applied - could directly support the economic viability of interoperable energy systems by reducing integration costs and accelerating deployment timelines. Acting as a middleware, the LPC eliminates the need for expensive proprietary gateways and extensive re-engineering, potentially leading to reductions in engineering hours and overall project Capital Expenditures (CAPEX) [41] [42] [27]. By standardising communication across diverse assets, KER2 also mitigates the risk of vendor lock-in [41] [42] [43] [44] [33], thereby creating long-term operational and investment flexibility for integrators, DSOs, and technology providers. The tool could enable faster market participation for grid-supporting assets. In residential and community contexts, its interoperability functions could indirectly drive cost savings for end users through improved optimisation and reduced grid dependency.

Social Layer

Within UC3 and UC8, by translating legacy communication protocols into the IEEE 2030.5 standard, the LPC could enable older and heterogeneous devices to participate in modern energy platforms, reducing technological exclusion. This inclusiveness promotes fairer access to the benefits of digitalisation and distributed flexibility, particularly for small-scale operators and communities that rely on existing infrastructure [37] [31] [32]. For engineers

and installers, KER2 could reduce integration complexity while simultaneously building demand for new digital skills related to interoperability standards and data governance. Its open-source nature under the MIT licence might encourage collaboration and capacity building within technical communities, supporting the creation of local expertise and green jobs [45] [46]. At the community level, interoperability supported by the LPC enhances reliability and user confidence, contributing indirectly to energy literacy and acceptance of digital tools [47] [48] [49].

Environmental Layer

In UC3 and UC8, KER2 could contribute to environmental sustainability by extending the useful life of existing energy assets and minimising the material footprint associated with new hardware deployment. By enabling legacy systems to communicate through modern, standardised protocols such as IEEE 2030.5, the LPC eliminates the need to replace functioning equipment solely for compatibility reasons, thereby reducing electronic waste and embodied emissions linked to manufacturing and installation [50] [51]. Furthermore, by facilitating the integration and coordination of distributed renewable energy resources - such as batteries, PV, and heat pumps - KER2 indirectly supports higher renewable penetration and reduced reliance on fossil-based backup generation. Improved interoperability might also reduce system inefficiencies, enabling more precise demand-response operations that lower overall energy consumption and emissions [52] [53].

KER3: Testing procedure and software tool

UC9 - Management of EV Charging Clusters as HESS

Utility & Target Users

In the context of UC9 business model, KER3 could reinforce the reliability and market readiness of VPP operations by ensuring that communication between aggregated DERs and system operators complies with IEEE 2030.5 standards. The TPST's automated validation and reporting features might enable TSOs, BSPs, and EMS developers to verify interoperability and performance before deployment, reducing integration risk and certification costs. By facilitating standard-compliant communication across EV charging clusters, KER3 could strengthen the confidence of market actors - particularly TSOs, aggregators, and grid operators - in the technical robustness of flexibility services.

TLBMC

Economic Layer

In the context of UC9, KER3 could strengthen the economic performance of flexibility market operations by reducing integration, validation, and compliance costs. Through automated testing and reporting of IEEE 2030.5 communication processes, the TPST could minimise the need for manual verification during DER aggregation and VPP deployment. From a revenue perspective, KER3 contributes indirectly by increasing reliability and trust in interoperability. The tool's capacity to validate new DER configurations before deployment helps avoid costly errors and downtime, ensuring continuous service provision and higher operational uptime for aggregators like ENX. By supporting standard compliance in a fully automated, open-source framework, KER3 can provide a scalable quality-assurance layer that enhances the business case for digitalised flexibility management in the EV and distributed energy domains.

Social Layer

Within UC9, KER3 could also indirectly reinforce social trust and governance quality in flexibility markets by ensuring standard-compliant communication between distributed assets and the grid. Through automated validation of IEEE 2030.5 interactions, the TPST could support more ethical and accountable digital infrastructure, strengthening confidence in the reliability of VPP operations [64]. Moreover, KER3's open-source and cross-platform design could enhance digital accessibility and capacity-building, empowering technical staff and market operators to independently test and certify device compliance.

Environmental Layer

KER3 could indirectly contribute to the environmental performance of by improving the reliability, efficiency, and sustainability of DER and EV integration processes. Through automated testing and validation of IEEE 2030.5 communication, the TPST reduces the need for repeated manual testing, thereby potentially minimising resource consumption, time, and energy use across deployment cycles. By ensuring consistent and interoperable communication between distributed assets, KER3 also helps prevent system inefficiencies that can result in unnecessary energy waste or curtailment of renewable generation. In this sense, the tool strengthens the environmental value of VPPs and hybrid systems by enabling more precise, standards-compliant operation. Moreover, its open-source and virtualised nature could reduce dependency on hardware-intensive testing infrastructures, contributing to a lower-impact digital ecosystem that supports decarbonisation and sustainable grid management.

KER4: InterSTORE Data Space Connector

UC3: Grid Supporting BESS

Utility & Target Users

If applied to support the deployment of UC3, the DSC could strengthen the utility of grid-supporting BESS by enabling secure, standardised, and decentralised data exchange among involved entities. By leveraging its key features - such as IDS-based Data Spaces and blockchain - the DSC ensures that energy and operational data can be shared transparently, traceably, and under controlled access conditions, reinforcing trust and regulatory compliance. The tool directly benefits DSOs, aggregators [39] [40], and technology providers who require verified and interoperable data exchange to operate and monetise distributed assets [41] [42] [27]. It could also support research and innovation actors, allowing them to better integrate and analyse real-world BESS performance data.

TLBMC

Economic Layer

In UC3, KER4 could enhance the economic value of interoperability by reducing data management and integration costs while enabling new revenue models built on trusted data exchange [41] [42] [43] [44] [29]. By automating secure data sharing through decentralised architectures, the DSC eliminates the need for multiple manual processes, leading to potential operational efficiency gains for aggregators and DSOs. From a market perspective, KER4 may create opportunities for monetising energy and performance data through service subscriptions or data-driven analytics, opening new revenue streams for technology providers and operators. By supporting standardised interoperability across partners, it

could also contribute to reducing vendor lock-in and foster economies of scale in digital energy markets.

Social Layer

In UC3, KER4 could also indirectly strengthen the social dimension of interoperability by promoting transparency, accountability, and trust in data-driven energy collaboration. Through secure and permission-based data sharing, the DSC may empower stakeholders - including DSOs, technology providers, and research partners - to exchange information with confidence, ensuring that sensitive operational data remains under full control of its owner [47] [48] [49]. Moreover, by simplifying access to verified performance data, KER4 encourages knowledge exchange and collaboration across organisations, fostering a culture of openness and innovation. Its role in ensuring data sovereignty also aligns with the principles of energy democracy and digital responsibility, enabling participants to contribute to grid-supporting services without compromising privacy or control. Over time, this contributes to promoting higher stakeholder engagement, inclusion, and confidence in interoperable digital energy ecosystems [16] [18] [67].

Environmental Layer

In UC3, KER4 could indirectly contribute also to environmental sustainability by optimising data flows needed for grid-supporting BESS operations and renewable energy integration. Through its decentralised and interoperable architecture, the DSC facilitates accurate, real-time data exchange between systems, enabling more efficient management of distributed assets and reducing unnecessary energy losses. Additionally, by supporting more data-driven decision-making and performance monitoring, KER4 could help in the long term to identify inefficiencies, extend asset lifetimes, and reduce resource waste [26] [38] [68].

UC5 - Hybrid Floating Storage Flexibility Monitoring

Utility & Target Users

In UC5, if applied, KER4 can strengthen the overall utility of HESS [73] [74] by enabling trusted and standardised data exchange among DSOs, aggregators, and microgrid operators managing multi-technology assets such as Li-ion, vanadium flow, and second-life batteries. The DSC ensures secure interoperability and data sovereignty, allowing stakeholders to share performance, lifetime, and environmental data without compromising confidentiality. For UC5 target users - particularly regional DSOs, C&I consumers, and policymakers - KER4 might provide a reliable digital framework for validating second-life battery use and promoting transparent circular economy practices [28] [75]. By integrating blockchain-based verification and semantic data catalogues, the DSC supports traceability and compliance with regulatory frameworks on battery reuse, thereby enhancing confidence and scalability of hybrid storage solutions demonstrated in UC5.

TLBMC

Economic Layer

In UC5, KER4 could directly support the economic viability of HESS by streamlining data sharing among DSOs, aggregators, and technology providers involved in the operation and monetisation of Li-ion, vanadium flow, and second-life batteries. By enabling data traceability and access control, KER4 might contribute to lowering the administrative burden associated with certification, reporting, and performance verification - key steps in proving the reliability of second-life assets. Furthermore, KER4 might enhance revenue realisation

by supporting transparent communication of performance data and operational metrics, which are crucial for participating in balancing markets and flexibility services [76].

Social Layer

In UC5, KER4 may reinforce the social legitimacy and acceptance of HESS by ensuring that data related to second-life battery performance, safety, and sustainability is shared transparently and securely among stakeholders. Through its trusted data-exchange architecture, the DSC builds confidence in the reuse of energy storage components, addressing one of the main social barriers to circular economy adoption - public trust in the reliability and safety of repurposed technologies [38] [68]. For communities and policymakers, KER4 enables verifiable reporting on environmental and operational metrics, promoting transparency and accountability. By integrating blockchain-based notarisation and user authentication, it supports traceable data flows, ensuring that second-life batteries meet compliance and warranty standards.

Environmental Layer

In UC5, KER4 might indirectly improve the environmental value of HESS by enabling more efficient and better-quality data exchange on asset performance, lifetime, and resource efficiency. This traceability supports evidence-based sustainability assessments, ensuring that environmental benefits - such as reduced e-waste and lower raw material extraction - are measurable [38] [68]. At system level, the DSC may promote data-driven optimisation of hybrid dispatch strategies, allowing operators to reduce energy losses and extend component lifetime [77] [78].

UC9 - Management of EV Charging Clusters as HESS

Utility & Target Users

In UC9, KER4 can significantly facilitate secure and standardised data exchange between DERs, aggregators, and system operators. Its decentralised and blockchain-enabled architecture supports a reliable flow of operational and flexibility data across multiple actors involved in the VPP setup. For all target users, the DSC is clearly useful: (i) aggregators and BSPs could benefit from improved interoperability and streamlined data sharing with TSOs/DSOs; (ii) system operators get transparent access to flexibility and asset-performance data; (iii) technology providers and EMS developers can integrate new services securely; (iv) prosumers and local communities could benefit indirectly from increased reliability, transparency, and access to market participation.

TLBMC

Economic Layer

In UC9, KER4 could reinforce the economic value of flexibility markets by securing efficient, trusted, and automated data exchange between aggregators, TSOs, and DER operators. From an operational point of view, KER4 could contribute to enhancing market efficiency and scalability by reducing manual data handling and supporting new business models. Aggregators and flexibility service providers could leverage the DSC to monetise data flows and improve revenue from balancing services, while system operators could gain reliable access to validated information that supports more accurate procurement and dispatch decisions. Economically, the DSC might contribute to cost-effectiveness and long-term profitability.

Social Layer

In UC9, KER4 could play a considerable role in building social trust and accountability by ensuring transparent, auditable, and secure data exchanges between DER owners, aggregators, and system operators [64]. Its blockchain-backed transaction notarisation might strengthen confidence among stakeholders that data is both authentic and secure, an essential condition for social acceptance of digital energy markets. At the community level, KER4 could contribute to higher social inclusivity by enabling smaller prosumers and local actors to participate in data-driven flexibility schemes under equal and trusted conditions [84].

Environmental Layer

In UC9, KER4 might indirectly support environmental sustainability and decarbonisation by enabling more efficient data-driven coordination of distributed renewable assets. Through its secure and standardised data exchange, the DSC could facilitate real-time optimisation of energy flows between PV systems, EV chargers, and storage units, maximising renewable utilisation and reducing curtailment. By improving interoperability and transparency in data sharing, KER4 allows system operators and aggregators to better forecast and balance renewable generation, leading to lower reliance on fossil-based balancing resources and reduced grid losses.

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